

UNOBTRUSIVE AND
PERSONALISED MONITORING OF
PARKINSON'S DISEASE
USING SMARTPHONES

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER
FOR THE DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
IN THE FACULTY OF SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

2019

By
Julio E. Vega Hernandez
School of Computer Science

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Abstract

Parkinson's Disease is a neurodegenerative condition with no cure and a wide variety of idiosyncratic motor and non-motor symptoms that impact people's quality of life. In infrequent and short clinical consultations, health care professionals use validated clinical scales that are time-consuming and rely on clinical expertise or patients' perception. Moreover, symptoms can fluctuate within or between days due to the natural progression of the disease or medication and thus, a short session only provides a snapshot and not a longitudinal image of the disease. In practice, it is difficult for clinicians to tailor treatments and medication to each person's symptoms. Therefore, a granular, continuous, and objective methodology to track symptom fluctuations would improve patients' quality of life and make health services more efficient.

The complexity of Parkinson's makes it a challenging but suitable study case to investigate new personalised approaches supported by technology and tailored to each patient's condition. This work aims to explore the use of behavioural inferences extracted from smartphone data to track the fluctuations in Parkinson's Disease symptoms. We recruited 7 participants with early Parkinson's (Hoehn & Yahr scale ≤ 3), instrumented their personal Android and iOS mobiles, and collected a dataset with up to 22 data sources, 24/7, during 222 to 380 days and within the technological, ethical, and UX limitations of a real-world deployment. As part of this dataset, we assessed their symptom severity using four clinical scales and seven cognitive tests every six weeks and patients self-reported the severity of their three main symptoms on a daily basis.

Through an agile iterative design process, we generated knowledge that supports ground truth collection for longitudinal Parkinson's tracking. We identified five design implications for future Parkinson's self-reporting tools. We published PaperStream, an open-source tool to create and encode questionnaires or surveys automatically. Also, we created a paper diary that blends digital and analogue

data collection which participants used to gather daily self-reported symptom severity scores with average answer compliance of 96.39% (SD=0.05) among 7 participants monitored between 222 and 380 days.

We created an adaptative method to track weekly self-reported fluctuations in pain, gait and fatigue, the first one of its kind for Parkinson’s Precision Medicine. Our method adapts to an individual’s condition (personalised) and tracks symptoms while participants carry on with their regular lives (naturalistic), over time (longitudinal) and without people’s input (unobtrusive). Instead of relying on the structure of the collected smartphone data to find patterns, our method starts with a generalised set of predictions based on mobility and activity recognition features that are overfitted to each patient’s symptoms. We showed that this method tracks fluctuations better than chance with an agreement measured by Cohen’s kappa between 0.19 and 0.53 finding a different subset of predictions for each participant. Also, exploring how this method can be deployed in the real world, we show that splitting our dataset into personalisation/testing sets is not a suitable strategy to identify a relevant subset of smartphone features to track symptoms on unseen data.

Our results should be considered under the assumptions we made when we designed our method as well as the three primary sources of error in our methodology: the validity of the smartphone features, the confounders in participants behaviour, and the drawbacks of self-reporting. Nonetheless, this work is evidence that the unobtrusive and personalised monitoring methodology we proposed has the potential to track fluctuations in Parkinson’s symptoms with the most impact on patients’ daily life. Thus, we encourage researchers to tackle questions that remain open: how can we refine the mobility and activity recognition smartphone features we used? What other behavioural areas and smartphone features can be exploited to monitor other motor and non-motor symptoms? What other ground truth collection methods can minimise the problems related to analogue self-reported data? What is the clinical and self-management utility of the weekly fluctuations we tracked with our personalised models? What parameters and models of our method can be improved? Moreover, in the future, how can we include people with Parkinson’s in the development and evaluation of their personalised models?

Declaration

No portion of the work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or other institute of learning.

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Acknowledgements

A Rosa, Julio, Anahí y Rubí por su apoyo incondicional, me hubiera gustado estar más cerca todos estos años pero el amor de familia siempre fue mas grande que la distancia. Si tuve la oportunidad de empezar y terminar esta etapa ha sido gracias a ustedes

A Alla porque todos los días desde el primer día has estado aquí con una sonrisa y un corazón inmenso

To my supervisors, Simon Harper, Markel Vigo, and Caroline Jay for being incredible mentors and friends that believed in me, supported me and showed me the way. All the positive impact my work might have in the future will always be thanks to you all

To the participants of our studies who were always committed, patient and enthusiastic. You are a big source of inspiration and I hope this work is a step towards better Parkinson's care

To my friends from and outside the IAM lab that made this journey unforgettable. To my friends back home that every year reminded me of what a second family means

Finally, I would like to thank Prof. Sonja Kotz, Dr Ellen Poliakoff, Dr Samuel Couth, Dr Manuele Reani, and Dr Glen Martin for their advice at the different stages of this project and the *Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología* and the *Secretaria de Educación Pública* of Mexico as well as the *Medical Research Council Confidence in Concept scheme* for sponsoring this project

Chapter 1

Introduction

This work aims to explore the use of personalised digital phenotyping to track the fluctuations in Parkinson’s Disease symptoms. Digital phenotyping has been defined as the moment-by-moment quantification of individual-level human traits in the wild using data from personal digital devices (Onnela et al., 2016). We quantify human behaviour using features (traces) that we extract from smartphone data (e.g. time spent at home using GPS data) in order to track the fluctuations of self-reported pain, gait and fatigue severity. Our aim is relevant because the complex nature of Parkinson’s symptoms and its traditional clinical assessment make it difficult for clinicians to get an accurate picture of the disease. Therefore, a granular, continuous, and objective methodology to track symptom fluctuations would improve patients’ quality of life and make health services more efficient.

Idiopathic Parkinson’s Disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative disease with a wide variety of idiosyncratic motor and non-motor symptoms that impact people’s quality of life (Chrischilles et al., 1998). This variability makes it a challenging but suitable study case to investigate new Precision Medicine approaches supported by technology and tailored to each patient’s condition (Espay et al., 2016; Riggare et al., 2018).

In infrequent and short clinical consultations, health care professionals use validated clinical scales to quantify the severity of patients’ symptoms (Ramaker et al., 2002). However, symptoms can vary within or between days due to the natural progression of the disease or medication (Espay et al., 2016), and thus, a short session only provides a snapshot and not a longitudinal image of the disease. What is more, the scales used are time-consuming, and rely on clinical expertise or patients’ perception (Del Din et al., 2016; Dorsey et al., 2017; Maetzler et al.,

2016). In practice, it is difficult for clinicians to tailor treatments and medication to each person's symptoms (Sung et al., 2005; Tzallas et al., 2014) and they are often adjusted over time based on the clinician's judgement and patients' daily experience.

The need for appropriate technologies in PD healthcare is recognised by the International Parkinson and Movement Disorders Society (MDS) Task Force on Technology (Espay et al., 2016), who suggested that:

Major opportunities could be realised if new technologies are developed as part of open-source and/or open-hardware platforms that enable multichannel data capture sensitive to the broad range of motor and nonmotor problems that characterise PD and are adaptable into self-adjusting, individualised treatment delivery systems

In line with this, previous research has investigated the use of environmental electronics to monitor Parkinson's symptoms. Environmental sensors track people in their homes or in laboratory conditions blending within their surroundings without interfering with people's routines. Nonetheless, they can be expensive or cumbersome to deploy in real-world settings, and they only sense participants' interactions within the instrumented space, missing mobility and physical activity events that we show in Chapter 6 are relevant to track Parkinson's symptoms (Hong et al., 2009).

Other researchers have used wearable devices like accelerometers, gyroscopes, microphones, GPS and other sensors to measure Parkinson's symptoms packed as single- or multi-purpose tools. In comparison to environmental sensors, inertial ones measure fine movements in controlled and naturalistic settings as long as participants attach them to their bodies. Hence, they have been able to provide short objective assessments of specific PD motor symptoms (Patel et al., 2009; Pérez-López et al., 2015). Nevertheless, wearables have technical limitations inherent to the type of device used: they have a limited subset of sensors on board, they can be uncomfortable to wear, can be forgotten as they are not integral to people's lives, and their battery life spans a few hours. In research settings, these restrictions often mean that participants need to carry out scripted periodic tasks that disrupt their routines and make it infeasible to monitor people longitudinally in naturalistic settings. Furthermore, most previous studies in Parkinson's have ignored non-motor symptoms which can be as disabling as the motor ones (Jankovic, 2008; Weintraub et al., 2011). Although not yet ready

for clinical use, previous work highlights the opportunity and need for an unobtrusive, longitudinal, and personalised Parkinson’s monitoring methodology that tracks both motor and non-motor symptoms (see Chapter 2).

Therefore the general goals of this work are:

- Investigate the technical capabilities of modern smartphones to collect multiple sensor data over one year while complying with the technical, ethical, UX, and privacy limitations of an in-the-wild research deployment (see Chapter 3).
- Investigate the use of clinical scales and self-reported data as ground truth data for the development of a personalised method for Parkinson’s monitoring (see Chapter 4).
- Develop a personalised and longitudinal methodology to track the fluctuations of Parkinson’s symptoms (see Chapter 5).
- Investigate the use of clinical literature, and human behaviour traces extracted from smartphone data in the development of our methodology (see Chapter 6).

More specifically, we theorise that if we collect multiple data sources from smartphones over time, we will be able to extract several behavioural traces to use them as proxy measurements to Parkinson’s symptom fluctuations. We base our theory on three facts a) smartphones are ubiquitous, and people carry their devices for prolonged periods every day, b) previous research has shown that we can infer behavioural traces from smartphone data (Barnett, Torous, Staples, Sandoval, et al., 2018; Canzian et al., 2015), and c) Parkinson’s motor and non-motor symptoms impact patients behaviour (Chapuis et al., 2005; Dowding et al., 2006; Hobson et al., 1999; Martinez-Martin et al., 2011).

1.1 Research Questions

This thesis aims to answer the following research questions:

RQ1. What smartphone data is suitable to track Parkinson’s symptoms working with technological, ethical, and UX limitations?

Smartphones are ubiquitous and contain a wide range of sensors which make them a suitable tool to collect longitudinal data. Nevertheless, the two most

popular mobile platforms (Android and iOS) have technological and privacy constraints that hinder access to raw data streams. What is more, an in-the-wild deployment is limited by ethical considerations to safeguard people’s privacy, to not overwhelm participants with taxing cognitive and physical activities, and to keep people’s data safe. Since smartphones are a tool ingrained in our daily lives, users expect a consistent battery life and graphical interface’s latency over time. Thus, a tool that collects data in the background, even if invisible for users, can hinder the device’s UX by consuming battery and processor cycles making participants drop out of research studies.

RQ2. What symptom assessment methods are appropriate to use as ground truth to validate our methods? We need a reference point to verify that the model we create is tracking real symptom fluctuations. A first option is to use validated scales employed in traditional clinical practice. Nevertheless, some are subject to the examiners’ expertise, and most of them are meant to be applied on a weekly or monthly basis. This means there is a mismatch between the time granularity with which smartphone data is generated (up to milliseconds) and the clinical information available over time. Another option is self-reporting which allows researchers to collect data on a daily or weekly basis. However, it is prone to recall bias and low answer compliance rates. In any case, we need to tackle what we call the “Ground truth paradox”, where we want to create a model to complement or even substitute clinical assessment methods, while at the same time relying on them and their drawbacks to evaluate such models.

RQ3. Can we use behavioural traces to track Parkinson’s symptoms fluctuations? After we understand what behavioural traces can be computed from the data collected from RQ1, we explore how we can combine these traces and what value they have to track Parkinson’s symptoms. We do this by conceiving new methods from a Precision Medicine perspective due to the idiosyncratic nature of the disease. We are interested in a model that adapts to people’s unique behaviour and symptoms by finding the most relevant subset of traces for each individual. Therefore, it is essential we monitor people in-the-wild, and longitudinally, so we measure their day-to-day symptom fluctuations and their impact on human behaviour, without asking participants to perform assessment tasks or interrupting their normal activities.

1.2 Contributions

The main contributions of this work are:

1. A smartphone dataset for Parkinson’s monitoring

We collected around 300,000 hours of data from up to 22 smartphone sensors from seven participants monitored between 222 and 380 days while complying with technological, UX, clinical, and ethical constraints using the Aware Framework (Ferreira et al., 2015). This dataset also includes ground truth data that came from assessments we carried out every six weeks using four clinical scales and seven cognitive tests as well as a paper diary we developed for daily self-reporting of symptom severity (in this work we refer to both clinical and self-reported scores as ground truth since we use them as reference values for comparison purposes (Cardoso et al., 2014)). This dataset holds great value for exploring Parkinson’s monitoring using smartphones in naturalistic conditions. The instrumentation phase, the deployment process, and our dataset are described in Chapter 3.

2. Knowledge that supports ground truth collection for longitudinal Parkinson’s tracking.

We used self-reported data as ground truth informed by a 49-day prototyping period. In Chapter 4, we describe the agile, iterative design process we followed to create the most appropriate tool for self-reporting in our study: a paper diary that reached 96.39% (SD=0.05) mean compliance among 7 participants monitored between 222 and 380 days. Although the diary was not validated as a clinical tool to measure Parkinson’s symptoms, it allowed us to collect the self-reported severity of our participants’ top three symptoms. As an output of this design process, we share five design implications to create artefacts for PD longitudinal self-reporting and an open-source software tool to create and encode paper diaries automatically called PaperStream.

3. An adaptative method to track Parkinson’s symptom fluctuations

We created an adaptative method to track weekly Parkinson’s symptom fluctuations (see Chapter 5). Our method is tailored to an individual’s condition (personalised) and tracks symptoms while participants carry on with the ordinary lives (naturalistic), over time (longitudinal), and without people’s input (unobtrusive).

Instead of relying on the structure of the collected smartphone data to find patterns, our method starts with a generalised set of predictions that are overfitted to each patient’s symptoms. Overfitting is desired as individuals have unique

behaviours and we aimed to identify the most relevant prediction subset to track weekly symptom fluctuations. We showed that this method tracks fluctuations better than chance (random weighted classifier) finding a different subset of predictions for each participant. Also, exploring how this method can be deployed in the real world, we show that splitting our dataset into personalisation/testing sets does not help to identify the best overall prediction subset. In Chapter 7 we discuss our method’s advantages, limitations, parameters, assumptions, and insights that inform the design of future personalised tracking approaches.

1.3 Conclusion

In this chapter, we outlined the chronic and personal nature of Parkinson’s and the problems with the current clinical assessment that motivate our work. We also highlighted how the literature has focused on monitoring motor symptoms in controlled conditions and the opportunity to explore a personalised monitoring approach. Based on the theory that we can track symptom fluctuations using smartphone data, we defined three research questions to explore smartphone data collection, ground truth collection, and their combination to track symptom fluctuations. Such questions guided our three main contributions, our one-year smartphone dataset for Parkinson’s monitoring in naturalistic conditions, knowledge that supports ground truth collection, and an adaptative method to track symptoms fluctuations.

In Chapter 2, we provide a primer of Parkinson’s Disease and discuss previous technology-based naturalistic monitoring research, we also review the literature on digital and analogue self-reporting, and we analyse the triggers and daily life impact of Fatigue, Pain, and Gait problems in people with the disease. In Chapter 3 we describe the formative information phase of this work and our main monitoring study’s design, instrumentation, and execution which includes the dataset we collected between 222 and 380 days from seven people with Parkinson’s. Chapter 4 details the design process we followed to create PaperStream, the design implications for future self-reporting artefacts and our paper diary that is used as a ground truth collection tool. In Chapter 5, we describe our adaptative method including its parameters and assumptions. In Chapter 6 we show how this method identified a subset of behavioural traces that track the self-reported fluctuations of fatigue, pain, and gait problems better than chance,

and we detail how a traditional personalisation/testing split was not able to obtain the best overall subset consistently. In Chapter 7, we discuss the strengths and limitations of our method and suggest improvements for future iterations and finally, we conclude in Chapter 8 by consolidating the knowledge that we generated during this work setting up a plan for new personalised monitoring approaches. To wrap up this chapter, we list the papers and resources we created that highlight the impact of this work.

1. **Paper.** “Back to Analogue: Self-Reporting for Parkinson’s Disease”. ACM CHI 2018 (Vega, Couth, et al., 2018).
2. **Paper.** “Monitoring Parkinson’s Disease Progression Using Behavioural Inferences, Mobile Devices and Web Technologies”. Julio Vega. ACM WWW 2016 (PhD Symposium) (Vega, 2016a).
3. **Paper.** “Using Web Interaction to Monitor Parkinson’s Disease Progression through Behavioural Inferences on the Web”. Julio Vega. Web for All Conference 2016 (PhD Symposium) (Vega, 2016b).
4. **Dataset.** 22 Android data sources, 11 iOS data sources, four clinical scales and seven cognitive tests as ground truth, and daily self-reports of the severity of participants top 3 symptoms from 7 people with Parkinson’s monitored between 222 and 380 days. Pending publication.
5. **Software tool.** PaperStream, an open source multi-platform app that allows researchers to create paper diaries or surveys that people can answer using a pen, and then, extract all the answers from the scanned pages into a CSV file. It is implemented in Python and Web technologies and uses OpenCV and Optical Marking Recognition techniques to detect the answers on paper. <https://paperstream.netlify.com/>
6. **Five design implications for Parkinson’s longitudinal self-reporting tools.** Reduce participant completion demand, design to offset the effect of tremor on input, enable implicit reminders, design for positive and negative consequences of increased awareness of symptoms, and consider the effects of handwritten notes in compliance, encoding burden, and data quality (Vega, 2016a).
7. **Three Extended Abstracts.** Presented at ACM ASSETS 2017 (Vega, Jay, et al., 2017b), Measuring Behaviour 2016 (Vega, Vigo, et al., 2016), and the Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Systems Research Symposium 2018 (Vega, Vigo, et al., 2018).

8. **Five posters.** Presented at ACM ASSETS 2017 (Vega, Jay, et al., 2017a), Measuring Behaviour Conference 2016 (Vega, Jay, et al., 2016), Parkinson's UK Research Conference 2016 and 2018 (Vega, Jay, et al., 2016), and the Microsoft PhD Summer School 2016 (Vega, Jay, et al., 2016).
9. **Three invited lectures.** Delivered at the University of Oulu, Finland, the University of Bristol, and Microsoft Research Cambridge, UK.

Chapter 2

Background

In this chapter, we provide a primer on Parkinson’s Disease symptoms and current clinical monitoring. We contrast this with technology-based monitoring that allows us to frame the scope of this work and highlight its novelty. We also review the literature on digital and analogue self-reporting that guides the development of the paper diary we use to collect symptom severity scores during our main study (see Chapter 4). Finally, we analyse the triggers and daily life impact of Fatigue, Pain, and Gait problems in people with Parkinson’s that we use in Chapter 6 to select what smartphone features will be feed to the method we present in Chapter 5.

2.1 Parkinson’s Disease

Parkinson’s is an incurable neurodegenerative disease affecting around 1% of the population worldwide and increasing as we age (Nutt et al., 2005; Tugwell, 2008). Parkinson’s idiosyncratic nature means that patients develop a subset of a wide variety of motor and non-motor symptoms.

There are four cardinal symptoms of Parkinson’s (Jankovic, 2008). 1) Bradykinesia or slowness of movement, characterised by loss of amplitude or speed during rapid alternating movements. 2) Rest tremor, a rhythmic oscillatory involuntary movement with a frequency usually between 3-6 Hz. 3) Rigidity, an increased muscle stiffness felt as a resistance when passively moving the affected limb or neck. 4) Postural instability, a loss of postural reflexes that is the primary cause of falls. Likewise, secondary motor symptoms include but are not limited to:

speech impairment, hypomimia (masked faces), dysphagia (swallowing difficulties), sialorrhoea (drooling), micrographia (abnormal small writing), and gait impairment characterised by shuffling, short or festinating steps, decreased arm swing, and slow turning around (Jankovic, 2008; Lance et al., 1963; Massano et al., 2012). Furthermore, non-motor symptoms have a significant impact on people's quality of life and can be as disabling as motor ones (Chaudhuri et al., 2006; Duncan et al., 2014; Martinez-Martin et al., 2007; Sánchez-Ferro et al., 2016). They include neuropsychiatric features like apathy, anxiety, depression or hallucinations, cognitive deterioration, constipation, urinary dysfunction, sexual dysfunction, excessive sweating, seborrhea, sleep disorders, sensory dysfunction, pain, fatigue and others (Massano et al., 2012).

Several scales exist to quantify the severity of Parkinson's symptoms and their impact on daily life (Movement Disorder Society Task Force on Rating Scales for Parkinson's Disease, 2018). For example, the Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) is the gold standard in clinical assessment and widely used in research settings to quantify motor and non-motor symptoms (Goetz et al., 2008). Similarly, the Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire (PDQ-39) is a reliable tool to assess the quality of life in Parkinson's patients (Peto et al., 1998). Yet, these instruments can be time-consuming, subjective, and rely on clinical expertise or patients' perception (Del Din et al., 2016; Dorsey et al., 2017; Maetzler et al., 2016).

In addition, traditional clinical assessment is costly (Dodel et al., 1998; Findley et al., 2003; Le Pen et al., 1999; Tugwell, 2008) and typically involves sporadic and short observations that only provide clinicians with a snapshot of patients symptoms (Dorsey et al., 2017; Moore et al., 2007). This makes it labour intensive to adjust the treatment regime of patients (Maetzler et al., 2016; Moore et al., 2007). Moreover, the response to levodopa, the most efficacious Parkinson's medication, can change even after the first two years of treatment (LeWitt, 2008) and within five years, 50% of treated patients develop motor complications (Lang et al., 1998; LeWitt, 2008; Okun, 2017). Complications include involuntary movement (dyskinesia), predictable OFF time or periods when symptoms are more severe due to the medication effect wearing off, and ON and OFF fluctuations that last from minutes to hours (Lang et al., 1998). Thus, patients and clinicians would benefit from a continuous and objective monitoring methodology (Maetzler et al., 2016).

2.2 Parkinson's Monitoring Using Technology

Espay et al. (2016) identified six Parkinson's clinical problems where technology could offer solutions: improved diagnosis, monitor response to therapy and motor symptom fluctuations, monitoring nonmotor symptoms and progression, improving medical treatment, enhance surgical treatment, and improving rehabilitation interventions. Given the aim of this work, we focus on technology-based monitoring of motor and non-motor symptoms that we divide into four categories:

- Active and Controlled. Approaches using active sensing (i.e. with people's interaction) under controlled conditions where participants must perform scripted tasks in the laboratory or home-like conditions.
- Active and In-the-wild. Approaches using active sensing in-the-wild, where participants must perform scripted tasks within their normal routines.
- Passive and Controlled. Approaches using passive sensing (i.e. without people's interaction) under controlled conditions in the laboratory or home-like scenarios.
- Passive and In-the-wild. Approaches using passive sensing while people carry on with their normal routines.

Even though controlled approaches have had positive results when assessing or monitoring symptoms in instrumented and constrained scenarios, their performance is not guaranteed and might decrease under naturalistic circumstances (Hammerla et al., 2015; Son et al., 2018; Toosizadeh et al., 2015). These testing conditions hinder the development of monitoring systems with practical applications for clinical care. Therefore, we frame our work in studies that have monitored Parkinson's symptoms in the wild. We identified 19 papers (see Table 2.1) guided by reviews done by Son et al. (2018) and Del Din et al. (2016) and through a manual search of the references and posterior citations of each reviewed work. We do not include projects that assess symptom changes pre-post interventions or those aimed to classify healthy controls and patients as they are outside of the scope of this dissertation. Nonetheless, we refer the reader to systematic and non-systematic reviews on technology-based assessment and monitoring of Parkinson's (Aghanavesi et al., 2016; Asakawa et al., 2016; Bhidayasiri et al., 2017; Hasan et al., 2017; Haubenberger et al., 2016; Hubble et al., 2015; Ossig et al., 2016; Oung et al., 2015; Ramdhani et al., 2018; Rovini et al., 2018; Sánchez-Ferro et al., 2016; Silva de Lima, Evers, et al., 2017; Thorp et al., 2018).

We discuss these papers around four attributes of the monitoring approaches they proposed: unobtrusiveness, longitudinal, personalisation, and non-motor symptom suitability. We argue that these characteristics take us closer to a monitoring approach suitable for real-world conditions and since no other work has explored a monitoring protocol incorporating all four of them, they give novelty to our work.

2.2.1 Unobtrusivness

We analyse unobtrusiveness via the burden imposed on patients by a monitoring protocol (i.e. participants' expected workload). For example, some of the reviewed studies require single (Bayes et al., 2018; Braybrook et al., 2016; Griffiths et al., 2012; Pérez-López et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Molinero et al., 2018) or multiple sensors to be attached to people's bodies (Das et al., 2012; Fisher et al., 2016; Mera et al., 2012; Patel et al., 2011). In most of these studies, inertial sensors have been used to collect continuous movement data without participants' intervention for short periods (up to two weeks). However, most of these devices are not part of people's routine (except for smartphones and perhaps smartwatches to some degree) and have shown high attrition rates after 6 (32%) and 12 (50%) months (Espay et al., 2016).

On the other hand, some projects have used smartphones to take advantage of their ubiquity and familiarity, but relying on active sensing where patients are asked to take breaks from their normal activities to complete assessment tasks. Nonetheless, smartphone app use can also decline distinctly; there is evidence that "26% of apps are used only once, and 74% of apps are not used more than 10 times" (Espay et al., 2016).

Researchers have observed this adherence levels in a micro and macro scale. In an n-of-1 study, a person with Parkinson's found a finger tapping task performed on her iPhone onerous and difficult after five days, going from 13 completed tasks per day to 0 (Riggare et al., 2018). The participant designed and self-imposed the assessment task and yet, she found out that it was time-consuming and demanding due to daily life commitments. Moreover, she rightfully points out that other patients might not have the skills, physical autonomy, knowledge, and attitude to carry out this type of active monitoring.

In a larger study, Zhan et al. (2016) recruited 121 patients and 105 controls and asked them to perform five smartphone-based tasks (presumably taking < 5

minutes) twice each day before and after medication using the HopkinsPD app. They were able to detect motor changes in response to medication with a 71% accuracy. Nonetheless, 7,563 sessions were captured over six months which equates to a mean of 33 sessions per participant (according to Figure 8 of their paper, only 41 people with Parkinson's performed more than 20 assessment sessions).

Similarly, as part of the development of the mobile Parkinson's Disease Score (mPDS) using the same app, Zhan et al. (2018) recruited two participant cohorts, one with 129 patients and another with 23 patients plus 17 healthy controls that had to execute the same five tasks twice a day (before and after medication) over six months. Likewise the previous compliance rates, the first cohort completed a mean of 48 assessments over 180 days with a wide range 2-278 (in oversimplified terms we could consider a participant performed two assessment instances every 7.5 days), while the second cohort completed a mean of 210 assessments over 180 days with a wide range 2-996 (or in other words two instances every 1.7 days). We speculate the second cohort was more compliant as they were recruited for in-person clinical assessments every three months in comparison to the first group which was recruited online and presumably was not as motivated to comply with the protocol as they did not have a close relationship with the research team. The mPDS shows promise to monitor motor symptoms backed up by significant correlations with the MDS-UPDRS, PDQ-39 and Up and Go test (even if only computed with 16 cross-sectional pairs) and a mean intraday score change of 13.9 out of 100 points (even if only extracted from 23 patients). However, the adverse effect on compliance of its obtrusive assessment tasks supports our proposal of exploring an unobtrusive approach for long-term monitoring.

Furthermore, for the development of the cloudUPDRS system, 35 patients had to perform a set of 17 smartphone-based tasks daily. However, after the first week "compliance rates dropped sharply", and only 12 patients (34%) finished the study after 12 weeks (Stamate et al., 2018). Even though the authors propose a method to reduce the number of tests that participants have to perform, a shorter assessment session does not guarantee patient engagement. For example, Arora et al. (2015) requested 20 participants to execute a 5-minute set of five tasks, four times a day, for a month, and they observed 68.9% adherence. Similarly, during the mPower project, the longitudinal study with the most participants enrolled to date, patients had to execute four smartphone-based tasks three times a day in short sessions (< 5 minutes). After the first six months,

out of the 1,087 people that joined and self-identified as Parkinson’s patients, only 150 used the app at least on five separate days over six months, and they barely went back to the app after 100 days (Bot et al., 2016). This is not to say that wearable-based/active monitoring is not useful as these approaches can still provide objective assessments in clinical practice, wearables might become part of patients’s lives if people see value in using them, or projects could focus on tracking the long-term trends of symptoms by spacing the active sessions weekly (Tsanas et al., 2010), quarterly or biannually (Memedi et al., 2015). The latter alternative could have informed the change in the second version of the mPower study protocol that requires patients to complete daily assessment tasks in 2-week bursts every three months (“mPower 2.0,” 2018). Still, all this evidence suggests that unobtrusive monitoring is preferred to track symptoms reliably and continuously over extended periods.

2.2.2 Longitudinal

Longitudinal monitoring is necessary to capture a more accurate image of the disease due to its complexity (Del Din et al., 2016). Several works have focused on monitoring motor symptoms or medication-induced motor fluctuations on an hourly basis, but we did not find experiments that replicated the high sensitivity and specificity scores obtained during short-term experiments (up to 2 weeks) over more extended periods (Bayes et al., 2018; Braybrook et al., 2016; Fisher et al., 2016; Griffiths et al., 2012; Mera et al., 2012; Rodríguez-Molinero et al., 2018).

There is a close link between unobtrusiveness and long-term tracking as hinted in the previous section and as observed in Parkinson’s self-reporting (see section 2.3). Generally speaking, the most demanding a task is, the less likely it is participants remain engaged with it over time. Thus, it is crucial to keep participants under a light workload if they are to be involved in active monitoring assessments. For example, the dataset used by Tsanas et al. (2010) was collected within an active weekly 30-min testing protocol that ran over six months (Goetz et al., 2009), where it was reported participants only missed 9.4% of the planned assessment instances (participants performed a mean of 139.9 voice recordings within these assessments out of 156 that were expected). Moreover, Memedi et al. (2015) asked participants to answer seven questions, and perform four tapping tests and one drawing test four times a day for seven-day periods every 3 or 6

months over three years. Although they observed a drop-out rate between 22% and 47%, the participants that remained in the study had a median compliance of 93%.

Out of the six studies that ran continuously on a daily or weekly basis for more than 30 days, two stand out because they rely on passive monitoring. Liddle et al. (2014) found an inverse trend between the average time spent at home and partial UPDRS scores (17 items) for nine patients through a visual comparison. Although these results come from a non-systematic analysis, they suggest a relationship between Parkinson's symptom severity and a proxy to human behaviour (time at home) inferred from passive location data, which partially informs our decision of exploring behavioural proxies in Chapter 5.

Silva de Lima et al. (2018) analysed accelerometer data in naturalistic conditions from 220 people with Parkinson's using a wrist IMU (smartwatch) paired with a smartphone, 24/7 for up to 13 weeks. They found the severity of motor fluctuations (item 4.4 of part VI of the MDS-UPDRS) was not associated with changes in walking patterns, but that age and higher severity of motor symptoms (part III of the MDS-UPDRS) was associated with less walking time. Although they analysed the relationship between UPDRS sub-scores and walking activity on a population level, it is evidence of the relationship between accelerometer-measured physical activity and motor symptoms. This study also supports the feasibility and suitability of passive sensing for long-term symptom monitoring as they got a median compliance rate of 68% (16.3 hours/participant/day) with a decline of 23% in data collected from the smartwatch after 13 weeks (Silva de Lima, Hahn, et al., 2017).

We speculate that the lack of naturalistic and longitudinal monitoring studies based on active monitoring is due to their cost and burden. It would be reasonable to expect that participants will not put up with invasive monitoring devices or intrusive assessment tasks for prolonged periods. Nonetheless, the incurable and complex clinical nature of Parkinson's plus the need to keep track of its symptoms as they evolve in the real world point to the necessity of creating longitudinal and unobtrusive approaches to track Parkinson's.

2.2.3 Personalisation

The idiosyncratic nature and fluctuations of Parkinson's call for a personalised analysis (Riggare et al., 2018) in order to tailor measurement approaches to an

individual's symptoms and provide customised, actionable feedback to patients (Espay et al., 2016). The REMPARK project (Bayes et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Molinero et al., 2018) hinted at the need for personalisation by including individual thresholds to detect gait-related bradykinesia based on inertial data, while another three studies explored an individualised approach further (Das et al., 2012; Riggare et al., 2018; Stamate et al., 2018).

Stamate et al. (2018) narrowed down 17 smartphone-based active tasks after a 1-week calibration period to a personalised subset that predicts individual UPDRS scores. Their goal was to reduce the duration of their assessment sessions to increase participants' compliance. They motivated this personalisation experiment by highlighting the idiosyncratic nature of Parkinson's since each patient would generally develop a subset of symptoms which dominate their UPDRS scores. Although their active tasks are focused on acceleration-based measurements of tremor, bradykinesia, and gait, we motivate the analysis we present in Chapter 5 in a similar manner, as we expect that only a subset of the smartphone features we collect is relevant to quantify the behavioural changes induced by the most affecting motor and non-motor symptoms of each participant.

Das et al. (2012) explored the use of Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) individual models to track the dyskinesia in the left hand of one participant and a shaky left hand with predominant left-right asymmetry on another person wearing five accelerometers for four days (wrists, ankles, and waist). Compared against a paper diary kept by both participants, their models reached an accuracy above 90% and a visual comparison of six hours of data are an indication that tracking these motor symptoms is feasible in the wild. Although it involved only two participants and two motor symptoms monitored over a few hours of data, this and other personalised approaches grant further research.

Out of all the studies we reviewed, the work by Riggare et al. (2018) was the only one that specifically addressed the potential of a personalised analysis to deliver personalised care. The first author of the paper was diagnosed with Parkinson's in 2003 and self-tracked her response to medication via a smartphone-based finger tapping task for five days (as mentioned above). She alluded a couple of benefits of personalised insights. She discovered changes in her daily motor function based on the tapping task scores which allowed her and her neurologist to discuss adjustments to her medications. Likewise, interacting with her data

during its analysis and visualisation, enabled her to put these results in context and learn about the dynamics between her medication and motor function. Although this analysis only comprised a single active assessment task over five days, these results hint at the benefits of exploring a personalised approach for clinical and self-management of Parkinson's. Indeed, we observed a similar positive self-awareness during the ground truth collection of our study using paper diaries (see section 4.3). Although it is not within the scope of this work to close the loop between our methods' output and patients daily function, the impact of personalised monitoring motivates our work and highlights its novelty as it is the first one, to our knowledge, to be designed to explore a personalised approach for tracking Parkinson's symptoms.

2.2.4 Non-motor symptom suitability

There is an "urgent need for developing unobtrusive systems to monitor non-motor endpoints in the home and community settings" (Espay et al., 2016) given the impact they have on people's quality of life (Chaudhuri et al., 2006; Duncan et al., 2014; Martinez-Martin et al., 2007; Sánchez-Ferro et al., 2016). However, almost all the papers we reviewed have focused on monitoring motor symptoms: tremor, bradykinesia, gait disturbances, motor fluctuations (ON/OFF periods, dyskinesia), voice disturbances, posture impairment, hand/finger/leg movement, or a summary of these represented by partial or total UPDRS scores. The exception was Kotschet et al. (2014) that identified immobility as a marker of daytime sleepiness using a wrist IMU and Prince et al. (2018) that analysed the short- and long-term behaviour of a smartphone-based memory test as part of the mPower project, finding non-significant impairment but "a larger degree of longitudinal performance variability" on people with Parkinson's compared to healthy controls. Thus, we explore the ability of the method we present in Chapter 5 to track changes on other Parkinson's non-motor symptoms, specifically, self-reported pain and fatigue.

Table 2.1: Research on naturalistic technology-based monitoring of PD. Column n shows people with Parkinson's/Controls

Author	Device	Duration	n	Ground Truth	Measured Task/Behaviour	Clinical Target	Monitoring	Personalised
Memedi et al. (2015)	Handheld touchscreen device	36 months (quarterly and biannually)	65/0	UPDRS and PDQ39	Self-assessments and fine motor tests	Overall severity	Active	No
Zhan et al. (2018)	Smartphone	6 months	129,23 / 0,17	UPDRS, PDQ-39, Time Up and Go test, State before and after medication	Voice, finger tapping, gait, balance and reaction time tests	Intraday symptom fluctuations, overall severity, medication response	Active	No
Zhan et al. (2016)	Smartphone	6 months	121/105	State before and after medication	Voice, balance, gait, dexterity, reaction time tests	Medication response	Active	No
Tsanas et al. (2010)	In-house device (Intel's AHTD)	6 months (weekly)	42/0	UPDRS	Vowel phonation recordings	Overall and motor severity	Active	No
Prince et al. (2018)	Smartphone	6 months	312/236	UPDRS I, II, and full scale	Memory and finger tapping tests	Short- and long-term behaviour of memory and tapping tests and their relation to disease severity	Active	No
Liddle et al. (2014)	Smartphone	8 weeks	9/7	UPDRS I, II subset (17 items)	Mobility as measured by GPS	Exploring lifespaces and its relation to Parkinson's severity	Passive	No

Table 2.1: Research on naturalistic technology-based monitoring of PD. Column n shows people with Parkinson's/Controls (*continued*)

Author	Device	Duration	n	Ground Truth	Measured Task/Behaviour	Clinical Target	Monitoring	Personalised
Silva de Lima et al. (2018)	Smartphone and Smartwatch	13 weeks	220/0	UPDRS III, and item 4.4 of part IV, medication log	Wrist acceleration	Severity of motor fluctuations and its relation with gait	Passive	No
Stamate et al. (2018)	Smartphone	3 months	35/0	UPDRS	Limb tremor, finger tapping, gait	Tremor, bradykinesia, gait	Active	Partially
Arora et al. (2015)	Smartphone	30 days	10/10	UPDRS III (modified, no rigidity or balance assessments)	Voice, posture, gait, finger tapping, and reaction time tests	Discriminate between controls and PD and predict the modified UPDRS III	Active	No
Griffiths et al. (2012)	Wrist IMU (Kineti-graph)	10 days	34/10	UPDRS III, IV, Abnormal Involuntary Movement Scale (AIMS), medication log	Wrist acceleration	Dyskinesia, Bradykinesia	Passive	No
Kotschet et al. (2014)	Wrist IMU (Kineti-graph)	10 days	68/30	Polysomnography, High Epworth Sleepiness Scores	Wrist acceleration (Immobility)	Excessive daytime sleepiness	Passive	No
Braybrook et al. (2016)	Wrist IMU (Kineti-graph)	At least 6 days	194/28	UPDRS III, laboratory experiments, clinical records	Wrist acceleration	Tremor	Passive	No
Fisher et al. (2016)	2 Wrist IMU	7 days	34/0	Diary, UPDRS III subset	Wrist acceleration	Dyskinesia, ON/OFF fluctuations	Passive	No

Table 2.1: Research on naturalistic technology-based monitoring of PD. Column n shows people with Parkinson’s/Controls
(continued)

Author	Device	Duration	n	Ground Truth	Measured Task/Behaviour	Clinical Target	Monitoring	Personalised
Mera et al. (2012)	Laptop, wrist unit, finger worn sensor	3 to 6 days	10/10	State before and after medication	Three tremor and three bradykinesia related tests	Tremor and Bradykinesia	Active	No
Riggare & Hagglund (2018)	Smartphone	5 days	1/0	-	Finger tapping test	Exploring finger tapping performance and motor function over time	Active	Yes
Das et al. (2012)	5 IMU	4 days	2/0	Diary	Wrist, Ankle, Waist acceleration	Dyskinesia, left-right asymmetry	Passive	Yes
Patel et al. (2011)	8 IMU	3 days	5/0	UPDRS	UPDRS based tasks and activities of daily living	Heel tapping and hand movement	Active	No
Bayes et al. (2018)	Waist IMU	3 days	33/0	Diary	Waist acceleration	ON/OFF fluctuations	Passive	Partially
Rodriguez-Molinero et al. (2018)	Waist IMU	1-3 days	23/0	Diary	Waist acceleration	ON/OFF fluctuations	Passive	Partially

2.3 Digital and Analogue Self-reporting

In this section we lay out the background necessary to understand and create our paper diary for self-reporting presented in Chapter 4.

Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) is a collection of methodologies to sample participants' behaviour and experiences in naturalistic settings multiple times over time (Shiffman et al., 2008). EMA is not delimited to a particular technology or methodology but includes the use of paper and electronic diaries which have been used extensively in clinical, psychological, and computer science research. Traditionally, analogue diaries use pen and paper to record answers to open- or closed-ended questions while digital diaries have been implemented in different hardware: smartphones (or their predecessors Personal Digital Assistants), desktop computers, laptops, and wearables. Although ours is not a diary study (we only use self-reporting as ground truth), we develop our self-reporting tool guided by the literature on diary design as the goal of both approaches is the same: to capture participants' feedback over time.

Both electronic and paper diaries have advantages and disadvantages. Paper diaries are cheap, portable, robust, can be pictured, memorised and scanned with ease (Luff et al., 2004), require less start-up time (Fletcher et al., 2003), and are easy for people to use (Bolger et al., 2003). On the other hand, for some diary designs it can be difficult to evaluate the validity of people's answers (e.g. retrospective completion), participants can have privacy concerns as diaries can be read by anyone, and there is a risk of errors when filling in missed entries with truthful data or fabricated answers. Moreover, these diaries can also be resource consuming and error-prone when it comes to data entry, encoding, and analysis (Bolger et al., 2003).

In contrast, electronic diaries can alleviate some of these issues and offer extra features. For example, they can have richer user interfaces with varied response formats and presentation styles (Bolger et al., 2003; Noyes et al., 2008), provide a standardised test environment, reach out to larger user populations, enable online scoring, and improve the quantity and quality of input (Noyes et al., 2008). Researchers can also evaluate the compliance of the study protocol thanks to automatic timestamps and signalling (Bolger et al., 2003; Stinson et al., 2009), prevent retrospective completion (Stinson et al., 2009), reduce data management burden (entry, encoding, transfer, storage, analysis) (Bolger et al., 2003; Lane et al., 2006; Laurenceau et al., 2005; Noyes et al., 2008), and dynamically adapt the

diaries' flow to the provided responses (Bolger et al., 2003). Nevertheless, as with any other computer-based task, their hardware or software can malfunction, and the cost of replacing or fixing it can be high, the characteristics of their screen (if any) can pose difficulties to certain populations (e.g. people with motor or visual impairments), and there is still a concern for data confidentiality especially if data is transmitted over the Internet (Noyes et al., 2008). Additionally, there is a higher financial commitment than paper diaries (although this might be offset by the cost of manual data management using paper), training might be required depending on the device and participants, there could be an overhead for researchers as setting them up may require advanced technical skills (Bolger et al., 2003; Stinson et al., 2009), and electronic diaries implemented in devices like smartphones rely on batteries that can limit certain study designs. Moreover, there is a risk of perpetuating a "digital divide", i.e., conducting research with more convenient or accessible populations where high-tech devices are easy to deploy or where computer literacy may affect participants' willingness to enrol (Bolger et al., 2003).

From the previous paragraphs, it might seem evident that electronic diaries have a distinct advantage over paper diaries. Nonetheless, Dale et al. (2007) in a systematic review of the use of Personal Digital Assistants vs paper diaries in randomised and quasi-randomised controlled trials suggested that there might be an element of publication bias, because all the reports included, and almost all those excluded, were in favour of electronic diaries. This might also be exacerbated by an unfair comparison of paper and electronic diaries (Tennen et al., 2006) and by some research misinterpreting or generalising research focused on the attributes of a diary sub-type and sampling strategy (Broderick et al., 2006), thus leading to strong recommendations like: "in our view, computerised methods are always preferable" (Christensen et al., 2003). In fact, comparisons between electronic and paper diaries have had mixed results suggesting that both types yield data of comparable quality, that there is an advantage to electronic diaries, or even that neither paper nor electronic diaries provide data of sufficient accuracy to serve as a measure of outcome in clinical trials (Tennen et al., 2006).

Unsurprisingly, evidence for participants' preference for either method is mixed too. People approved electronic diaries but did not think any was onerous (Lam et al., 2010), others found a slight majority of participants that preferred electronic devices (Fletcher et al., 2003) or a significant majority that favour digital

approaches (Heiberg et al., 2007; Kvien et al., 2005; Lane et al., 2006; Mangera et al., 2014; Velikova et al., 1999). In any case, there is a consensus that more research is needed to analyse the comparability, compliance, data quality and user acceptance of electronic and paper diaries (Bolger et al., 2006; Broderick et al., 2006; Laurenceau et al., 2005; Tennen et al., 2006).

In consequence, the rationale to favour either method is context dependent. Concerning electronic and paper-based tasks, Noyes et al. (2008) recommended that choosing one or the other should be based on their advantages and disadvantages, and their merits concerning the task demands and required performance outcomes. It is suggested that the effectiveness of a diary study depends on careful consideration of the research questions to answer (Bolger et al., 2003) and the appropriateness of either method to tackle them (Green et al., 2006). This is more evident after considering the many factors that can influence user preference and compliance: study design (i.e., having unreasonable expectations of patients (Hyland et al., 1993)), participant motivation (Green et al., 2006; Morren et al., 2009), population demographics (Morren et al., 2009), participants familiarity with technology (Laurenceau et al., 2005; Tennen et al., 2006) factors inherent to the reported phenomena (like reluctance to report relapses in discharged alcohol-dependant participants (Bolger et al., 2006)), and factors related to disease self-monitoring like the fear of damaging the relationship with health-care professionals, termination of access to medication, or discomfort monitoring indicators of pathology (Broderick et al., 2006).

In the context of Parkinson's, diaries have been used to monitor falls and motor/non-motor symptom fluctuations. Fall diaries are the accepted gold standard for fall quantification (Godfrey et al., 2016), and frequently, they require patients to record the time of a fall beside its circumstances using open-ended questions after each episode (Ashburn et al., 2008; Hunter et al., 2017; Luukinen et al., 1994). Since these diaries are event-based, they can represent a lighter burden for people with Parkinson's compared to fixed time diaries and therefore be suitable for long-term monitoring, for example, six months (Ashburn et al., 2008), one year (Luukinen et al., 1994), or even four years (Hunter et al., 2017). Nevertheless, Hunter et al. (2017) observed attrition in diary usage (51% after 48 months) mainly related to study withdrawal and non-compliance.

Motor fluctuation diaries, on the other hand, are meant to measure changes between ON and OFF time (when medication is and is not working, respectively).

Therefore, they require participants to log their motor status choosing among 3, 4, or 5 different states, every 30 minutes for 2 to 7 days (Hauser et al., 2004; Reimer et al., 2004). Although they are recommended (Antonini et al., 2011) and accepted as endpoints for measuring the efficacy of Parkinson’s medication, recall and diary fatigue can occur, and compliance can be challenging (Papapetropoulos, 2012). Indeed, Lyons et al. (2007) suggest “it does not appear to be a realistic expectation that the majority of patients will complete each entry at half-hour intervals for seven consecutive days”. Following a similar approach, the SCOPA-DC diary was created to measure Parkinson’s symptoms fluctuations seven times a day (Marinus et al., 2002). Although also demanding, this diary had good internal consistency and reproducibility in stable patients over two weeks, and there was evidence of its construct validity. Finally, Nyholm et al. (2004) compared the use of electronic (Personal Digital Assistants) and paper diaries for motor functioning asking people to complete 10-11 questions every two hours on two nonconsecutive days per week over four weeks. Although they did not expect high compliance with the paper diary, they found that 78% participants completed the diary within a 15-minute window after the scheduled time and 98% did so when no limit was considered; they attributed these numbers to user’s motivation or invalidly completed diaries (prospectively or retrospectively).

The identified Parkinson’s diaries have focused on patients with motor fluctuations and dyskinesias (involuntary movement) using event- or time-based strategies (e.g. falls and ON/OFF episodes respectively). Furthermore, for the latter “the extent to which accurate diary data can be collected beyond a time period remains unknown” (Papapetropoulos, 2012). Consequently, since the design of a diary must be tailored to the study and the use of such a method has not been reported for longitudinal, end-of-day, day-to-day assessments of Parkinson’s symptoms, the insights and design implications that we share in section 4.3 represent a valuable contribution. In Chapter 4, we detail the agile, iterative design process that led us to create a paper diary guided by our participants’ feedback, constrained by our study’s needs, and taking into account the four suggestions from Bolger et al. (2003) to implement analogue diary studies:

1. Make the diaries easily portable
2. Reduce the possibility of participant error
3. Pilot test the diaries on participants from the population to be studied
4. Maintain contact with participants, in a personal yet unobtrusive manner.

2.4 Triggers and Impact of Fatigue, Gait and Pain

Using the diary we present in Chapter 4, we collected the self-reported severity scores of the top 3 symptoms of each participant over 222 and 380 days (see section 3.2.2). The method we propose in Chapter 5 requires clinical evidence to decide what behaviour is expected from participants and their symptoms and, guided by our rationale explained in section 6.1 we chose to explore the tracking of self-reported Fatigue, Pain, and Gait fluctuations. Thus, we survey the clinical literature for the triggers and consequences of Fatigue, Pain, and Gait on people's daily life, as well as studies that have used smartphone data to monitor these symptoms in Parkinson's and other conditions (if any). We did not include our participant's feedback in this process as the method was developed post data collection, but we discuss in Chapter 7 future research opportunities in this regard.

2.4.1 Fatigue

Fatigue has a high incidence in people with Parkinson's (Herlofson et al., 2003; Rochester et al., 2006; Wen et al., 2012) and can be one of the most distressing (Rochester et al., 2006) and disabling symptoms associated with the disease, affecting people's quality of life and physical ability (Friedman et al., 2010). However, the lack of biomarkers or a gold standard measurement, a lack of a consistent definition, patients' perceptions, confounding factors (sleep problems, cognitive dysfunction, depression, anxiety), and the presence of different subtypes of fatigue hinder its assessment (Friedman et al., 2010). For example, Friedman et al. (2010) summarise the subtypes of fatigue as peripheral (muscle fatigue induced by repetitive contractions), central (an abnormal degree of persistent mental/physical tiredness), physical (sense of exhaustion to perform physical tasks) and mental (cognitive effects during and after prolonged periods of demanding cognitive activities).

Studies have shown that people with Parkinson's have lower levels of physical activity than healthy individuals (Elbers et al., 2009; Hilten et al., 1993). It has also been found that fatigue in patients with early Parkinson's (Hoehn & Yahr scale < 3) has shown a significant positive correlation to the dimensions of Activities of Daily Living, Bodily Discomfort, Emotional Well-being, Social Support and Mobility of the PDQ-39 and a significant negative correlation to

the areas of general health, role limitation (physical), social functioning, and vitality of the Short Form Survey (SF-36) (Herlofson et al., 2003; McKinlay et al., 2008; Rand Corporation et al., 2006; Ware et al., 1992). Similarly, other studies have found an association between the PDQ-39's Mobility domain, and the Physical Fatigue (Elbers et al., 2014) and Reduced Activity domains of the Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI) (Havlikova et al., 2008).

To complement this empirical evidence that links domains of the PDQ-39, SF-36 and MFI to fatigue, we took into account the dimensions assessed by the six scales that reached the status of “Recommended” or “Suggested” by the Movement Disorder Society review of fatigue rating and screening in Parkinson’s Disease (Friedman et al., 2010). These scales are the Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS) (Krupp et al., 1989), Fatigue Assessment Inventory (FAI) (Fernandez et al., 2008), Functional Assessment of Chronic Illness Therapy-Fatigue scale (FACIT-F) (Cella, 2007), Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI) (Smets et al., 1995), Parkinson Fatigue Scale (PFS) (Brown et al., 2005), and the Fatigue Impact Scale for Daily Use (D-FIS) (Fisk et al., 2002).

From these six scales, we selected the items that we considered amenable for computation using the smartphone data we collected. This means, for example, we included items like “Been confined to the house more than you would like?” from the PDQ-39 since we can measure how long a person stays at home, but we did not include items like “Had problems doing up buttons or shoelaces?” (ADL PDQ39) as we cannot know when people button up their clothes or tie their shoelaces with our dataset.

We classified these scales’ items into six categories by the domain of people’s life they assess following a similar process as that of an inductive semantic thematic analysis. **Category 1, General Physical Functioning (GPF)**, covers items that ask participants for their physical status in terms of effort, exhaustion, or energy; these items do not focus on specific daily activities, but it is expected that the more fatigued a person is, the more likely they are to feel exhausted or not be engaged in physical effort (see Table 2.2). **Category 2, ADL/Carrying out activities (ADL)**, covers items about performing routine activities or responsibilities and “getting things done”; similarly to Category 1, it is expected that higher levels of fatigue stop people from engaging on daily chores (see Table 2.3). **Category 3, Mobility**, expects people to have problems walking or getting around in public as well as spending more time at home if the patient

is fatigued (see Table 2.4). **Category 4, Social Life** covers interference and problems in the social interactions of patients with their families, friends and strangers (see Table 2.5). **Category 5, Sleep/Rest**, expects people to have problems sleeping or have the need to take breaks during the day (see Table 2.6). Moreover, **Category 6, Others** covers miscellaneous items like the effect of temperature, time of the day and inactivity periods on fatigue (see Table 2.7). Based on the categories mentioned above, we create a model (see Chapter 6) that expects that when fatigue severity is higher, patients have lower levels of physical activity, engage in less daily activities, and they have mobility, social interaction, and sleep problems.

Table 2.2: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 1 "General Physical Functioning (GPF)"

Scale	Item
FSS	Fatigue interferes with my physical functioning.
FSS	My fatigue prevents sustained physical functioning
FAI	Fatigue interferes with my physical functioning
MFI	Physically, I feel I am only able to do a little
MFI	I feel very active
MFI	Physically, I can take on a lot
MFI	I tire easily
PFS	I feel completely exhausted
D-FIS	Because of fatigue, I have trouble maintaining physical effort for long periods.
D-FIS	Because of fatigue, I am less motivated to do anything that requires physical effort.
D-FIS	Because of fatigue, I have to limit my physical activities.
FSS	Exercise brings on my fatigue
FAI	Excercise brings on my fatigue
FAI	I experience prolonged fatigue after exercise.

Table 2.3: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 2 "ADL/Carrying out activities (ADL)"

Scale	Item
FSS	Fatigue interferes with carrying out certain duties and responsibilities.
FAI	Work brings on my fatigue
FAI	Performance of routine daily activities increases my fatigue
FAI	Fatigue interferes with carrying out certain duties and responsibilities
FACIT-F	I am able to do my usual activities.
FACIT-F	I am frustrated by being too tired to do the things I want to do
MFI	I think I do a lot in a day
MFI	I get little done
MFI	I don't feel like doing anything
PFS	If I wasn't so tired I could do more things
PFS	Fatigue makes it difficult for me to cope with everyday activities
PFS	Because of fatigue I do less in my day than I would like
PDQ39 (MOB)	Had difficulty doing the leisure activities which you would like to do?
SF-36 (RL)	Cut down the amount of time you spent on work or other activities
SF-36 (RL)	Accomplished less than you would like
SF-36 (RL)	Were limited in the kind of work or other activities
SF-36 (RL)	Had difficulty performing the work or other activities (for example, it took extra effort)

Table 2.4: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 3 "Mobility"

Scale	Item
PDQ (MOB)	Had problems walking half a mile?

Table 2.4: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 3 "Mobility" (*continued*)

Scale	Item
PDQ (MOB)	Had problems walking 100 yards?
PDQ (MOB)	Had difficulty getting around in public?
PDQ (MOB)	Been confined to the house more than you would like?

Table 2.5: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 4 "Social Life"

Scale	Item
FSS	Faigue interferes with my work, family, or social life
FAI	Fatigue interferes with my work, my family, or social life.
FACIT-F	I have to limit my social activity because I am tired
PFS	My life is restricted by fatigue
PFS	Fatigue makes me reluctant to socialise
PDQ39 (SS)	Lacked support in the ways you need from your family or close friends?
SF-36 (SF)	During the past 4 weeks, to what extent has your physical health or emotional problems interfered with your normal social activities with family, friends, neighbors, or groups?
SF-36 (SF)	During the past 4 weeks, how much of the time has your physical health or emotional problems interfered with your social activities (like visiting friends, relatives, etc.)?

Table 2.6: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 5 "Sleep-Rest"

Scale	Item
FAI	Resting lessens my fatigue
FAI	Sleeping lessens my fatigue
FACIT-F	I need to sleep during the day
MFI	I am rested
PFS	I have to rest during the day

Table 2.7: Items from Fatigue scales classified under Category 6 "Others"

Scale	Item
FAI	My fatigue is worse in the afternoon
FAI	My fatigue is worse in the morning
FAI	Cool temperatures lessen my fatigue
FAI	Long periods of inactivity bring on my fatigue

2.4.2 Gait

Gait and balance problems are common symptoms of Parkinson's and are linked to increased disability, increased fall risk and decreased health-related quality of life and survival (Kelly et al., 2012; Kolk et al., 2013; Lyons et al., 1997; Muslimovic et al., 2008; Rahman et al., 2008). Busse et al. (2004) found that Parkinson's patients had a lower step count compared to healthy controls ($n = 20$) contrasting to Rochester et al. (2006) which did not find significant differences in levels of gait and gait-related activity between people with Parkinson's and controls ($n = 20$), and Chastin et al. (2010) which did not find a significant difference in the percentage of time people with Parkinson's spend laying or sitting down ($n = 17$) at late stages of the disease $H\&Y \geq 3$.

Researchers found that gait issues can promote mobility limitations (Dontje et al., 2013) and public withdrawal due to a) the feeling of shame or stigma that symptoms can trigger on patients, b) busy environments that pose unpredictable mobility challenges, and c) unpredictable symptom variations that can influence their day planning (Jones et al., 2008). Supporting these findings, it has been observed that patients would carefully organize errands to "ensure the shortest walking distance" (Lamont et al., 2012), that body function and walking capacity are correlated with the time people with Parkinson's spend walking ($n=50$) (Lamont et al., 2016), and that greater gait impairment is associated with less daily physical activity (walking outside, cycling, gardening, light and heavy household activities, and a maximum of two sport activities) as measured by the LASA Physical Activity Questionnaire (LAPAQ) (Nimwegen et al., 2011).

Based on the evidence provided above, we create a model (see Chapter 6) that expects that smartphone features quantifying mobility will reflect a trend where the more severe the gait impairment is, the more sedentary the person's lifestyle.

2.4.3 Pain

Pain prevalence has been reported between 38% and 95% in people with Parkinson's (Buhmann et al., 2017; Hess et al., 2013; Quittenbaum et al., 2004; Wen et al., 2012). However, empirical evidence that links pain and human behaviour in the context of this disease is limited (Bunting-Perry, 2010). In healthy older adults with severe pain, people have reported reduced mobility, reduced involvement in activities of daily living, psychological problems and reduced abilities to carry out social roles (Eggermont et al., 2009; Guerriero et al., 2016; Medicine, 2011, Reid et al., 2015, Reyes-Gibby et al., 2002; Tse et al., 2013; Won et al., 2004). Similarly, people with acute pain can have reduced quality of life, impaired physical function, extended recovery time and increased risk of chronic pain (Medicine, 2011).

In Parkinson's, it has been found that pain affects people's quality of life (Chaudhuri et al., 2015; Quittenbaum et al., 2004; Storch et al., 2013), their compliance with treatment (Guillemin, 2000), and frequently impairs everyday activities (Buhmann et al., 2017; Rana et al., 2018). Defazio et al. (2017) analysed the relationship between patients with different types of pain (dystonic, muscular, arthralgia, peripheral neuropathic, and central neuropathic pain) and motor and non-motor symptoms in Parkinson's. They found an association between these domains and the domains sleep/fatigue and mood/cognition of the Non-Motor Symptoms Scale (NMSS)(Chaudhuri et al., 2007). Bunting-Perry (2010) found that pain severity is strongly correlated to higher interference from pain in daily life as measured by the Brief Pain Inventory's Interference section which accounts for general activity, mood, walking ability, normal work activities, sleep, and enjoyment of life (Cleeland, 2009). Supporting these results, Rana et al. (2018) found that people with Parkinson's "scored significantly higher than controls" across the same seven domains. Finally, when it comes to peripheral neuropathic pain, Adewusi et al. (2018) showed that it is significantly negatively correlated with scores for the physical functioning and emotional role limitations domains of the RAND 36-Item Short Form Survey (SF-36). Thus, from the scales mentioned above, we selected the items we believe are amenable to computation using our dataset. Since there is no overlap among the domains they measure, instead of classifying them as we did for fatigue scales, we list them verbatim (Table 2.8).

Based on such domains, we create a model (see Chapter 6) that expects that

as participants self-report higher levels of pain they can have sleep problems, cognitive problems, sad or depressed feelings (which have been found to be related to mobility (Canzian et al., 2015)), and less engagement in physical activities and movement.

Table 2.8: Items from Pain scales related to human mobility and amenable to computation using our dataset.

Scale	Item
NMSS (Sleep/Fatigue)	Does fatigue or lack of energy limit the patient’s daytime activities?
NMSS (Sleep/Fatigue)	Does the patient have difficulties falling or staying asleep?
NMSS (Mood/Cognition)	Does the patient seem sad or depressed or has he/she reported such feelings?
RAND SF-36 (PF)	Vigorous activities, such as running, lifting heavy objects, participating in strenuous sports
RAND SF-36 (PF)	Walking more than a mile
RAND SF-36 (PF)	Walking several blocks
RAND SF-36 (PF)	Walking one block
RAND SF-36 (Role limitations)	Cut down the amount of time you spent on work or other activities

2.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, we outlined the complex nature of Parkinson’s Disease. We framed the novelty of our work as the first one to explore an unobtrusive, longitudinal, personalised, and non-motor symptom friendly method for Parkinson’s tracking, described in Chapter 5. We also highlighted the pros and cons of using paper and electronic diaries to collect self-reported data and identified design directions that we use to develop the most suitable self-reporting tool for our monitoring study in Chapter 4. Finally, we searched for clinical evidence that we use as a starting point to create an adaptative model to track fluctuations in Fatigue, Gait, and Pain in people with Parkinson’s described in Chapter 6.

Chapter 3

Methodological Approach

Our methodology has two main stages. 1) A formative instrumentation phase where we executed a three-month pilot study (Vega, 2016b, 2016a), set up our study’s protocol and data collection tools, and perform a preliminary deployment for testing purposes (see section 3.1). 2) The main monitoring study, where we collected smartphone data as well as clinical and self-reported scores from seven people between 222 and 380 days that represent the first contribution of this thesis: a dataset to explore longitudinal and unobtrusive Parkinson’s Disease monitoring (see section 3.2).

3.1 Formative Instrumentation

3.1.1 Pilot Study Insights

In this section, we overview the pilot study we conducted between July 1st and September 21st 2015. We only provide its primary insights, but a full description can be found in Appendix A. Our goals were to explore the technological and UX challenges of Parkinson’s Disease monitoring using smartphones and to leverage our gained knowledge to plan our main monitoring study.

One woman and two men with Parkinson’s carried Android phones instrumented with the Aware Framework (Ferreira et al., 2015), “Automate” and “Synchronize Ultimate” to collect data from various smartphone sensors. P01 used a Blu Studio Energy (BSE) phone as a secondary device, p02 a Sony Xperia Z3 Compact (XPE) as a primary device and p03 a BSE as a primary device. We collected 23 smartphone data sources from the BSE and 29 from the XPE (see

Table A.3).

We obtained the following insights from the instrumentation and deployment of the pilot, which informed our main monitoring study.

- Five behavioural areas possibly related to Parkinson’s symptoms that we can explore. Typing patterns, phone usage patterns, episodes of going up/down stairs, mobility patterns and social interaction patterns.
- Our data collection suite (Aware plus other Android apps) was not suitable for longitudinal data collection. p01’s phone lost $\approx 50\%$, and p02 $\approx 15\%$ of accelerometer data during the first six weeks of the study due to a read-write conflict between Aware and “Automate”’s backup routine. Accordingly, during the subsequent weeks, we stop Aware’s sensing between 1.45 a.m. and 2.45 a.m. to allow time for the backup. Also, there was a bug in “Synchronize Ultimate” that reduced the phone’s battery life by approximately 30%. As a temporary solution, we disabled this app and switched to manual sync, but we planned to find a syncing alternative as it is not feasible to manually backup data every week for one year.
- The impact of battery life on the smartphones’ UX was significant. p03 dropped out of the study after three weeks since he was getting 8 hours of battery time presumably due to his phone usage patterns, his location in a rural area, and his double SIM configuration (in our tests the phone collected data continuously for 20 hours).
- The BSE and XPE phones were suitable phones to collect data. Once the read/write and backup problems were resolved, p01 and p02 carried their phones without any other issues. BSE’s battery life spanned three days as a secondary device (p01), and XPE’s battery life lasted for ≈ 18 hours as p02’s primary device. Since the XPE has more sensors than the BSE, we chose the XPE phone as the monitoring device for our main study.

3.1.2 Software for Data Collection

Server. In our pilot, we discovered that Aware plus “Automate” and “Synchronize Ultimate” were not suitable for data synchronisation. As a solution, we deployed Aware’s web server made open source in early 2016. We installed it in a

university computer running Ubuntu 14.04 with local HDD encryption. We implemented batch and R scripts to receive a daily email digest of the data collected in the last 24 hours to monitor data collection issues. We did not have problems with the server and data storage during the study.

Aware mobile apps. Aware for Android collects up to 40 different data sources and Aware for iOS up to 25 data sources (see Table 3.2). By design, iOS has more restrictions on the raw data sources accessible by developers (no application logs, text messages data, light data, keyboard data, or cell phone tower data). Following our pilot findings, we chose Aware for Android and gave participants a choice to use our instrumented phones as primary or secondary devices. To comply with our ethics protocol, we added local encryption using SQLCipher to the most recent version of Aware for Android, and we anonymised the output of the keyboard and ambient noise sources (we substituted every alphanumeric character with a random character, and we did not store the raw audio recording used for noise measurement). Refer to subsection 3.1.3 for the testing and sensing configuration of Aware.

Plugin TinyBlackBox. In our pilot, we identified phone usage patterns based on touchscreen events as a behavioural area possibly linked to Parkinson's. To collect these touchscreen events, we developed an Aware plugin based on the TinyBlackBox (TBB) app (Montague et al., 2015) that captures four phone interaction data sources:

1. Screen IO logs. Timestamped touch events per Document Object Model (DOM) element in the interface of an Android app. Due to Android's security model, it is necessary to have admin access to the phone's operative system to collect this data.
2. Interaction logs. Tap and Focus events triggered on the active app.
3. Keystrokes log. Keyboard typing events. We do not collect this source as it is equivalent to Aware's keyboard sensor.
4. DOM Tree interfaces log. A JSON tree with all the elements of the active app. Screen IO and Interaction logs refer to this tree.

3.1.3 Hardware for Data Collection

During our pilot, we found the Sony Xperia Z3 Compact a suitable phone for data collection, but we had to search for a replacement because by November 2016 it

was not available in the market anymore. We screened the top 100 smartphones ordered by battery life¹ and considered those available in the UK ($n = 50$), those running Android < 6.0 as it was necessary to execute TinyBlackBox ($n = 35$), and those with a battery life greater than 9 hours ($n = 11$). From the phones listed in Table 3.1, we discarded the Meizu PRO 5, Sony Xperia Z3, Samsung Galaxy S6 edge+, and Sony Xperia Z5 Compact for their price ($> \pounds 350$), and the Samsung A3, Meizu m2 Note, Moto E, and Sony Xperia M2 because similar models were already in the list. We purchased the remaining three phones, Meizu M3 Note, Moto X Play, and Samsung Galaxy A5 (2016) to test Aware and TBB.

Table 3.1: Smartphones sold in the UK, running Android < 6 with at least 9 hours of battery life

Smartphone	Battery life	Price (£)
Meizu M3 Note	11h 06 min	219
Moto X Play	11h 33 min	263
Samsung Galaxy A3 (2016)	10h 08 min	229
Sony Xperia Z3 Compact	10h 02 min	191
Samsung Galaxy A5 (2016)	9h 55 min	303
Meizu PRO 5	9h 54 min	455
Meizu m2 note	9h 52 min	150
Samsung Galaxy S6 edge+	9h 29 min	455
Sony Xperia Z5 Compact	9h 27 min	424
Sony Xperia M2	9h 19 min	160
Motorola Moto E (2015)	9h 00 min	84

We discarded the Meizu M3 Note and the Samsung Galaxy A5 because TBB’s Screen IO logging did not work. Therefore, we configured Aware on the Moto X Play to collect the 22 data sources listed as used in Table 3.2 plus Plugin TBB and left the phone on a desk for 24 hours, with Bluetooth, WiFi, GPS and, a 4G data connection switched on. After repeating this test 3 times, the Moto X Play had approx. 23% of battery left which we deemed enough estimating a full usage day of around 18 hours (6 hours of sleep time). We collected data continuously for five days to test data synchronisation and storage and found no problems. In consequence, we chose to use the Moto X Play during our main monitoring study. Nonetheless, the change from an XPE to a Moto X Play meant we lost barometer data which stopped us from exploring the going up/down stairs behavioural area.

¹<http://www.phonearena.com/>

Table 3.2: Aware sensing configuration in Android and iOS for the main monitoring study. Dashes mark sensors that Aware collects but that are not present in a platform. Values in parenthesis represent the sensor pull frequency we used

Sensor	Android (freq)	iOS (freq)	Description
Accelerometer	On (5Hz)	On (5Hz)	Acceleration applied on the smartphone
Applications (foreground)	On	-	Log of apps in use
Applications (history)	-	-	It does not work on Android 5 or later
Applications (notifications)	On	-	Log of app notifications
Applications (crashes)	On	-	Log of app crashes
Barometer	Not Used	Not Used	Pressure data
Battery	On	On	Battery percentage
Bluetooth	On (1 min)	On (1 min)	Bluetooth devices visible around the smartphone (only Low Energy devices in iOS)
Calls data	On	On	Caller trace and duration of incoming, outgoing, missed calls
Messages data	On	-	Sender trace of received and sent texts
ESM	Not Used	Not Used	Experience sampling messages received
Gravity	Not Used	Not Used	Pull of Earth's gravity
Gyroscope	Not Used	Not Used	Rate of rotation data on three axes of the phone
Installations	On	-	Log of installed apps
Light	On (5Hz)	-	Ambient light

Table 3.2: Aware sensing configuration in Android and iOS for the main monitoring study. Dashes mark sensors that Aware collects but that are not present in a platform. Values in parenthesis represent the sensor pull frequency we used (*continued*)

Sensor	Android (freq)	iOS (freq)	Description
Linear accelerometer	Not Used	Not Used	Acceleration applied to phone excluding the force of gravity
GPS	Not Used	Not Used	Estimation of the user's current location. We used Plugin Fused Location instead
Magnetometer	Not Used	Not Used	Earth's geomagnetic field strength
MQTT	Not Used	-	Messages received using the MQTT protocol
Network data	-	On	Network type (wifi/mobile) and status (on/off)
Network traffic data	On	-	Bytes sent and received over mobile and wifi networks
Keyboard typing	On	-	Typing events on the smartphone's keyboard
Processor	On (10 sec)	Not Used	CPU load
Proximity	Not Used	Not Used	Distance to an object in front of the smartphone
Rotation	Not Used	Not Used	Orientation of the device as a combination of an angle and an axis
Screen	On	On	Screen events (i.e. unlock, locks)
Significant Motion	On	-	Flags motion episodes when the magnitude of the acceleration goes above/below 1
Telephony data	On	-	Network operator and SIM information
Telephony GSM data	On	-	GSM cell tower in use
Temperature	Not Used	-	Ambient temperature in celsius
Timezone	Not Used	On (1 day)	Device's current timezone
WiFi	On (1 min)	On (1 min)	WiFi networks and access points around the smartphone

Table 3.2: Aware sensing configuration in Android and iOS for the main monitoring study. Dashes mark sensors that Aware collects but that are not present in a platform. Values in parenthesis represent the sensor pull frequency we used (*continued*)

Sensor	Android (freq)	iOS (freq)	Description
Plugin Google Activity Recognition	On (1 min)	-	Google’s activity recognition
Plugin iOS Activity Recognition	-	On (3 min)	iOS’s activity recognition (Aware also collects activity data requested by other apps)
Plugin Ambient Noise	On (5 min)	Not Used	Ambient noise in decibels
Plugin Contacts	Not Used	Not Used	Daily snapshot of the contact list
Plugin Conversations	Not Used	-	Detects if the user is engaged in a conversation or not
Plugin Device Usage	Not Used	Not Used	Smartphone usage and non-usage sessions
Plugin Fitbit	Not Used	Not Used	Calories, steps, heart-rate, sleep data from Fitbit devices
Plugin Google Login	Not Used	-	Use Google login to sign up to Aware
Plugin Fused Location	On (3 min)	On (3 min)	Google’s Fused Locations API to provide the user’s location in an energy efficient way
Plugin OpenWeather	On (1 hr)	On (1 hr)	OpenWeather API to provide the weather conditions on the user’s location
Plugin TinyBlackBox	Not Used	-	In-house plugin based on TinyBlackBox to capture screen interaction data
Used sensors	22	11	Number of sensors that we collected data from during our main monitoring study
Available sensors	40	25	Number of sensors available on each platform

3.1.4 Study Protocol

We describe our main monitoring study's recruitment process, ground truth instruments, and data collection schedule. After the pilot, it took nine months from 26th January 2016 to get ethics approval from the UK's National Health Service and its Health Research Authority (see Appendix B).

Recruitment

We reached out to people aged 45-75 at the early stages of idiopathic PD (Hoehn & Yahr ≤ 3) from clinics in Greater Manchester, Parkinson's UK local groups, and the patient network of the Body Eyes And Movement (BEAM) laboratory of the School of Biological Sciences of the University of Manchester. Participants were excluded if they presented:

- Motor symptoms of sufficient severity to render them incapable of sitting still or making simple motor responses reliably.
- Auditory impairment or a level of English proficiency rendering them incapable of understanding verbal instructions.
- Visual impairment. Participants who scored worse than 6/12 (20/40) near visual acuity in either eye (with correction) on the Snellen letter chart.
- Marked cognitive impairment. Patients who score less than 88/100 on the Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination Revised (ACE-R) scale (Mioshi et al., 2006) are excluded from further testing and are referred to their GP.
- A significant level of depression. Participants who score ≥ 6 on the Geriatric Depression Scale (Yesavage et al., 1986) are excluded from further testing and are referred to their GP.
- Neurological disease (other than PD) or psychiatric illness.
- Serious head injury.

Ground Truth

We need instruments that assess participants' symptoms as ground truth to validate our tracking method. Due to the idiosyncratic nature of Parkinson's, we included scales and tests that assess motor, cognitive, and emotional domains of a participant's health. However, there was a tradeoff between the number of scales to use and their burden on our participants. We chose the following instruments supported by the Parkinson's expertise of Professor Sonja Kotz, Dr Ellen

Poliakoff, and Dr Samuel Couth:

- Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS). A valid and reliable scale to assess Parkinson’s symptoms that is widely used in clinical and research settings (Goetz et al., 2008). It has four subdomains that assess non-motor experiences of daily living, motor experiences of daily living, motor symptoms, and motor complications. Each subdomain is composed by 13, 13, 33, and 6 items respectively, and each item is ranked on a scale from 0 to 4 (Normal, Slight, Mild, Moderate, Severe).
- PDQ-39. The PDQ-39 is a reliable, valid, responsive, acceptable, and feasible tool for the assessment of the quality of life in Parkinson’s patients (Peto et al., 1998). It comprises 39 questions divided into eight subdomains: mobility, activities of daily living, emotional well-being, stigma, social support, cognition, communication, and bodily discomfort. Each question is valued on a 5-point scale: “Never”, “Occasionally”, “Sometimes”, “Often”, “Always”.
- The Addenbrooke’s Cognitive Examination Revised (ACE-R). It assesses cognitive skills within five subdomains: orientation/attention, memory, verbal fluency, language, and visuospatial (Mioshi et al., 2006). We used this scale as a screening instrument and to assess the cognitive decline in the middle and end of our study.
- Non-motor symptom questionnaire (NMSQuest). A validated scale for screening nine domains of non-motor symptoms through 30 Yes/No questions (Chaudhuri et al., 2006).
- A battery of digital cognitive tests programmed in the E-Prime 3.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, Pittsburgh, PA) and executed in a single laptop presented to participants on each visit (Couth et al., 2016):
 - Simple Reaction Time (Heilman et al., 1976; Jahanshahi et al., 1992; Kutukcu et al., 1999). Participants were shown a blue “x” in the middle of the screen and had to press the spacebar key when it turned green. The time in milliseconds was recorded between the x changing colours and the spacebar stroke.

- Choice Reaction Time (Evarts et al., 1981; Jahanshahi et al., 1992; Kutukcu et al., 1999). Participants were shown a white “x” in the middle of the screen and had to press the Z or M keys whether the “x” turned blue or green respectively. The time in milliseconds was recorded between the x changing colour and the keystroke.
 - Sustained Attention to Response Task (Robertson et al., 1997). Participants had to press the spacebar every time they saw a digit on the screen other than 3. The number of correct strokes was recorded. This task tests participants’ ability to sustain attention and inhibit responses over a prolonged period.
 - Random Number Generator (Ginsburg et al., 1994). Participants had to say out loud a random number between 1 and 10 (inclusive) on every beat of a metronome played on the laptop. Participants’ voice was recorded.
 - Digit Span (Blackburn et al., 1957). Participants had to listen to sequences of digits and then type them back from memory. This test is based on the classic paradigm (Wechsler, 2009). The E-Prime script allows determination of an individual’s auditory digit span. It is tunable as far as the number of blocks and the duration of stimuli are concerned. It gives sets of 5 trials on a set of digits that starts with a length of 3 and goes up or down depending on performance (3+ correct makes the number of digits increase, 2- makes it decrease). The number of correct and incorrect recalls was recorded.
- A battery of analogue cognitive tests:
 - Stroop Colour-Word (Stroop, 1935). It is a sensitive and highly reliable test to measure inhibition (Asakawa et al., 2016). We used a paper-based version of this test as described by Fine et al. (2008). Participants were presented with four tasks. In the first one, we showed them a matrix of 5x10 squares coloured red, green or blue and participants had to name the colour of each square. In the second one, participants had to read a matrix of 5x10 words formed by “red”, “green”, and “blue”. In the third one, we showed participants a similar matrix of 5x10 words but printed on a dissonant ink colour, and participants had to name the ink colour rather than reading the word (e.g. “red” was

printed in blue ink and participants had to say blue instead of red). The fourth test was similar to the third one, except that some words appeared inside a box. The examinee had to name the ink colour of words inside a box, or read the printed word otherwise. This last test is a task-switching paradigm; The Colour-Word Interference Task (CWIT) (Delis et al., 2001), a recently developed modification of the Stroop Test to predict cognitive decline on the Dementia Rating Scale (DRS).

- Phonemic fluency and Semantic fluency (Shao et al., 2014). Participants were presented with two tests. One where they had to generate as many words as possible starting with a letter of the alphabet, and another one to generate as many words as possible within a single category (fruits, sports, etc.) under 60 seconds.
- Daily symptom self-reporting. Participants choose their top 3 symptoms and self-report their severity daily on a scale from 0 (No severity) to 3 (High Severity). After we prototyped different self-reporting instruments we favoured a paper diary (see Chapter 4). We clarify that although we refer to the diary data as ground truth throughout this thesis, it is not clinically validated and thus it does not fall under the traditional “ground truth” definition like the aforementioned clinical scales.

Assessment Visits

The study’s protocol included a screening visit and after that, 6-weekly assessment visits during 48 weeks. During the screening session, participants gave their written consent, and we assessed cognitive impairment and depression with the ACE-R and GDS. Weeks 1, 12, 24, 36, and 48 were long visits that lasted up to 2.5 hours where we applied the full MDS-UPDRS, PDQ-39, NMSQ, laptop tests, and analogue cognitive tests. In turn, Weeks 6, 18, 30, and 42 were shorter visits where we applied the same scales except for the full MDS-UPDRS. The ACE-R was applied again during weeks 24 and 48 to measure cognitive change (Table 3.3).

Table 3.3: Ground truth collection visits. One screening session followed by four short and five long alternating assessment sessions

Visit	ACE	GDS	MDS-UPDRS	PDQ-39	NMS	Laptop tests	Analogue tests
Screening	Y	Y	-	-	-	-	-
Week 1	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 6	-	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 12	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 18	-	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 24	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 30	-	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 36	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 42	-	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y
Week 48	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

3.1.5 Preliminary Deployment

We followed a snowball recruitment process to test our instruments in-the-wild. P01 joined on 7th December 2016 and collected data until 20th January 2017. After the first three weeks, we discovered a set of software bugs that made Aware crash and stop data collection. We were collecting large amounts of data from a wide variety of sensors for a sustained period. Thus, most bugs were storage, memory, and data synchronisation related as well as time-consuming to debug because smartphones had to be used for a few days at the time to simulate real usage. To fix them, we submitted 24 commits² to Aware’s code repository from January 26th 2017 to 07th March 2017. We attach a letter from Aware’s creator and project leader Adj. Prof. Denzil Ferreira from the University of Oulu, Finland highlighting our contributions (see Appendix C).

In parallel, we recruited participants, p02, p03, p04, p05 during February 2017 (p02 was excluded due to his ACE-R and GDS scores) with p03 being the only person to adopt our smartphone as a primary device. After upgrading our phones to Android 6.0 to fix a bug that stopped Bluetooth sensing, we dropped support for Plugin TBB and therefore the phone usage behavioural area we identified in

²<https://github.com/denzilferreira/aware-client/commits?author=JulioV>

the pilot. We prioritised Bluetooth over touchscreen data given that only p03 actively used the phone. We deployed our phones to p01-05 in March 2017, but after six weeks we discovered we sensed only 40% of the theoretical monitored hours from secondary smartphones compared to 80% from p03's device due to three reasons:

1. Participants forgetting their secondary smartphone at home.
2. Participants generating data only on their primary smartphone (screen events, typing events, calls & texts).
3. Android 6's battery saving policies that stopped apps running in the background when the phone is not in use.

To tackle this issue, we deployed Aware for iOS in people's personal phones. We mirrored the sensing rates of Aware for Android and tested it in the wild for four weeks. We collected only 11 features using Aware for iOS (see Table 3.2) meaning that:

1. Keyboard access was not allowed stopping us from exploring the keyboard typing behavioural area identified in the pilot.
2. Only Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) sensing was available which detects fewer devices than traditional Bluetooth.
3. Activity Recognition (AR) data was pulled every 3 minutes instead of 1. It was not available for p06 as her iPhone was running iOS 9.3.5.

3.2 Main Monitoring Study

After we finished the preliminary deployment phase and the parallel design process for self-reporting tools (see Chapter 4), we started the main data collection stage of our one-year monitoring study. In this section, we describe our dataset which represents the first contribution of this work. We summarise our participants' demographics, clinical and self-reported ground truth data, as well as the smartphone data we collected.

3.2.1 Participants

Our main monitoring study spanned from July 2017 to August 2018. We recruited participants p06-p08 in July 2017. Exact monitored dates per participant are in

Table 3.4, sensed days vary between 222 and 380 due to our snowball recruitment process and the ground truth co-design process (see Chapter 4). Five participants were monitored using their personal iPhones (p01, p04, p05, p06, p08) and two adopted a Moto X Play as their primary device (p03, p07). Participants' demographics at recruitment time are in Table 3.5.

We recruited four more male participants in December 2017, but we do not use their data in this thesis as we were still collecting it at the time of analysis. P09, p10 and p11 used their iPhones and p12 one of our Moto X Play devices. Due to time constraints, we only monitored them for nine months (until September 2018) and emailed them the PDQ-39 and the NMSQuest every month instead of our 6-week visits. P12 dropped out of the study in June 2018 for personal reasons.

Table 3.4: Monitored period for p01-p08

Participant	Sensed days	Phone	Start	End
p01	222	iOS	2017-07-27	2018-03-05
p03	223	Android	2017-07-26	2018-03-05
p04	264	iOS	2017-07-24	2018-04-13
p05	268	iOS	2017-07-25	2018-04-18
p06	380	iOS	2017-07-25	2018-08-08
p07	366	Android	2017-08-03	2018-08-02
p08	368	iOS	2017-08-04	2018-08-07

Table 3.5: Demographic data of p01-p08

Participant	Gender	Age	Years since diagnosis	Daily dose levodopa	H&Y in ON
p01	M	53	7	375	2
p03	F	72	12	300	2
p04	F	65	5	200	2
p05	M	65	3	150	1
p06	F	64	2	150	1
p07	M	70	3	400	2
p08	M	71	9	600	2

3.2.2 Ground Truth Data

During our 6-week assessment visits, we applied three clinical scales: the MDS-UPDRS every other visit (Table 3.6), the PDQ-39 (Table 3.7), and the NM-SQuest. The latter scale was designed for non-motor symptoms screening, and although its results are not meant to be summed up as numeric scores we do it for informational purposes in Table 3.8). Our participant’s symptoms as measured by the UPDRS did not change considerably. We attribute the improvement of p03 in week 24 (-14) and p08 in week 12 (-19) to medication changes, and the fluctuations in the rest of the visits to the natural progression of Parkinson’s symptoms, medication state during the assessments (medication wearing off or kicking in), or measurement error. For the PDQ-39, it has been suggested that a change of 5 points represents a minimal meaningful change (Fitzpatrick et al., 2004) which we saw over different periods for all participants (e.g. weeks 18 to 36 and 36 to 48 for p01).

We conducted five laptop-based cognitive tests: Single Reaction Time (Table 3.9), Choice Reaction Time (Table 3.10), Sustained Attention to Response (Table 3.11), Digit Span (Table 3.12), and a Random Number Generator. As well as three analogue ones: the Stroop test (Table 3.13) and two Verbal fluency tests. For the first four laptop-based tests we provide accuracy scores in their respective tables, for the Stroop test we provide completion time. We do not share metrics for Random Number Generator and Verbal Fluency tests because the recordings have not been encoded. Extra metrics like response times segregated by correct and incorrect answers can be computed but are not within the scope of this thesis.

We only report ground truth data from assessment visits done after 24th July 2017 when our paper diary and Aware for iOS were deployed. P03 was out of town during week 30 and did not complete the cognitive tests of that session.

Table 3.6: MDS-UPDRS total scores for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-260)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	35	59	77
w12	NA	NA	NA	NA	43	62	58
w24	86	73	40	32	42	54	69
w36	84	59	31	30	49	59	63
w48	76	55	32	33	40	50	57

Table 3.7: PDQ-39 total scores for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-100)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	9.5	10.1	25.2
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	7.6	10.4	20.6
w12	NA	NA	5	14.4	8.3	6.4	23.3
w18	16.3	23.2	4.7	22.2	5.7	7.6	22.4
w24	18	24.5	12.1	15.2	4.2	7.2	26.3
w30	14.6	15	2.9	18.1	2.6	5.4	26.7
w36	21.9	24.5	6.4	12.4	5.5	6.2	24.2
w42	18.1	18.9	8.2	15.5	6.2	10.0	17.6
w48	14.6	15.1	4.4	14.2	5.5	5.8	25.8

Table 3.8: NMS total scores for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-30)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	7	10	11
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	6	10	9
w12	NA	NA	4	10	9	9	13
w18	6	16	6	11	6	9	16
w24	4	15	7	12	7	7	14
w30	6	13	4	8	6	8	13
w36	8	21	6	9	6	8	15
w42	5	10	5	9	6	8	13
w48	6	14	5	9	6	7	15

Table 3.9: Simple Reaction Time accuracy for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-100)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	90	100
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	90	90
w12	NA	NA	100	100	90	100	100
w18	100	90	100	90	100	90	90
w24	100	90	100	90	100	100	100
w30	90	NA	100	100	100	90	90
w36	90	90	100	90	100	100	100
w42	90	90	90	100	100	100	100
w48	100	90	100	100	100	100	100

Table 3.10: Choice Reaction Time accuracy for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-100)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	95	75	85
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	90	95	75
w12	NA	NA	90	95	90	85	95
w18	95	90	100	100	90	85	95
w24	95	100	100	95	95	80	80
w30	85	NA	95	100	100	90	90
w36	90	75	100	100	95	90	90
w42	80	25	100	90	100	85	95
w48	75	95	100	95	95	95	95

Table 3.11: Sustained Attention to Response accuracy for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-100)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	100.0	94.8	96.3
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	99.3	97.8	97.8
w12	NA	NA	100	98.5	100.0	98.5	96.3
w18	96.3	97	99.3	99.3	99.3	99.3	97.0
w24	97.8	96.3	99.3	98.5	100.0	99.3	94.8
w30	97.8	NA	100	99.3	0.7	99.3	95.6
w36	100	99.3	100	100	100.0	100.0	97.0
w42	97	97.8	100	99.3	99.3	99.3	97.8
w48	98.5	96.3	99.3	100	99.3	98.5	97.8

Table 3.12: Digit Span accuracy for p01 to p08 collected over one year (range 0-100)

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	92	68	76
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	88	80	72
w12	NA	NA	92	96	88	84	80
w18	76	80	100	100	84	80	72
w24	80	76	100	100	68	80	80
w30	76	NA	96	96	84	92	68
w36	88	88	100	96	84	88	76
w42	88	80	100	96	84	88	68
w48	88	92	84	88	84	100	84

Table 3.13: Stroop completion time for p01 to p08 collected over one year

visit	p01	p03	p04	p05	p06	p07	p08
w01	NA	NA	NA	NA	54	84	60
w06	NA	NA	NA	NA	57	86	59
w12	NA	NA	47	49	48	58	54
w18	46	70	43	48	43	70	53
w24	50	59	38	43	46	76	49
w30	43	NA	37	37	48	84	51
w36	44	72	36	47	49	66	46
w42	44	97	34	39	43	65	48
w48	40	69	35	39	46	64	49

Paper Diary

We detail the motivations, design process, and the 49-day prototyping period that lead us to create a personalised paper diary for symptom self-reporting in Chapter 4. For consistency, we present in this section the diary’s compliance at the end of the main study (min. 222 days, max. 380 days) and in comparison to the results of those 49 days (see Table 3.14). The diary’s mean answer compliance only declined by 2.15% over an average of 299 days. P01’s compliance improved (4.58%), and p06 was the only participant with a sharp decline from 100% compliance after 49 days to 86.84% after 380 days. p03 and p04 got a smaller reduction (1.78% and 0.77%) while p08 receded by 3.93%. P05 and p07 had perfect compliance in contrasting circumstances, while p05 was tracking only two symptoms once a day which did not vary considerably (see Figure 3.4), p07 was tracking three symptoms, three times a day, in addition to the handwritten notes mentioned in subsection 4.2.6 (see Figure 3.6). P07 might be considered a super user, but the compliance levels we obtained confirm the simplicity, reduced workload and user acceptance of our diary. In Figure 3.1 to Figure 3.7 we illustrate participants severity scores where it is possible to visualise the idiosyncrasy of Parkinson’s symptoms. Each square represents a day, and scores 0-3 represent *No severity*, *Low severity*, *Moderate severity*, and *High severity* of symptoms. Participants chose their three main symptoms and self-reported them 1, 2, or 3 times a day over the monitoring period (participants were required to report them at least once a day at the end of the day). There are those symptoms like p04’s B or p05’s B that are reported as *No severity* most of the time, others like

p03’s A,B, and C which fluctuate between *No severity* and *High severity*, and those like p01’s B and C which fluctuate mostly between *No severity* and *Low severity*. These are the fluctuations we track with our method in Chapter 5. The original symptoms for each participant’s A, B, and C labels are in Table 6.1.

Table 3.14: Diary compliance at the end of the 49-day prototyping period and the main monitoring study

Participant	Compliance (49 days)	Compliance (study end)	Diff	Total monitored days
p01	91.84%	96.42%	+4.58%	222
p03	100%	98.22%	-1.78%	223
p04	100%	99.23%	-0.77%	264
p05	100%	100%	0.00%	268
p06	100%	86.84%	-13.16%	380
p07	100%	100%	0.00%	366
p08	97.95%	94.02%	-3.93%	368
Overall	98.54%	96.39%	-2.15%	299

Figure 3.1: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p01

Figure 3.2: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p03

Figure 3.3: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p04

Figure 3.4: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p05

Figure 3.5: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p06

Figure 3.6: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p07

Figure 3.7: Daily self-reported severity of the top 3 symptoms of p08

3.2.3 Smartphone Data

We collected 22 different data sources from Android and 11 from iOS (see Table 3.16). Both platforms sense common data sources, but some are not equal. Accelerometer data in iOS was collected continuously while in Android only when the acceleration magnitude was over 1 using an open source significant motion detection algorithm³. Bluetooth data in iOS was limited to Low Energy devices while Android was not, thus iOS detected between 96% and 99.8% fewer Bluetooth devices. Network traffic data was only available for Android, and Network type only for iOS (phone connected to WiFi or Mobile networks). Screen events were fewer for iOS (locked, unlocked) than Android (off, on, locked, unlocked) which means that in Android it is possible to infer lock screen interactions. Timezone was supported in both platforms, but we did not activate this source in Android by mistake, although if needed, timezone can be inferred from location data.

³<https://github.com/sensorplatforms/open-sensor-platform/blob/master/embedded/common/alg/significantmotiondetector.c>

Activity Recognition (AR) data was collected from the phones’ native APIs. In Android, we fixed a compatibility bug in January 2018 thus missing data before this date, and in iOS, AR data was collected without setbacks excluding p06 as her iPhone did not support this feature. Plugin Fused Location was collected at the same rate in both platforms, but we collected additional location coordinates in Android generated by third-party apps like Google Maps. Finally, WiFi networks in iOS can only be sensed while the phone is connected to a network, thus gathering between 92% and 97% fewer access points records than Android.

In Table 3.15, we report the monitoring coverage of each participant measured by the number of hours with at least 18 location coordinates logged (20 coordinate pairs are expected - 1 every 3 minutes; 18 is used to take into account two records likely not done on the hour). Coverage ranges from 71.8% to 98.0% with a mean of 86.78%. The distribution of such hours over the monitored period can be seen in Figure 3.8 to Figure 3.14. Missing data can be attributed to the phone being powered off, GPS satellites out of reach (terrain geography or being inside a building), the OS killing Aware to manage memory or battery, the user disabling location services, or synchronisation problems. It is unknown what exactly contributed to p01’s lower coverage.

Table 3.15: Sensing coverage measured by hours with at least 18 location coordinates recorded

Participant	Device	OS	Sensed days	Sensed hours
p01	iPhone SE	10.3.2	222	71.8%
p03	Moto X Play	6.1	223	84.0%
p04	iPhone 6	10.3.2	264	88.3%
p05	iPhone 7	10.3.2	268	89.8%
p06	iPhone 4s	9.3.5	380	98.0%
p07	Moto X Play	6.1	366	90.3%
p08	iPhone 7	10.3.3	368	85.3%

Table 3.16: Records collected for each smartphone sensor for p01-p08

Sensor	iOS phones (11 sensors)					Android phones (22 sensors)	
	p01	p04	p05	p06	p08	p03	p07
Accelerometer	136,980,993	193,795,012	194,753,567	257,864,201	218,442,799	17,983,642	27,218,713
Applications (foreground)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	15,562	7,261
Applications (notifications)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	35,095	30,231
Applications (crashes)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	75	83
Battery	236,207	323,271	341,999	625,219	457,444	402,544	732,559
Bluetooth	2,138	4,605	20,583	1,883	1,225	371,271	503,635
Calls data	382	2,381	4,131	4,948	3,429	681	112
Messages data	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	699	681
Installations	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	295	850
Light	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1,750,443	4,242,509
Network data	129	299	360	413	554	NA	NA
Network traffic data	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	553,646	1,291,747
Keyboard typing	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	38,565	17,443
Processor	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1,628,014	1,817,493
Screen	1,964	11,498	12,076	12,611	8,554	21,052	20,764
Significant Motion	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	381,593	1,136,874
Telephony data	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	144,463	341,154
Telephony GSM data	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	162,252	343,299
Timezone	3,883	5,675	5,827	9,077	7,781	NA	NA
WiFi	227,618	332,161	339,798	533,043	447,628	6,596,966	3,847,420
Plugin Google Activity Recognition	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3,510	862,972
Plugin iOS Activity Recognition	189,387	326,515	321,099	0	612,118	NA	NA
Plugin Ambient Noise	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	19,539	243,456
Plugin Fused Location	140,898	296,763	318,279	630,971	454,215	469,619	508,543
Plugin Open Weather	5,171	7,900	10,682	7,820	8,971	5,177	9,381

Figure 3.8: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p01

Figure 3.9: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p03

Figure 3.10: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p04

Figure 3.11: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p05

Figure 3.12: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p06

Figure 3.13: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p07

Figure 3.14: Sensing coverage measured by at least 18 location records per hour for p08

3.3 Conclusion

In this chapter, we overviewed our 3-month pilot study describing the behavioural areas amenable to computation and the technical decisions it informed on our main study. We detailed the protocol, ground truth instruments, and software and hardware we used during our main study. In addition, we highlighted the technical and data quality problems we faced and their solutions during a preliminary deployment stage. Finally, we described the dataset we collected after 380 days, which represents the first contribution of this work. In Chapter 4, we report our second contribution: knowledge that supports ground truth collection for longitudinal Parkinson's tracking.

Chapter 4

Self-reporting as Ground Truth

In this chapter, we illustrate the agile, iterative design process that led us to our second contribution: knowledge that supports ground truth collection for longitudinal Parkinson’s tracking, including five design implications for future self-reporting tools. Supported by the diary design literature reviewed in section 2.3, we created a paper diary that blends digital and analogue data collection which we used to gather self-reported symptom severity scores to evaluate our third contribution, an adaptative symptom tracking method that we detail in Chapter 5. We have published this design process and implications in the ACM CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems 2018 (Vega, Couth, et al., 2018).

Since we can compute behavioural features from smartphone data on an hourly or daily basis, we need ground truth that matches that time granularity to validate our method. Traditional Parkinson’s clinical scales like the MDS-UPDRS (Goetz et al., 2008) or the Parkinson’s Disease Questionnaire (PDQ-39) (Peto et al., 1998) can measure the long-term progression of Parkinson’s, but they were not designed, nor it is feasible to apply them every day as they can be time-consuming or depend on the examiner’s expertise. An alternative is to interpolate the clinical scores which might be suitable under certain conditions (e.g. monitoring early non-medicated patients (Tsanas et al., 2012)). However, we believe it is not realistic to assume hourly or daily smartphone-inferred behaviour has a monotonic linear change over months. We could have carried out interviews or electronic/analogue assessments like spiral drawing (Pullman, 1998), but they are time-consuming and disruptive if we consider the required recording frequency and the duration of our study. In contrast, self-reporting is a suitable option as evidenced by

previous works on mental health monitoring (Barnett, Torous, Staples, Sandoval, et al., 2018; Canzian et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2016). Moreover, we can rely on people’s ability to report the severity and impact of their symptoms as they do when completing part II of the MDS-UPDRS or the PDQ-39.

Nonetheless, self-reporting using an electronic or a paper instrument presents its own set of challenges that affect user compliance, acceptance, and data quality. Indeed, a digital approach can be more suitable for precise timing and within-day assessments (Green et al., 2006; Laurenceau et al., 2005; Tennen et al., 2006), whereas an analogue approach is convenient for once-a-day assessments (Laurenceau et al., 2005; Tennen et al., 2006). Considering we can monitor our participants at both time scales, our goal was not to compare a digital and an analogue method but instead design and test different prototypes.

Our premise was that a technology-based approach would provide participants with an effective, flexible, and resilient technique for symptom self-reporting. Unexpectedly, after testing four prototypes using Bluetooth, NFC, and a micro-controller, we accomplished 98.64% answer compliance and high user acceptance using a paper diary to track day-to-day fluctuations over a 49-day testing period and 96.39% at the end of our study. The diary is tailored to each patient’s condition, does not require any handwriting, allows for implicit reminders, provides recording flexibility, and its answers can be encoded automatically. We also share five design implications for future Parkinson’s self-reporting artefacts as part of this thesis’ second contribution: 1) reduce participant completion demand, 2) design to offset the effect of tremor on input, 3) enable implicit reminders, 4) design for positive and negative consequences of increased awareness of symptoms, and 5) consider the effects of handwritten notes in compliance, encoding burden, and data quality.

4.1 From a Digital to an Analogue Symptom Diary

Throughout seven months, a group of people with Parkinson’s and the research team co-designed six different prototypes to self-report Parkinson’s symptoms (see Figure 4.1). We started the design process along p01 (Point A in Figure 4.1) focusing on a digital device because they are suitable for precise timing and within-day assessments (Broderick et al., 2006; Green et al., 2006; Laurenceau et

al., 2005) and our smartphone data would allow us to track participant’s activities at an hourly rate. We decided to collect the overall daily impact of Parkinson’s symptoms rather than their severity because impact is already employed as an end-point in research (e.g. PDQ-39) and because we are using people’s behaviour as a proxy to their condition. Thus, we asked participants to answer “*Overall, how have your symptoms impacted your day so far?*” on a 4-point scale: “*No impact*”, “*Low impact*”, “*Moderate impact*”, and “*High impact*”. We chose an even number of steps because people tend to select the middle point if there is an odd number of answers (Tsang, 2012) and because p01 considered it difficult for patients to discern 6 or 8 levels of impact. Although this question has not been clinically validated, it is suitable for our study as it provides a longitudinal individual overview that we use to perform a personalised analysis instead of a cross-sectional one. Above all, any designed device had to comply with our study’s requirements:

- Independent. It must be separate from our monitoring tool (smartphone); using a mobile app could remind people they are being monitored and make them change their behaviour (Brage et al., 2005; McCarney et al., 2007; Wickström et al., 2000).
- Accessible. It must be usable by people with dexterity problems caused by Parkinson’s motor symptoms.
- Frictionless. Due to our study length, participants did not have to wait, configure, or perform actions that could make self-reporting feel like a chore.

Figure 4.1: Design process timeline from December 2016 to August 2017 including participants recruitment, prototype development and deployment, and interviews.

4.1.1 First button-based prototype

The first prototype was formed by 4 Flic¹ Bluetooth buttons (Point B in Figure 4.1) that log clicks, double clicks, and holding presses on the Flic mobile app using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) triggering a catalogue of predefined actions. A beep notifies users of a click and a red glow signals no connection between a button and the phone. These buttons complied with our three requirements: they were a self-contained device, p01 considered them accessible to people with moderate motor symptoms (Hoehn and Yahr scale ≤ 2), and the buttons could be pressed at any time effortlessly. Each button represented one step in our severity scale and was glued to an A4 piece of paper with the surveying question printed. We added a sticker to each button imitating a visual analogue pain scale and developed a plugin for Aware to store each click (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2: First prototype using Flic buttons on an A4 piece of paper

P01 used the buttons daily to self-report their symptoms over six weeks and suggested three changes:

- *Portability.* p01 emphasised he wanted a portable device. He reported the buttons were “easy to use” which made him keen to press them multiple times a day. In turn, he wished to bring the board outside his house, but he could not do it because the rig was too big and the buttons were pressed

¹<https://flic.io/>

accidentally in his bag. As a result, he trimmed down the A4 sheet around the buttons (Figure 4.3):

“It’s half my day [being at work], I thought it was important to record data during the day as well.” (p01)

- *Personalised Monitoring.* p01 suggested using four buttons to track four specific symptoms using 1 to 4 clicks to report their severity instead of an overall impact. He reasoned that in practice he only had a small set of symptoms that impacted his daily routine with different severity and at various times.

“When you are feeling bad you want to say what symptom is particularity affecting you now.” (p01)

- *Focus on daily experience.* p01’s suggested rephrasing the surveying question because it could be leading participants to report their symptoms had no impact as some people would have already adapted to their condition and what is affected now is not their daily routine per se but how they experience it.

“What’s happened is you’ve already allowed your symptoms to impact your day just by having a different lifestyle, so your symptoms used to impact your day [...] maybe experience is a better word.” (p01)

Figure 4.3: P01 trimmed down the A4 sheet of paper into a 20 x 7 cm piece to make it portable

4.1.2 Second button-based prototype

For our next prototype, we made three changes to the button set following p01's feedback (Point C in Figure 4.1). First, we placed the buttons inside a spectacles case to make them portable and avoid accidental presses. Second, we asked participants for their top 4 symptoms and assigned each to a single button to personalise the monitoring. Third, we rephrased the surveying question to: "How are your symptoms impacting your daily experience so far?" to focus on daily experience (see Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4: Second prototype using Flic buttons and one button per symptom. Spectacles case is 155 x 60 x 27 mm

After we recruited p03, p04, and p05 (Point D in Figure 4.1) we interviewed them to validate these changes (Point E in Figure 4.1). We showed them one button without modifications, explained its functionality, and asked: "if you had one or more of these buttons, how would you use them to report the severity of your symptoms?". The three participants backed up p01's idea of individualised monitoring and praised its portability and simplicity.

“If those were the designated buttons, I would have one for each of my different symptoms. That would be much more sophisticated than just having a single button because it would differentiate what I’m communicating. In terms of severity, you want to keep things simple so you know one press for a bit, two presses for moderate and three presses for this is really awful. [...] I’m completely interested in how you formulated this study I think it is very splendid. I mean, the golden bullet is simplicity, isn’t? The simpler you keep things the more effective. That’s thinking. This is a glasses case, isn’t it? Perfect! That’s really good, I love it.” (p04)

We deployed the second prototype to p01-5 for six weeks. However, upgrading our phones to Android 6.0 (see subsection 3.1.5, Point F in Figure 4.1) made the buttons connection unstable due to a bug² in Android 6.0 affecting multiple equal BLE devices paired up to certain Bluetooth chips. A patch for it was available but not yet merged into Android’s source code.³ This prompted us to design a substitute self-reporting tool, but even if this bug were fixed, we discovered that our paper diary perfectly meets the needs and constraints of our monitoring study.

4.1.3 NFC cube

Our third prototype was a cube with 6 NFC tags attached to each side (Figure 4.5) developed at Point G of Figure 4.1. We tested two alternatives: a) each tag represents a symptom and participants need to scan a tag multiple times to report its severity, and b) three tags describe different symptoms, and the other three represent three levels of severity. p01-5 agreed the first option would be more intuitive and they would not need to fiddle with the cube (more accessible). Although the cube was portable (6 cm on each side), we discarded it because it was not independent or frictionless as, by Android’s security model, participants would need to unlock their phone to scan the tags and thus be reminded of the monitoring tool.

²<https://issuetracker.google.com/issues/37115854>

³<https://android-review.googlesource.com/#/c/315988/>

Figure 4.5: Alternative prototype using a wooden cube with a NFC tag on each face. The cube measures 6 cm on each side

4.1.4 Micro:bit

We built our fourth prototype (Figure 4.6) using a Micro:bit at Point G of Figure 4.1. We programmed the device so participants would press Button A located at the left-hand side to report four symptoms labelled A, B, C or D, and button B located at the right-hand side to select the intensity of that symptom on a scale from 1 to 4.

The device would be independent despite transmitting the selection to an Android application. However, we discarded it because we would have needed to 3D print a case to make it portable, we did not consider it frictionless as batteries would have to be swapped every four weeks, and the device had reconnection problems with the Moto X Play using BLE. Time was a limiting factor for us (see Appendix D), but it might be worth exploring this option further under different circumstances.

Figure 4.6: Alternative prototype using a Micro:bit. The black box on the right is a battery case that powers the device. Measurements: 5.5 x 7 x 1.5 cm.

4.1.5 Paper Diary

Finally, we went back to analogue and used pen and paper for three reasons: 1) paper diaries are suitable for once-a-day assessments (Laurenceau et al., 2005; Tennen et al., 2006), and our smartphone data would still yield metrics relevant for this time scale, 2) our participants were familiar using diaries and notebooks which could ease adoption and 3) it would be a stand-alone, cheap, reliable and fast artefact to develop and deploy. Consequently, we created the layout showed in Figure 4.7 informed by our three design constraints for a self-reporting tool and the feedback from the first two button prototypes: independent, accessible frictionless, personalised and portable (Point H in Figure 4.1). We anticipated manual entry would be a burden for us and knew that, although for some types of paper diaries user compliance decreases over time (Carter et al., 2013), reducing participant demand might increase it (Broderick et al., 2006; Green et al., 2006). Our rationale to comply with these requirements and overcome possible drawbacks of analogue approaches was:

1. *Independent.* A paper diary is entirely autonomous from our users' smartphones.
2. *Accessible.* Participants do not have to write anything down. All input fields can be completed by marking the corresponding section.
3. *Frictionless.* Having a page per day and a bookmark (ribbon attached to the back cover) helped participants to find the section they needed to report on. We also assumed this would decrease the chance for input errors as suggested in (Bolger et al., 2003). On the recommendation of an external person with Parkinson's with hand tremor, we included a gel ink pen which could be clipped to the booklet's spine, was retractable so that participants with dexterity issues did not have to deal with pen caps, and was anecdotally easier to write with.
4. *Personalised.* Participants choose their top 3 symptoms to be tracked. We reduced the number of symptoms from 4 to 3 and put them into four entries per page due to space constraints and p01's opinion that it was not feasible to answer the diary more times than this.
5. *Portable.* We printed 60 pages on double-sided A5 booklets. We chose this size because participants already had similar diaries and 60 pages to swap diaries on each assessment visit of the study.
6. *Reduced demand.* To reduce the burden of completing the diary, we request participants to self-report their symptoms only once a day, but we gave them three more optional entries. This way we can collect day-to-day changes and possibly the most relevant within-day fluctuations.
7. *Blending analogue and digital.* We augmented our diary so it can be encoded automatically instead of manually, thus, tackling one of the main drawbacks of analogue approaches. For this, we implemented an open source desktop app with Python and Web technologies called PaperStream. Using Optical Mark Recognition techniques, PaperStream detects pen marks from scanned pages of diaries and surveys and extract their answers into CSV files (Vega, 2017).

P01

Tuesday, 30 May 2017

How are your symptoms impacting your daily experience so far?

HH		MM	
11	12	00	Dyskinesia None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
10	am	15	Slow Walk None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
9	pm	30	Fatigue None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
8	6	45	
7	5		

HH		MM	
11	12	00	Dyskinesia None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
10	am	15	Slow Walk None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
9	pm	30	Fatigue None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
8	6	45	
7	5		

HH		MM	
11	12	00	Dyskinesia None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
10	am	15	Slow Walk None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
9	pm	30	Fatigue None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
8	6	45	
7	5		

HH		MM	
11	12	00	Dyskinesia None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
10	am	15	Slow Walk None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
9	pm	30	Fatigue None <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> High
8	6	45	
7	5		

1 Please, fill out at least one row per day SKIP

Figure 4.7: Diary’s first layout. Each page has four entries, and each entry has the participant’s top 3 symptoms that can be scored on a scale from 1 to 4 (None to High) depending on the impact of that symptom in people’s daily experience.

Figure 4.8: Top: diary’s second layout printed as a double-sided A5 booklet with three sections to log time and the severity of 3 symptoms on a 4 point scale. Bottom: note scheme used by p07 with daily handwritten notes and extra notes for exceptional circumstances during his day; there is also an example of error handling by the participant, crossing out an undesired rating

We recruited p06 and deployed the diary to p01-6 (Point I in Figure 4.1). After two weeks we asked their opinion on the diary’s design, surveying question, usage patterns, and what they liked and disliked (Point J in Figure 4.1). During the interviews two aspects came to our attention: p03-5 reported that although they could perceive the severity of their symptoms changing during the day, its impact was harder to quantify, and either was something that they have adjusted in the past or something that they would only notice on the rare occasion when their symptoms were at their worst. To cope with it, they started to log the severity instead of the impact of their symptoms, so we adopted this format for the rest of the study. Secondly, p06 withdrew from the study because the diary felt like a chore and it was overwhelming for her to try to remember what she did during her day.

“It ends up being filled in retrospectively because I don’t take it everywhere with me so then I have to remember where I was and what was happening earlier today. For instance, if I was walking somewhere, then I need to be specific about the time because you will need to match it with what your computer says was happening at that moment and quite often I don’t remember in that kind of detail so I’m kind of guessing.” (p06)

However, during our interview it was clear she assumed we were matching the diary with her daily life and therefore, she had to record the time, symptom severity and even notes on the margin about her activities as precisely as possible. After clarification, she re-join the study. The workload that she put up with might be comparable to medication intake diaries where participants log their medication every 30 minutes-1 hour but for no more than 2-7 days within a week.

“I’m assuming that you’re trying to match what I say with what is on the tracking thing. So that I need to be as specific as I can about the time [...], I just assumed that you would be trying to put the two things together.” (p06)

After p01-6’s feedback, we made three minor changes (Figure 4.8). First, we included three entries per page since no participant filled in more than that on any day. Second, we marked the last two entries of each page as “Optional”. Third, we simplified the surveying question to make it clear we want an average symptom severity rather than the impact: *“So far, what is the severity of your*

symptoms?”. P01-5 used the first version of the diary for the last four weeks of these 6-week monitoring cycle since the changes were not significant. On the following 6-week cycle, we deployed the revised version of the paper diary (Point L in Figure 4.1), we reintroduced p06 and recruited p07, p08 (Point K in Figure 4.1) and interviewed them after 15 days as we did with p01-5 (Point M in Figure 4.1).

4.2 Diary Compliance and Insights

We report compliance based on Liao et al. (2016) guidelines since the diary implements an EMA-like strategy (Table 4.1). The prototyping period was 49 days long, and the diary followed a time variable, self-initiated, once-a-day prompting schedule. Compliance is defined as the number of days with at least one answered entry divided by 49 days. Back-filling possibly influenced compliance, but it was allowed and desired in our study as it is common practice in traditional Parkinson’s clinical assessment. Although p01-4 used the diary for 12 weeks, we report the first 49 days for consistency as this is the period over which p01-8 participated. For a comparison between the answer compliance between the prototyping period and the main monitoring study, see section 3.2.2.

Table 4.1: Diary compliance over the 49-day prototyping period

Participant	Compliance
p01	91.84%
p03-7	100%
p08	97.95%
Overall	98.54%

We emphasise the symptom survey used in the diary has high face validity, but its clinical validity has not been tested. Therefore, although the survey might be suitable for our project’s longitudinal and personalised analysis, its outcome values are self-reported and subject to bias. It should not be considered an instrument ready to deploy in clinical settings, but an opportunity to explore a new reporting artefact.

To better understand our participants’ experience with the diary and shed light on what led to this level of compliance, we transcribed the 15-day interviews verbatim using a paid service and performed a thematic analysis following an inductive semantic approach (Braun et al., 2006). For consistency, we only

included the second interview of p06. Two researchers independently coded the interviews with a moderate agreement (unweighted kappa=0.77) and discussed any discrepancies to reach a consensus. We identified seven topics: four related to positive attributes of the diary, one identifying an issue with this approach and two miscellaneous features.

4.2.1 Simplicity

Five participants thought the diary was simple and easy to use. The other two had a neutral opinion on it.

“It’s just so easy to complete [...] I think the diary is neat, concise, well put together, well made, it’s sturdy, not going to fall apart easily, it’s well marked out.” (p05)

“It’s very simple, very easy to complete. I don’t think I’ve had much difficulty, deciding what ranking to give each measure.” (p08)

4.2.2 Considerations for writing

Five participants highlighted at least one of the two considerations we had in mind to support and offset the effect of hand tremor when using the diary: a) they did not have to hand-write anything down in the diary, and b) the retractable ink gel pen we provided allowed them to mark the paper using less pressure compared to a ballpoint pen.

“A good feature is that I don’t have to write, I can just circle the time and fill in a circle for the symptoms.” (p01)

“Oh I like the pen, I like the pen very much. It’s just very smooth sort of writing, easy writing, I don’t need to press too hard. I think it’s better than a ballpen, you don’t need as much pressure to write with it which helps with my writing. One of my problems is trouble writing because it’s the right hand I’ve got my tremor in.” (p05)

4.2.3 Flexibility

Five participants considered the diary flexible and benefited from it. They talked about flexibility regarding completion time and error detection and correction.

Since there was not a fixed time window to answer the diary, they could do it whenever it was more convenient, including times when they would answer it retrospectively the day after they forgot the night before. Although this might be an issue for other studies and diaries like those tracking medication's ON and OFF cycles, for us, it was acceptable and indeed a desired feature. Also, participants appreciated the fact that each page was marked with the date and therefore allowed them to have a clear view of the day to be reported and at the same time identify or even correct erroneous entries.

“I don't need to worry if I miss it, I can always go back to it, I can just sort of think back if I missed a day thinking, oh what did I do yesterday? [...] Sometimes I've missed a day and come back to that the day after.” (p05)

“It's easy, one or two days, or one day last week, I was feeling absolutely tired out, and I'd put a three mark in, and I crossed it off and put a four in, because I was really low on energy.” (p07)

4.2.4 Implicit reminders

All participants used the physical presence of the diary at home as an implicit reminder for its completion. Since we only required them to answer the diary once a day, some people kept their diaries near their bed or where they charge their smartphones. Besides, those participants that wanted to fill in the diary more often kept it in the kitchen where meal or medication time would prompt them to complete it. Reminding through physical presence was described before by Sellen and Harper as an affordance of paper where, for example, employees would be reminded of actions that needed to be taken through the physical presence of documents on their desk or drawers working as a “continuous yet relatively unobtrusive” hint (Sellen et al., 2002).

“I keep it [the diary] on the chest of drawers in the hall, because that's where I plug in and recharge my phone every evening. I don't put it in the drawer, I actually have it on the surface and that way I can give myself maximum opportunity to make sure I put something in the diary before I go upstairs to bed.” (p04)

“I normally have it with me at my work desk. I think the visual appearance of the diary as I go to bed, where I have it on my desk, is a prompt to me to do something with it when I need to. There’s something about having a visual prompt to do it. I’m afraid I’ve got to that age, where I do that with all sorts of things.” (p08)

4.2.5 Interpretation problems

There were two interpretation issues. There was some confusion regarding the scale for the “Low energy” symptom. Participants were asked to rate each symptom from “None” to “High” severity. It was unclear to p03 and p07 whether “High” on the scale for this symptom indicated high energy levels or high severity of low energy. Both concluded it was the latter. On the other hand, p01, p04, p05 and p06 were not sure if they should record the time when they were filling the diary in or the time at which the reported severity level was present. We emphasised we were looking for an average severity level of each symptom up to the point of logging and therefore instructed them to record the time of reflection.

“It creates a bit of a confusion potentially between whether I’m reporting the section on the day or whether I’m reporting what’s happening at the time of recording. So, what I’ve recorded, I’ve done it as a reflection of the day, rather than a reflection of that moment.” (p04)

The second problem might build a case for the acceptance of in-situ self-reporting of symptoms severity. However, paper diaries for intensive time-based sampling in Parkinson’s are not meant to be used for more than a few days. Technology-based EMA could be an alternative, but since interruption burden is also a limitation, it is necessary to overcome two issues: the amount and length of interruption and the friction of accessing the reporting artefact (Intille et al., 2016). For example, the use of micro-interactions in smartwatches showed higher compliance compared to a smartphone-based EMA intervention over four weeks (Intille et al., 2016). What is more, a custom-made wrist Bluetooth button provided a convenient method for a person with post-traumatic stress disorder to report one symptom leading to hyper-arousal for four months (Larsen et al., 2017). Likewise, a custom-made Bluetooth artefact allowed participants to report physical activity or sleep/stress using a touch-sensitive surface for one week (Paruthi et al., 2017).

In the context of Parkinson's, these ideas could be adapted for longitudinal self-reporting in the wild. Nevertheless, researchers should explore the role of motor and non-motor symptoms on the acceptability and efficacy of such hardware in addition to its clinical validity. Whether digital or analogue artefacts are used, the design insights we provide in section 4.3 represent actionable items for designers and scientists that can foster creativity and innovation.

4.2.6 Suggesting additional notes

Three participants suggested space for notes describing current or previous activities to the self-reporting. We thought asking something like this would be too demanding for all of our participants, but those who suggested it were keen to do it out of motivation to enrich our analysis and also as a guide to discover patterns in their daily life. These notes are not relevant for our main study, but researchers interested in collecting them might find it useful to know that some participants considered writing a one word/sentence note doable. It is also worth highlighting the case of p07, who developed a note-taking system within our diary, marking in blue everyday activity labels and in red severe circumstances that affected his day (Figure 4.8).

“I wonder whether there should be a little spot for an explanation of what the problem is, rather than just filling in the blanks [...] just put on like a one-liner about what the problem was.” (p05)

4.2.7 Self-awareness of symptoms

Finally, we noticed that four participants started being more aware of their symptoms. P01 felt compelled to fill in extra entries in the diary when his symptoms were severe, while p04 confirmed her notion that her symptoms do not fluctuate strongly within days. P07 tried to identify what activities had the worst effect on his symptoms using his daily note system and hinted at using this information to manage his daily routine. P06 in contrast to p01 was motivated to report her gait when it was better than usual. She mentioned this practice is a coping strategy to try to improve her gait and at the same time show others that she is doing well. What is more, since she considers this idea inherent to her, she believes it has been, and will be, consistent.

“It shows some days are better than others. It can pinpoint, associated with the notes that I’m writing, of what is causing me a bad day, and avoid it if possible, or acknowledge that doing this or that, is going to bring a high score on the symptoms.” (p07)

“Yesterday I went for a walk and I was quite proud of my walking, I’ve scored myself because I was thinking, this is good. It is like I’m trying to show how good I can be, to compete with myself.” (p06)

4.3 Design Implications

Our paper diary reached 98.54% compliance over a 49-day prototyping period among seven participants. We provide design implications that support the creation of future artefacts to collect self-reported data in Parkinson’s Disease whether researchers decide to go back to analogue or use a digital medium. We reflect on the seven constraints and attributes that guided the diary design and on the seven themes we identified from our participant’s experience. However, the following implications should not be considered canon for this particular type of diary and must be scrutinised under our study’s limitations (see Appendix D). The iterative design process, our patient’s insights, PaperStream, the paper diary, and these implications, form the second contribution of this thesis: knowledge that supports ground truth collection for longitudinal Parkinson’s tracking.

Reduce participant completion demand. We confirmed that by using a less demanding end-of-day diary, we accomplished higher compliance than reported before as suggested by (Broderick et al., 2006; Green et al., 2006). In our diary, three factors lessened patients’ load: having an artefact with a physical footprint that enabled implicit reminders, a flexible completion strategy that adapted to people’s routines and allowed them to correct errors, and the “Immediacy of capture” affordance that comes with the use of a pen and allows people to capture their symptoms quickly (Riche et al., 2017).

Design to offset the effect of tremor on input. Our participants appreciated that the diary could be completed without writing and with as little movement of the hand as possible. We enable this by using questions with ordinal answers, without open-ended inquiries and by pre-printing as much information as possible (e.g. the date). Furthermore, the strokes that were necessary were

made with an ink gel pen which our participants perceive as better than a ball-point pen confirming the anecdotal evidence we had at the start of the design process. Interestingly those were also the only people that chose tremor as one of their primary symptoms. However, people with Parkinson's with advanced dyskinesias, moderate kinetic tremor (between 3 and 10 cm) or rigidity might have problems handling a pen, and in this case, increasing the size of the answer areas or using a marker might allow participants to answer the diary using bolder strokes. Even favouring technology might be a good alternative, as it can correct for involuntary movements (Levine et al., 2005). For reference, our sample of participants had mild motor symptoms as measured by Part III of the MDS-UPDRS ($mean = 36$ points out of 132, $sd = 3.53$), and none to slight dyskinesias and ON/OFF fluctuations as measured by Part IV of the same scale ($mean = 3.7$ out of 36, $sd = 5.6$). Moreover, based on the conversations we had with our participants every six weeks, we know that when their symptoms were particularly severe, they would try to defer some of their daily activities which could include the diary's completion, as they can predict the wearing-off of their medication. Yet, as Parkinson's progresses the percentage of predictable drug cycles decreases and thus researchers might want to test the use of the diary during the worst periods to adapt its design and improve compliance.

Enable implicit reminders. All participants used the diary's presence as a trigger to log their symptoms' severity, something we did not expect. Of course, this is not as relevant for diary designs that require a fixed logging time or those that are event-based where the monitored phenomenon is the reminder. Although paper enables this behaviour, researchers can design other noticeable analogue artefacts that integrate into people's pre-existing habits by being in frequented places. Such devices do not ask people to change their routines but function as an aide-memoire. Furthermore, this attribute could be emulated in electronic approaches running on smartphones or computers without recurring to intrusive reminders like alarms, but instead using direct access icons placed on the device's home screen, an ongoing notification on their lock screen, or even with physical objects that participants can place in their environment as with the paper diary.

Design for positive and negative consequences of increased awareness. To the best of our knowledge, no research has explored the effect of symptoms awareness on the health of individuals with mild Parkinson's Disease. In the context of self-monitoring, we observed what Wilde et al. (2007) stated:

“awareness grows over time if people think what they experience, [and] see its relationship to their disease or condition”. The authors established awareness of symptoms as one of two core components of self-monitoring that can lead to improved disease self-management by recognising symptoms, common triggers, and setting and refining goals related to preventing acute illnesses. In fact, p07 identified daily triggers to plan his routine. This is in line with what Ayobi et al. (2017) observed when self-reporting artefacts helped people with Multiple Sclerosis to understand their bodily reactions in everyday life.

Nevertheless, as seen in other conditions, there could also be unexpected negative consequences such as participants becoming worried, obsessed or anxious over their symptoms (Ayobi et al., 2017; Nunes et al., 2015) or symptoms (coughing) getting worst after thinking about them (Nunes et al., 2015). Following this evidence, we also contemplate the possibility where participants might adhere to their medication intake schedule more faithfully to boost their efficacy but, more worryingly and on an extreme case, this same behaviour could prompt patients to modify it without consulting their doctor. Based on a systematic review of self-care technologies on chronic conditions where the authors recommend fostering reflection by making health and contextual information available (Nunes et al., 2015), we speculate that giving participants access to their diary completion history and having contextual notes about everyday activities increased their awareness and therefore the likelihood of any of the consequences listed above (although we do not know to what degree). Thus, researchers who want to limit this effect could prevent participants from annotating their diaries, use short diaries that are swapped more often, or use electronic approaches where the control of both circumstances is more granular (e.g., not allowing any retrospective inspection of answers). Besides, other authors should also consider possible bias with reporting strategies like those from p04 and p06, where the severity of symptoms can skew the frequency of diary completion.

Consider the effects of handwritten notes in compliance, encoding burden and data quality. Handwritten notes might provide rich insights from participants self-reporting experience. Likewise, people might find it easier to add notes using pen and paper thanks to the pen affordance of “Integrating information in context” (Riche et al., 2017). However, it could also represent an unbearable task for other people; for example, adding such notes contributed to p06’s temporary withdrawal from our study. Furthermore, the availability of

contextual notes can be linked to an increase of symptom awareness as explained above. In any case, researchers should have in mind that transcribing these notes requires either time to do it manually or expertise to develop a piece of software that does it automatically. Additionally, prompting handwritten notes using open questions brings the need for extensive coding and larger item non-response (Reja et al., 2003).

4.4 Conclusion

During the agile prototyping of the different self-reporting tools described above, we found out that pen and paper are a suitable method to collect longitudinal day-to-day fluctuations. P01-8's feedback provided us with a detailed view of the problems and virtues of our prototypes that were the base to conduct each redesign.

Although our decision process was tied to a set of constraints, a button-based or app-based tool might be the right choice under different circumstances (Carter et al., 2013), for example, when the chosen device does not interfere with other aspects of the monitoring study. Therefore, in line with other authors, we do not advocate the use of either analogue or electronic approaches as a silver bullet, but instead, recommend tailoring either option to the study's goals.

We highlight the attributes that favour our paper diary compared to some technologies: it is cheap, accessible, frictionless, personalised, portable, low-demand, automatically encoded, straightforward and flexible. These are all characteristics that make it a suitable tool for ground truth data collection in our main study.

Chapter 5

Personal Predictions

In this chapter, we present an adaptative, clinical knowledge-based method we created called Personal Predictions. It is a method that starts with a set of smartphone features and can identify a personalised subset suitable for Parkinson’s symptom tracking (see Chapter 6).

We aimed to quantify an individual’s behaviour using data collected from their smartphones over time. In the literature, this also referred to as Digital Phenotyping (Jain et al., 2015). Although previous research has modelled the relationship between longitudinal variables using analytical methods like Generalized Estimating Equations (Liang et al., 1986) and Generalized Linear Mixed Models (Breslow et al., 1993), both approaches aim to create a population-based model instead of a personalised one.

Personalised care is one of the four pillars of Precision Medicine with the potential to transform our traditional reactive disease healthcare system into a more cost-effective and action-prompting alternative (Flores et al., 2013). However, the lack of sufficient statistical methodology is the main bottleneck in much of the digital phenotyping work, rather than the technical challenges (Marsch, 2018).

Machine and Deep Learning algorithms are a prevailing method to analyse sensor data in digital health research. We argue that they are not the right tool to use at this time for several reasons. First, we aim to explore whether relying on clinical knowledge instead of the structure of the data enables us to track Parkinson’s fluctuations. Second, we prioritised clinical interpretability and thus discarded deep learning models that act like a black box limiting understanding and explainability (Kubota et al., 2016). Third, most machine learning algorithms assume the distribution of the training set is static, but human behaviour is not.

Thus, once a new model is tested on data with a different distribution to that used in training its predictions might be invalid (Kubota et al., 2016). Fourth, the parameters of machine learning algorithms need to be tuned, and this requires expertise (Q. Yang, Suh, et al., 2018) which in practice would not be available for each patient. Although we could ignore these limitations and benchmark vanilla ML algorithms to explore their usefulness as these issues can potentially be overcome in the future (for example by Automatic Machine Learning (Feurer et al., 2015; Thornton et al., 2013)), we consider these experiments outside of the scope of this work.

To our knowledge, the work published by Barnett, Torous, Staples, Sandoval, et al. (2018) is the only analytical method specifically created to analyse multiple longitudinal variables on an individual basis. It labels days as normal or statistically anomalous and explores their incidence around schizophrenia relapses (rare events). Although it would be possible to apply this method to our dataset to explore if there are anomalies before a positive or negative PDQ-39 for example, their method cannot be applied to track symptom fluctuations. Thus, we consider this exploratory exercise outside of the scope of this thesis and future work.

Accordingly, we investigate the creation of a clinical-knowledge based method to track individual symptom fluctuations.

5.1 Creating a Personal Prediction

We select a set of smartphone features that we theorise fluctuate along a clinical or self-reported ground truth score (GTS). This manual selection process is based on 1) clinical knowledge about the impact of Parkinson’s symptoms on daily human behaviour, 2) previous tech-based monitoring studies, and 3) patients’ experience.

Each selected feature has an associated binary value describing the way it should behave in relation to the GTS. For example, if Feature 1 is time at home and the GTS is fatigue, we theorise Feature 1 increases when the magnitude of the score increases (more fatigue equals more time spent indoors). Feature 2, distance travelled, should have a negative change when the magnitude of the score decreases and so on (Figure 5.1). The triplet formed by the GTS, the smartphone features, and their predicted behaviour is what we call a Personal Prediction. We define a Positive Personal Prediction PP_p which corresponds to a positive change of the clinical score (participant’s health is getting worse), and

its opposite, a Negative Personal Prediction PP_n when the clinical score is going down (participant’s health is improving).

Figure 5.1: A Personal Prediction has a ground truth score (GTS), a set of smartphone features, and their hypothesised relationship. For example, Feature 1 should change positively if the score does so, while Feature 2 changes negatively. The hypothesised relationships are based on the literature.

Figure 5.2 is an example of a PP_p with Fatigue as the GTS plus 8 location and 2 activity recognition features. When a person is getting more fatigued, we theorise they spend more time at home, travel less distance, cover less geographical space, their maximum displacement is shorter, their location entropy is lower, the probability that they have pauses during travel is higher, their circadian routine is less consistent, the distance they travel from home is lower, they spend less time walking, running, or cycling, and they spend more time sitting or standing.

Figure 5.2: Personal Prediction example for fatigue and location(GPS) and activity recognition (AR) features. When a person is getting more fatigued we theorise they spend more time at home (arrow pointing up), travel less distance, etc.

5.2 Elements of a Personal Prediction

The GTS and smartphone features are time series data. We chose the diary as GTS over the clinical scales due to their time resolution (daily vs 6-weekly for the clinical and cognitive tests). We summarise the smartphone features to match the granularity of the GTS (the diary can be answered up to three times a day, but in practice, it was done mostly once, see section 3.2.2). We split the GTS and smartphone features into seven days periods starting on Mondays to match our participants' routines. We used the slope of a linear regression model to represent change over every seven-day period taking into consideration all points in each segment (even when participants self-reported their symptoms more than once a day). We discuss alternatives to the linear regression model in Chapter 7.

Let symptom \mathbf{s} be the GTS we track using \mathbf{F} smartphone features both collected over \mathbf{w} weeks; the output of the first stage is a Positive and Negative Personal Prediction formed by three elements (see Figure 5.3):

1. A list, *Predictions*, of \mathbf{F} binary values $[-1, 1]$ representing the theorised behaviour of \mathbf{F} features with respect to a positive and a negative change of symptom \mathbf{s} .
2. A list, *SymptomFluctuations*, of \mathbf{w} binary values $\Delta\mathbf{Score}_w \in [-1, 1]$ representing the *observed* negative or positive trend of the self-reported severity of symptom \mathbf{s} over \mathbf{w} weeks.
3. A set of \mathbf{F} lists, *SmartphoneFluctuations*, of w binary values $\Delta\mathbf{Feature}_{wx} \in [-1, 1]$ representing the *observed* negative or positive trend of smartphone feature \mathbf{F} over \mathbf{w} weeks.

5.3 Personalising a Personal Prediction

We split *SymptomFluctuations* and the \mathbf{F} lists of *SmartphoneFluctuations* into two sets, one for personalisation (*SymptomFluctuations_{per}*, *SmartphoneFluctuations_{per}*) and the other for testing (*SymptomFluctuations_{test}*, *SmartphoneFluctuations_{test}*). There is a tradeoff in this split; we search for a personalisation period long enough to capture different behaviour fluctuations but short enough so that participants report their symptom severity for as briefly as possible.

The personalisation stage is formed by six substages (A-F) (Figure 5.4). Its input is the triplet coming from the previous step: a *Prediction* (positive and negative), *SmartphoneFluctuations_{per}*, and *SymptomFluctuations_{per}*. Its output is the list of all possible smartphone features combinations ranked according to their capacity for tracking symptom \mathbf{s} .

- A) Compute all combinations $\sum_{1 \leq n \leq F} \binom{F}{n} = 2^F - 1$ of F smartphone features.
- B) Subset the features from *SmartphoneFluctuations* present in combination \mathbf{c} for each week \mathbf{w} .
- C) Compare the Positive and Negative *Prediction* and count how many features behave as expected ($\mathbf{n1}$ and $\mathbf{n2}$ respectively).
- D) Label the Positive and Negative *Prediction* for each week \mathbf{w} as “Rejected” or “Holds” if $\mathbf{n1}$ and $\mathbf{n2}$ are bigger or equal than \mathbf{ct} (a fixed compliance threshold). We test all thresholds from $F/2$ to F .
- E) Label each week \mathbf{w} as “Better” if the negative prediction holds, “Worse” if the positive prediction holds, and “No change” if both or neither prediction hold.
- F) Compute Cohen’s kappa coefficient to measure the agreement between the output of our method and the ground truth for all weeks of the personalisation period. Rank each combination \mathbf{c} by its \mathbf{kappa}_c .

5.4 Testing a Personal Prediction

We evaluate the performance of the personalised features over the testing weeks. We select the features from the combinations with the highest \mathbf{kappa}_c (the most agreement during the personalisation stage, the better), the highest \mathbf{ct} (the more features behaving according to the literature, the better) and the lowest number of features (the simpler the model, the better). We then follow the same process as in the personalisation phase but using the *SymptomFluctuations_{test}* with the testing weeks as ground truth. The top combination of features is chosen as the most relevant to track a participant’s self-reported symptom severity.

We compare our method against a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC) to explore if the testing results are relevant. An RWC is a naive model that labels each week at random based on a multinomial distribution with three classes (“Better”, “Worse”, “No Change”). For example, if 80% of the periods for testing are labelled as “Better”, the RWC will pick the label “Better” at random 80%

of the time. We compute the mean precision (Figure 5.5) and recall (Figure 5.6) of each class over 1000 iterations of a RWC as the mean values remain within a margin of ± 0.1 in 16 different scenarios with 300 to 1×10^6 iterations.

Figure 5.3: Output of the first stage of the Personal Predictions method. A) A list of binary values representing the theorised behaviour of the smartphone features with respect to the tracked symptom s . B) The observed trend of symptom s over w weeks. C) The observed trend of F smartphone features over w weeks

Figure 5.4: Six stages of personalisation: A) Compute all combinations of 1 to F smartphone features. B) Subset week w of each smartphone feature. C) Compare the positive and negative predictions and count how many features behave as expected. D) Label the positive and negative predictions as 'Rejected' or 'Holds' depending on the number of features being higher than threshold ct . E) Label each week as 'Better', 'Worse', or 'No Change' depending on whether the positive and negative predictions were rejected or held. F) Compute the Cohen's kappa coefficient between the output and ground truth labels for all weeks

Figure 5.5: Precision of a Random Weighted Classifier with p01's slow walk scores for 16 iterations from 300 to 1,000,000. Precision of class 'Better' (squares), 'Worse' (circles), and 'No Change' (triangles) remain within a margin of 0.01

Figure 5.6: Recall of a Random Weighted Classifier with p01's slow walk scores for 16 iterations from 300 to 1,000,000. Recall of class 'Better' (squares), 'Worse' (circles), and 'No Change' (triangles) remain within a margin of 0.01

5.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented our Personal Predictions method. It takes as an input a list of weekly symptom fluctuations, lists of smartphone features fluctuations, and a list representing their expected relationship based on the literature. Each feature is expected to go up, down or remain the same with respect to changes in the symptom severity that is being monitored. The method adapts the smartphone features to find a subset that is relevant to track symptom fluctuations according to a personalisation subset of the ground truth data. We then test the best combination(s) of features and use a Random Weighted Classifier as a baseline.

Chapter 6

Results

In this chapter, we create a Personal Prediction to track participants' self-reported severity of pain, gait, and fatigue based on clinical literature (see section 6.1). We implement and preprocess 14 location, and 2 activity recognition smartphone features which we theorise are relevant to track such symptoms (see section 6.2). We show that our method tracks weekly fluctuations better than chance (third contribution of this thesis) but also how a personalisation/testing splitting is not suitable for a real-world deployment (section 6.3).

6.1 Creating a Personal Prediction

We aim to track Parkinson's symptom fluctuations using analytical methods and evaluate them using measurements of participants' real symptom severity as ground truth. To fulfil this purpose, we scored several clinical scales and asked participants to self-report their most disabling symptoms (see section 3.1.4). In both cases, however, we are limited by what we call the "Ground truth Paradox". The paradox comes from the fact that our study, and those before us, tracks Parkinson's symptoms using sensors that produce objective and granular data to substitute scales used in clinical practice. This is needed because such scales are subjective, impractical to apply on a daily basis, or prone to recall bias. However, to date, they are the best tools that exist to assess patients health. Thus, our methods need to be evaluated using the scales they are trying to replace.

We collected the full MDS-UPDRS every three months, and the PDQ-39 and a cognitive battery every six weeks (see section 3.2). These tools are valid and reliable to assess Parkinson's symptom severity. However, our smartphone data

is collected continuously and can be summarised in hourly or daily periods. This means we have clinical scores that cover the past week (MDS-UPDRS) or the past month (PDQ-39) but that in practice cannot be directly paired up with our smartphone features in either an hourly or daily scale because people’s routines and their symptoms fluctuate over time. We could have interpolated the clinical scores as done by Tsanas et al. (2012) when predicting UPDRS scores of non-medicated patients with vowel phonations, but it is not realistic to assume that hourly, or daily smartphone-inferred behaviour has a monotonic linear change over months. Thus, we collected self-reported data to tackle this granularity mismatch.

We compile in Table 6.1 the top 3 symptoms chosen by each participant. In Table 6.2, we re-classify them according to relevant sections of the MDS-UPDRS. To tackle only a thin slice of this problem but at the same time explore data from as many participants as possible, we focused on self-reported fatigue, pain and gait problems as evidence suggests they affect human mobility (see section 2.4). These three categories cover ten pairs of self-reported symptoms from six participants: p01, p03, p04, p06, p07, p08 (first three rows of Table 6.2).

Table 6.1: Top 3 symptoms self-reported daily by p01-p08

Participant	Symptom A	Symptom B	Symptom C
p01	Dyskinesia	Slow Walk	Fatigue
p03	Pain	Low Energy	Freezing
p04	Tremor	Fatigue	Involuntary Movement
p05	Tremor	Swallowing	-
p06	Gait	Stiffness	Slowness
p07	Low Energy	Sleep	Attention
p08	Gait	Bradykinesia	Pain

Table 6.2: Top 3 symptoms self-reported daily by p01-p08 categorised according to relevant MDS-UPDRS sections.

Category	Participant symptom
Gait	p01-B, p03-C, p06-A, p08-A
Fatigue	p01-C, p03-B, p04-B, p07-A
Pain	p03-A, p08-C

Table 6.2: Top 3 symptoms self-reported daily by p01-p08 categorised according to relevant MDS-UPDRS sections. (*continued*)

Category	Participant symptom
Tremor	p04-A, p05-A
Dyskinesia	p01-A, p04-C
Bradykinesia	p06-C, p08-B
Rigidity	p06-B
Sleep	p07-B
Eating	p05-B

6.2 Implementing a Personal Prediction

To narrow down our data analysis, we only focus on features that are related to mobility and physical activity that were common to pain, gait, and fatigue as people with Parkinson’s are at higher risk of developing mobility limitations due to changes in motor and non-motor symptoms (Zhu et al., 2017). Although we could have computed proxies to sleep problems, detailed physical activity, and social interaction using the accelerometer, light, Bluetooth, calls and text messages logs, we leave these out for future work.

We computed 16 validated features from the literature to measure mobility and physical activity. Fourteen extracted from location coordinates using the R code provided by Barnett, Torous, Staples, Sandoval, et al. (2018) which is based on the work of Canzian et al. (2015), and two more from the Activity Recognition (AR) API in iOS.¹

The mobility features are based on the concept of a mobility trace defined by pauses (stops) and flights (moves). A pause is a period when a person does not move, and a flight is a segment of linear movement. Instead of implementing these features from scratch, we used a validated process (Barnett, 2018) that imputes missing flight and pause events inherent to non-continuous sampling rates (1 record every 3 minutes in our case). The process has four general steps, and a detailed description can be found elsewhere (Barnett, 2018):

¹We discarded Google’s AR API for p03 and p07 as we lost more than 50% of their data due to a library bug in Aware’s AR plugin for Android.

1. Project latitude/longitude coordinates to each person’s projection on a 2D plane.
2. Convert the projected data into to pauses and flights following a rectangular model (Shin et al., 2007).
3. Impute missing trajectories by resampling from observed events over each missing interval or sequence of events.
4. Compute mobility metrics.

We used the default parameters for the imputation and mobility metrics algorithms: considered radius from significant locations equal to 200 meters, “temporally local” as the imputation weighting method (events close in time tend to have similar mobility patterns), minimum pause duration equal to 120 seconds, and minimum pause distance equal to 50 meters (the last two values are parameters for the rectangular model to compute flights and pauses, and more information can be found elsewhere (Shin et al., 2007)). The only parameter we modified was the tolerated accuracy for the location coordinates which is a threshold to discard coordinate pairs with an accuracy lower than the provided value. In order to be conservative, we only kept pairs with an accuracy smaller than one mean plus half a standard deviation, in Table 6.3 we can see that we discarded 6%, 5%, 17%, 5%, 12%, 2% and 18% for participants p01 to p08.

Table 6.3: Location records included in the analysis with an accuracy lower than 1 mean + 0.5 SD

	Accuracy mean	Accuracy sd	Total records	Included records	%
p01	109.37	307.40	140,845	131,882	94
p03	84.86	276.93	354,906	336,641	95
p04	483.22	1024.50	296,062	247,192	83
p05	262.14	1026.01	317,941	302,699	95
p06	476.15	957.72	630,744	553,438	88
p07	104.07	3509.19	506,157	498,372	98
p08	462.93	777.16	453,963	372,810	82

In Table 6.4, we summarise the 14 mobility metrics using descriptions from this website (JP Onnela, 2018). A mathematical definition can be found in the paper by Canzian et al. (2015):

Table 6.4: Mobility metrics computed from location data

Mobility Metrics	Description
Time at home	Time spent at home in minutes. Home is the most visited significant location between 8 pm and 8 am including any pauses within a 200-meter radius.
Max home distance	Maximum distance from home in meters.
Pause probability	The fraction of a day spent in a pause (as opposed to a flight)
Circadian routine	A continuous metric that can take any value between 0 and 1, where 0 represents a daily routine completely different from any other sensed days and 1 a routine the same as every other sensed day.
Wkn circadian routine	Same as Circadian routine but computed separately for weekends and weekdays.
Distance travelled	Total distance travelled over a day.
Radius of Gyration (RoG)	It is a measure in meters of the area covered by a person over a day. A centroid is calculated for all the places (pauses) visited during a day and a weighted distance between all places and the centroid is computed. The weights are proportional to the time spent in each place.
Maximum diameter	Largest distance in meters between any two pauses.
Avg flight duration	Mean duration of all flights.
Avg flight length	Mean length of all flights
Std flight duration	The standard deviation of the duration of all flights.

Table 6.4: Mobility metrics computed from location data (*continued*)

Mobility Metrics	Description
Std flight length	The standard deviation of the length of all flights.
Significant locations	The number of significant locations visited during the day. Significant locations are computed using k-means clustering over pauses found in the whole monitoring period. The number of clusters is found iterating from 1 to 200 stopping until the centroids of two significant locations are within 400 meters of one another.
Significant location entropy	Entropy measurement based on the proportion of time spent at each significant location visited during a day. “Letting p_i be the proportion of the day spent at significant location I , significant location entropy is calculated as $-\sum_i p_i \log(p_i)$, where the sum occurs over all non-zero p_i for that day” (JP Onnela, 2018).

We extracted the AR features from iOS AR API. This API outputs one of 6 activities every time it is queried: stationary, walking, running, automotive, cycling, and unknown. We define movement time as the number of events labelled as walking, running and cycling. We define still time as the number of events labelled as stationary.

Thus, based on the features extracted and the literature we reviewed in section 2.4, we predict that when a person self-reports more severe fatigue, pain, or gait problems, each of our features should follow the trends in Table 6.5.

Table 6.5: Mobility metrics trends based on the clinical and monitoring literature

Symptom	Trend when symptom gets worse
Time at home	Increase
Distance travelled	Decrease
Radius of Gyration (RoG)	Decrease
Maximum diameter	Decrease

Table 6.5: Mobility metrics trends based on the clinical and monitoring literature (*continued*)

Symptom	Trend when symptom gets worse
Max home distance	Decrease
Significant locations	Decrease
Avg flight length	Decrease
Std flight length	Decrease
Avg flight duration	Decrease
Std flight duration	Decrease
Pause probability	Increase
Significant location entropy	Decrease
Circadian routine	Decrease
Wkn circadian routine	Decrease
AR Movement time	Decrease
AR Still time	Increase

6.2.1 Smartphone Features Preprocessing

We discarded days from our smartphone features where less than 15 hours of location data were collected. Although there are no suggestions in the literature on a minimum number of samples that need to be sensed to compute daily mobility features, we adopted the 10-hour threshold recommended by Zhu et al. (2017). We added 50% more hours to be more conservative, but it is essential to mention that such threshold was based on a 5 per second sampling rate vs our 3 per minute rate. In Table 6.6 we can see we did not include 28% of p01’s days, while for p03, p04, p05 and p08 we excluded around 13% of their days, and for p06 and p07 the loss was minimal (0.03% and 0.04%). Reasons for losing data include powering off the phone (deliberately or because of a flat battery) or being out of reach of a GPS satellite connection. For consistency, we excluded the same days from the AR data.

Table 6.6: Days where location data was collected during more than 15 hours (Valid days column). See also Figure 3.8 to Figure 3.14

Participant	Sensed days	Valid days	Invalid days	% of invalid days
p01	223	160	63	28
p03	224	195	29	13
p04	265	233	32	12
p05	269	238	31	12
p06	382	372	10	3
p07	366	350	16	4
p08	370	316	54	15

We imputed the missing days for all features for all participants using a Linear Weighted Moving Average (LWMA). We chose an LWMA (labelled `na.ma linear`) among 15 imputation algorithms following the methodology proposed by Moritz et al. (2015) (see Table 6.7). We used the time at home feature from p06 as it only lost 0.04 days of data (as defined above). We deleted days at random following an exponential distribution with 25 different random seeds at two different rates (0.1, 0.25) and imputed each iteration with 15 different algorithms (750 runs). We compute the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) for each run and average it per algorithm (see Table 6.8 and Table 6.9).

Although `na.aggregate` got the lowest MAPE for both rates, it does not take advantage of the time series nature of the data (all missing data is imputed with the mean). Therefore we chose a `na.ma linear` filter as it takes into account a seven-day window but with a geometric decrement (e.g. a day two days before a missing value is weighted 1/2) instead of a full weight (`na.ma simple`).

Table 6.7: Fifteen imputation algorithms tested with a random missing rate of 0.1 and 0.25.

Algorithm	Imputation Method
<code>na.aggregate</code>	Overall mean
<code>na.ma simple</code>	Simple moving average of 7 days
<code>na.ma linear</code>	Linear moving average of 7 days (arithmetical progression)

Table 6.7: Fifteen imputation algorithms tested with a random missing rate of 0.1 and 0.25. (*continued*)

Algorithm	Imputation Method
na.ma exponential	Exponential moving average
na.seasplit interpolation	Splits the times series into seasons and then imputes interpolation
na.StructTS	Seasonal Kalman filter
na.kalman StrucTS NoSmoothing	Seasonal Kalman filter without smoothing
na.interpolation spline	Spline interpolation
na.interpolation stine	Stine interpolation
na.kalman auto arima	Kalman smoothing on the state space representation of an arima model
na.seadec	Linear interpolation after removing seasonal component
na.interp	Linear interpolation after removing seasonal component (different implementation)
na.approx	Linear interpolation
ar.irmi	Iterative Robust Model-Based Imputation (IRMI) over lags
na.locf	Most recent non-NA prior to a missing value

Table 6.8: Average mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) over 25 simulations of 15 imputation algorithms with a random missing rate of 0.1. The lower the MAPE, the better an algorithm is suitable to impute data in our data features.

Algorithm	Miss Rate	MAPE
na.aggregate	0.1	1.50
na.ma simple	0.1	1.58

Table 6.8: Average mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) over 25 simulations of 15 imputation algorithms with a random missing rate of 0.1. The lower the MAPE, the better an algorithm is suitable to impute data in our data features. *(continued)*

Algorithm	Miss Rate	MAPE
na.ma linear	0.1	1.61
na.ma exponential	0.1	1.69
na.seasplit interpolation	0.1	1.76
na.StructTS	0.1	1.76
na.kalman StrucTS-NoSmoothing	0.1	1.84
na.interpolation spline	0.1	2.06
na.interpolation stine	0.1	2.06
na.kalman auto.arima	0.1	2.06
na.seadec	0.1	2.06
na.approx	0.1	2.06
na.interp	0.1	2.10
ar.irmi	0.1	2.38
na.locf	0.1	3.53

Table 6.9: Average mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) over 25 simulations of 15 imputation algorithms with a random missing rate of 0.25. The lower the MAPE, the better an algorithm is suitable to impute data in our data features

Algorithm	Miss Rate	MAPE
na.aggregate	0.25	3.35
na.ma simple	0.25	3.59
na.ma linear	0.25	3.68
na.seasplit interpolation	0.25	3.73
na.StructTS	0.25	3.73
na.kalman StrucTS-NoSmoothing	0.25	3.88
na.ma exponential	0.25	3.93
na.interpolation spline	0.25	4.68
na.interpolation stine	0.25	4.68

Table 6.9: Average mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) over 25 simulations of 15 imputation algorithms with a random missing rate of 0.25. The lower the MAPE, the better an algorithm is suitable to impute data in our data features (*continued*)

Algorithm	Miss Rate	MAPE
na.kalman auto.arima	0.25	4.68
na.seadec	0.25	4.68
na.approx	0.25	4.68
na.interp	0.25	4.68
ar.irmi	0.25	5.19
na.locf	0.25	7.48

Finally, we smooth out our mobility and AR features using an average moving window of 7 days. The ground truth data (diary self-reporting) was not modified in any way.

6.3 Applying a Personal Prediction

We tested our Personal Prediction (PP) on 10 self-reported symptoms of 6 participants (see Table 6.10). For each participant-symptom pair, we follow the same analysis pipeline. First, we personalise our initial PP with 16 features on 100% of each participant’s dataset to explore whether or not our method can track symptom fluctuations. Then, we investigate if the initial PP can be personalised in 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80% or 90% of the original data set to track symptoms on the complementary proportion (90%, 80%, ...). This evaluation strategy based on agreement (kappa), precision, and recall aims to explore whether collected data for a period is useful to track symptoms in future time blocks, and in consequence for how long a participant needs to collect ground truth data (equal to the length of the personalisation period). We follow Altman (1990) guidelines to interpret the kappa coefficient (see Table 6.11).

Table 6.10: Symptoms analysed with our Personal Prediction method as labelled by participants

Participant	Tracked Symptom (participant's label)	Category
p01	Slow walk	Gait
p01	Fatigue	Fatigue
p03	Low energy	Fatigue
p03	Pain	Pain
p03	Freezing	Gait
p04	Fatigue	Fatigue
p06	Gait	Gait
p07	Low Energy	Fatigue
p08	Gait	Gait
p08	Pain	Pain

Table 6.11: Kappa coefficient interpretation based on guidelines by Altman et al.

Kappa value	Strength of agreement
-1.00 - 0.00	-
0.00 - 0.20	Poor
0.21 - 0.40	Fair
0.41 - 0.60	Moderate
0.61 - 0.80	Good
0.81 - 1.00	Very good

All participant-symptom pairs were tested with the same Personal Prediction composed of 14 location and 2 activity recognition features. Our goal is not to identify or recommend smartphone features to contribute to the Parkinson's monitoring literature. Thus, we do not analyse in depth the meaning and recurrence of our features in the personalised models we create. However, we provide the following interpretation based on broad concepts of mobility for when these features are part of a personalised set for each participant.

Movement and still time, time at home, distance travelled, maximum diameter (longest distance between two stationary states -pauses-), number of significant locations visited (biggest concentration of pauses) and pause probability (proportion of day being stationary) are straightforward to interpret. For the other features we assume circadian routine is measuring the difference between the pauses and flights sequences between days, radius of gyration measures the area covered by a person in terms of a weighted distance to each pause, and significant location entropy represents the uncertainty of the proportion of a day a person spends at a significant place, thus if a participant is more fatigued or has more pain or has mobility problems, it is more likely that they will spend more time in a small subset of significant locations (staying at home for example).

Finally, flight-related metrics (avg/std duration and length) are a proxy to shorter/larger (avg) and less/more varied (std) movement bursts representing a more sedentary or active behaviour. We point out that the rectangular model on which the flights and pauses are computed is prone to produce short flights due to “geographical constraints such as roads, buildings, boundaries, etc.” (Shin et al., 2007). However, it is also expected that by increasing the observation area (in our case an unbounded area) we will see longer flights (Shin et al., 2007). We expect that since we compare these metrics within participants, any artefacts introduced to the flights due to geographical constraints or people’s routine will be similar over time, just as aggregating participants that move in the same constrained environment has been found reasonable (Shin et al., 2007).

We highlight that even though it is possible to interpret these features in general terms, there are confounding factors and “what if” situations that might skew their values and that we cannot discard without ground truth to validate them. For example, motor transportation was not removed, and it can be argued that driving does not represent the same physical effort compared to taking the bus or walking.

We also cannot assess the relevance of single features to mirror Parkinson’s symptoms fluctuations. That is why we sought confirmation from up to 16 features in our analysis, searched for their expected behaviour according to the literature, created a compliance threshold in our method, and selected the subset of features with the highest threshold (as many features behaving as predicted). Nonetheless, we do not know to what rate a higher compliance threshold implies more confidence that we are tracking symptom fluctuations. In Chapter 7 we

argue that patients' feedback can be used to confirm the relevance of smartphone features to track people's symptoms, but it was not possible for us to test this as the data analysis was done post-data collection.

In addition, although the symptom self-reported data has a higher time resolution than clinical scores, it has drawbacks. We did not assess the psychometric properties of our paper diary. Therefore, we do not know that the four-point scale we used (No to High Severity) did not have flooring or ceiling effects, or that the self-reported symptoms match their clinical definition (fatigue, pain, tremor). Nonetheless, this is not a problem for our analysis because we explore a personalised approach and so each participant can decide what a symptom means for them and how to assess its severity. We acknowledge that people's constructs and maximum symptom severity could have changed over time, and as such, we frame our results within this limitation as at this point there is no other solution.

Our method aims to track weekly symptom severity trends (a symptom is self-reported with lower or higher scores, and then those scores improve, get worse or stay the same over the week). We compare our method against a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC) to know if it is useful to track fluctuations better than chance. Although a kappa above zero between the output of our method and the ground truth already represents a better-than-chance agreement, we analyse the individual performance of each class against the RWC using precision and recall.

Yet, favouring precision or recall depends on the domain. In our case, two relevant questions are: is it more important to make fewer mistakes when classifying worse or better weeks at the risk of missing some of them (high precision)? Alternatively, is it more important to get all worse or better weeks with some level of error (high recall)? If clinicians would take action based on worse weeks (like changing patients medication), we could speculate they need high precision for such a class. On the other hand, if clinicians would like to cut off some measure of reassurance to patients to promote a feeling of optimism (e.g. by reflecting the stable nature of their condition in relation to their negative perception) (NICE, 2017), we could speculate that they need high recall on better weeks. However, as the applications and cost/benefits of personalised approaches for Parkinson's tracking are not known, we do not favour precision or recall in our results or method. Thus, in the results we present below, we only focus on whether the precision and recall of our method were higher than the RWC's.

6.3.1 p01 and Slow Walk

P01 self-reported slow walk problems over 17 weeks as better, 11 as worse, and 3 as no change from 24th July 2017 to 05 March 2018. We found that the best combination of features for this participant and symptom was formed by: distance travelled, maximum diameter, avg flight length, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, circadian routine, and time at home with a compliance of 0.57 (4/7), and a kappa of 0.53 (moderate agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to an RWC, we found that the precision and recall of worse and better weeks were better than chance by a margin of 0.26, 0.31 for precision and 0.54, 0.21 for recall (Table 6.12). In contrast, the precision and recall of the no change class were worse than chance (NA, -0.09) but this is because of the low ($n=3$) number of weeks belonging to that class. In Figure 6.1 we plot in a thick pink line with square symbols the weekly self-reported scores per class that we used as ground truth, and in a thin blue line with plus symbols the output of our method. If our method perfectly matched the ground truth, we would expect the thin line to follow the thick line. In practice, our method was able to track self-reported fluctuations in blocks, for example, the ten weeks from 23rd October to 25th December. This means p01's behaviour was consistent with what the clinical literature suggests during these blocks.

We explore if our method identifies relevant subsets of features based on a personalisation/testing splitting. All combinations of features are tested for a proportion (e.g. 90%) of the dataset and then filtered by kappa in descending order, by compliance in descending order, and by the number of features in ascending order. The top combinations according to these three criteria are then tested on the testing split (e.g. 10%). In Table 6.13, the "kappa (pers)" column shows the agreement of the best combinations of features identified in the personalisation proportion. After those are tried in the test proportion, the best one is picked ("Top prediction (test)") and "kappa (test)" shows its agreement, "features" show the number of smartphone features present in the top combination and "CT" (compliance threshold) the number of features that must behave as per the literature over each week.

We did not identify our main overall combination of features in any testing proportion except for the last one which was likely to happen because the 90% and 100% splits are similar (see Table 6.13). We also found that the performance

of the method measured by kappa was worse in all testing than personalisation proportions except for the first and last one (proportions kappas are plotted in Figure 6.2). In the first personalisation proportion (0.1), no combination had a kappa coefficient over 0. Thus single-feature predictions were given priority by our filters, and it turned out that for this participant, time at home was a relevant predictor. Indeed it is ranked fifth when all combinations were tested over 100% of the p01’s dataset. In the last personalisation proportion (0.9), the best combination with seven predictors had a perfect agreement because those last three weeks matched the type of behaviour that was seen during most of the personalisation phase.

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.3 and Figure 6.4), we can see that although kappa agreement is low, predictions like the one identified in proportions (0.2,0.3,0.4) can be more precise to detect specific classes (e.g. precision of 1.0 for better periods). Something similar happens with the recall (0.5) for the same proportions. As expected, precision and recall are high for the last and first proportion which had a high kappa. In other cases, precision and recall for all three classes are marginally better or worse than the RWC.

These results (and those similar from the rest of the participants) suggest that the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.12: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision and recall of both majority classes (worse and better) are better than an RWC which means our method can track weekly symptoms fluctuations of slow walk problems for p01 better than chance.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.62	0.36	0.26	0.91	0.37	0.54
no_change	NA	0.10	NA	0.00	0.09	-0.09
better	0.87	0.56	0.31	0.76	0.55	0.21

Table 6.13: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported slow walk of p01. The splitting strategy only found three subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column κ (test)).

train	test	κ (pers)	κ (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	0.00	0.34	1	1/1	time at home
0.2	0.8	1.00	0.16	6	4/6	distance travelled, avg flight duration, avg flight length, significant locations, significant location entropy, and time at home
0.3	0.7	0.81	0.15	6	4/6	distance travelled, avg flight duration, avg flight length, significant locations, significant location entropy, and time at home
0.4	0.6	0.57	0.22	6	4/6	distance travelled, avg flight duration, avg flight length, significant locations, significant location entropy, and time at home
0.5	0.5	0.66	-0.01	8	5/8	distance travelled, RoG, maximum diameter, avg flight duration, std flight duration, significant locations, significant location entropy, and time at home

Table 6.13: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported slow walk of p01. The splitting strategy only found three subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20 in column kappa (test)). (*continued*)

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.6	0.4	0.71	0.05	10	5/10	distance travelled, RoG, maximum diameter, std flight duration, significant locations, significant location entropy, circadian routine, time at home, movement time, and still time
0.7	0.3	0.68	-0.06	12	6/12	distance travelled, RoG, maximum diameter, avg flight length, std flight duration, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, circadian routine, time at home, movement time, and still time
0.8	0.2	0.52	0.00	12	6/12	distance travelled, RoG, maximum diameter, avg flight length, std flight duration, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, circadian routine, time at home, movement time, and still time
0.9	0.1	0.49	1.00	7	4/7	distance travelled, maximum diameter, avg flight length, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, circadian routine, and time at home

Figure 6.1: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported slow walk of p01. It reached a moderate agreement (kappa = 0.53)

Figure 6.2: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported slow walk of p01. The splitting strategy only found three subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.3: Precision for each testing period of self-reported slow walk of p01 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.4: Recall for each testing period of self-reported slow walk of p01 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.2 p01 and Fatigue

P01 self-reported fatigue problems over 12 weeks as better, 18 as worse, and 1 as no change from 24th July 2017 to 05 March 2018. This distribution is different compared to slow walk suggesting p01 endures and self-reports both symptoms in different ways. We found that the best combination of features for this participant and symptom was formed by: max home distance with a compliance of 1 (1/1), and a kappa of 0.37 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to a RWC, we found that the precision and recall of worse and better weeks were better than chance by a margin of 0.17, 0.21 for precision and 0.09, 0.36 for recall (Table 6.14). In contrast, the precision and recall of the no change class were worse than chance (NA, -0.03) because of the low ($n=1$) number of weeks belonging to that class. In Figure 6.5 we plot with square symbols the weekly self-reported scores by each week type and with plus symbols the output of our method. As with self-reported slow walk, our method was able to track fluctuations in blocks, for example, the eight weeks from 6th November to 25th December. Interestingly, the three biggest blocks of agreement almost coincide with those for this participant's slow walk which highlights the importance of including different metrics that can be personalised for different symptoms with different trends within the same person.

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.15). As opposed to slow walk, the best overall prediction was identified in 5 personalisation proportions (80%, 40%, 30%, 20% and 10%) with a fair agreement (kappa >0.3) except for proportion 30%. For the other proportions, movement time was identified as the best feature after personalisation, but its performance in testing was not better than random (kappa ≈ 0).

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.7 and Figure 6.8), we see that the precision for better and worse classes of the four proportions that found the best overall prediction were above chance. Recall was almost the same except for class worse during 20%, but this was because this proportion includes mostly worse weeks when our predictions were wrong. As with slow walk, the precision and recall for no change were poor due to the low number of weeks with this label.

Although the personalisation/testing results are better than for slow walk, the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for

symptom tracking, as a priori, it is not possible to know when to stop personalising and for how long the top combination will be relevant (testing length).

Table 6.14: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision and recall of both majority classes (worse and better) are better than an RWC which means our method can track weekly symptoms fluctuations of fatigue for p01 better than chance.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.75	0.58	0.17	0.67	0.58	0.09
no_change	NA	0.03	NA	0.00	0.03	-0.03
better	0.60	0.39	0.21	0.75	0.39	0.36

Table 6.15: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported fatigue of p01. The splitting strategy only found four subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)).

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	1.00	0.03	1	1/1	movement time
0.2	0.8	0.67	0.31	1	1/1	max home distance
0.3	0.7	0.57	-0.04	1	1/1	movement time
0.4	0.6	0.38	0.00	1	1/1	movement time
0.5	0.5	0.44	-0.12	1	1/1	movement time
0.6	0.4	0.39	0.33	1	1/1	max home distance
0.7	0.3	0.48	0.00	1	1/1	max home distance
0.8	0.2	0.38	0.33	1	1/1	max home distance
0.9	0.1	0.31	1.00	1	1/1	max home distance

Figure 6.5: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported fatigue of p01. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.37)

Figure 6.6: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported fatigue of p01. The splitting strategy only found four subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.7: Precision for each testing period of self-reported fatigue of p01 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.8: Recall for each testing period of self-reported fatigue of p01 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.3 p03 and Low energy

P03 self-reported low energy problems over 20 weeks as better and 11 as worse (0 no change weeks) from 24th July 2017 to 05 March 2018. We found that the best combination of features for this participant and symptom was formed by: avg flight length, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, and circadian routine with a compliance of 0.6 (3/5), and a kappa of 0.29 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to an RWC, we found that the precision and recall of worse weeks was better than chance by a margin of 0.19, 0.28. For better weeks, the precision was better by a narrower margin 0.11 but recall was practically equal to chance 0.01 (Table 6.16). No weeks were self-reported as no change meaning p03 would perceive this symptom as constantly fluctuating within a week. In Figure 6.9 we show how we can track fluctuations to a lesser degree compared to p01 but in blocks as well (up to 5 weeks).

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.17). The splitting did not find the best overall feature combination, but for personalisation 30%, 40%, 80% and 90% a very similar one was chosen. Nevertheless, the performance of all prediction in testing was worse than chance, indicating that the behaviour modelled during the personalisation was different from the one observed during testing (highest testing kappa was 0.19).

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.11 and Figure 6.12), we can see that the precision and recall for class better was marginally better or worse than chance. Something similar happens for class worse except for the first three proportions where both precision and recall were above chance by ≈ 0.23 with significant locations being a relevant feature to track fluctuations during the first nine weeks of monitoring.

As with previous participants, although kappa over personalisation is above 0.39 for all proportions, the kappa over testing is below 0.19 suggesting the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.16: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision of both majority classes (worse and better) is better than an RWC. Recall is better for both but the difference for the most common class (better) is marginal.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.54	0.35	0.19	0.64	0.36	0.28
no_change	0.00	NaN	NaN	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.76	0.65	0.11	0.65	0.64	0.01

Table 6.17: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported low energy of p03. The splitting strategy did not find subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$).

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	1.00	0.14	1	1/1	significant locations
0.2	0.8	1.00	0.09	1	1/1	significant locations
0.3	0.7	1.00	0.19	3	2/3	avg flight duration, significant locations, and circadian routine
0.4	0.6	1.00	-0.04	3	2/3	avg flight length, significant locations, and wkn circadian routine
0.5	0.5	0.85	0.04	1	1/1	significant locations
0.6	0.4	0.51	0.17	1	1/1	significant locations
0.7	0.3	0.50	-0.10	1	1/1	significant locations
0.8	0.2	0.39	0.00	5	3/5	avg flight length, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, and circadian routine
0.9	0.1	0.43	-0.50	5	3/5	avg flight length, std flight duration, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, and significant location entropy

Figure 6.9: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported low energy of p03. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.29)

Figure 6.10: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported low energy of p03. The splitting strategy found no subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.11: Precision for each testing period of self-reported low energy of p03 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.12: Recall for each testing period of self-reported low energy of p03 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.4 p03 and Pain

P03 self-reported pain problems over 16 weeks as better and 15 as worse (0 no change weeks) from 24th July 2017 to 05 March 2018. The best combination of features for this participant and symptom was formed by: avg flight duration, wkn circadian routine, and max home distance with a compliance of 0.67 (2/3), and a kappa of 0.35 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to a RWC, we found that the precision and recall of worse and better weeks were better than chance by a margin of 0.18, 0.17 for precision and 0.19, 0.17 for recall (Table 6.18). The difference is larger than those for the same participant's low energy. In Figure 6.13 we observe that we track pain in blocks just as it happened with previous symptoms. The two biggest blocks being 8 and 7 weeks.

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.19). Very interestingly, although the best overall combination was not identified, all combinations for proportions 20%-80% had a fair agreement ($\text{kappa} \geq 0.20$) when applied over the testing period. This suggests that this participant's symptom fluctuations were more consistent over time as suggested by the clinical literature and that avg flight duration is relevant to track p03's pain as it is shared among all but one proportion combinations of smartphone features.

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.15 and Figure 6.16), we see that the precision and recall for class better and worse was better than chance (albeit sometimes barely) on proportions 10% to 80%. As opposed to other symptoms and participants, pain and freezing for p03 were the only ones where the splitting was able to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking (7 out of 9 proportions).

Table 6.18: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision and recall of majority classes (worse and better) are better than an RWC which means our method can track weekly symptoms fluctuations of pain for p03 better than chance

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.67	0.49	0.18	0.67	0.48	0.19
no_change	NA	NaN	NA	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.69	0.52	0.17	0.69	0.52	0.17

Table 6.19: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported pain of p03. The splitting strategy successfully found seven subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)). p03 freezing and pain were the only symptoms where our method found suitable subsets for the majority of testing proportions.

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	1.00	0.06	3	2/3	distance travelled, avg flight duration, and wkn circadian routine
0.2	0.8	0.33	0.20	1	1/1	avg flight duration
0.3	0.7	0.37	0.33	3	2/3	avg flight duration, significant locations, and time at home
0.4	0.6	0.38	0.39	3	2/3	avg flight duration, significant locations, and time at home
0.5	0.5	0.50	0.38	5	3/5	avg flight duration, std flight duration, significant locations, pause probability, and time at home
0.6	0.4	0.47	0.33	5	3/5	avg flight duration, significant locations, pause probability, time at home, and max home distance
0.7	0.3	0.45	0.34	5	3/5	avg flight duration, significant locations, pause probability, time at home, and max home distance
0.8	0.2	0.44	0.33	5	3/5	avg flight duration, significant locations, pause probability, time at home, and max home distance
0.9	0.1	0.43	-0.50	5	3/5	avg flight duration, significant locations, pause probability, time at home, and max home distance

Figure 6.13: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported pain of p03. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.35)

Figure 6.14: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported pain of p03. The splitting strategy found seven subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.15: Precision for each testing period of self-reported pain of p03 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.16: Recall for each testing period of self-reported pain of p03 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.5 p03 and Freezing

P03 self-reported freezing problems over 20 weeks as better and 11 as worse (0 no change weeks) between 24th July 2017 to 05 March 2018. The best combination of features for this participant and symptom was formed by: RoG, avg flight duration, avg flight length, significant locations, and wkn circadian routine with compliance of 0.6 (3/5), and a kappa of 0.23 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to an RWC, we found that the precision and recall for class worse were better than chance by a margin of 0.2, 0.2 while only the precision of class better was better than chance 0.11, and its recall was worse than chance -0.04 (Table 6.20). In Figure 6.17 we can see that the tracking behaviour in blocks we observed in previous symptoms was only evident at the end of the monitoring period (7 weeks).

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.21). As we observed with pain for this same participant, the overall best prediction was not identified. Nonetheless, almost all predictions for the personalisation/testing proportions had a fair agreement with the ground truth. Again, significant locations was a relevant feature that was part of all predictions. In the two proportions with the worst kappa, our method found combinations with extra features (wkn circadian routine, pause probability, and significant location entropy) during the personalisation phase (kappa = 0.5, and 0.19). This shows how behaviour fluctuations included in the personalisation set can favour combinations that do not perform well on testing (significant locations on that proportion ranked 8th with a kappa = 0.32).

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.19 and Figure 6.20), we can see that the precision for both classes was better than chance as well as the recall for the worse class. The recall for class better was underperforming until tested with 50% or less of the dataset. This is, however, an artefact of eliminating non-conforming periods that were at the beginning of the dataset which can be seen in the recall of proportions 90%, 80% and 70% compared to 50%, 40%, 20% and 10%.

As opposed to other symptoms and participants, freezing and pain for p03 were the only ones where the splitting was able to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking (6 out of 9 proportions with kappa > 0.27).

Table 6.20: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision of both majority classes (worse and better) is better than an RWC. Recall is only better for the second most common class (worse).

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.55	0.35	0.20	0.55	0.35	0.20
no_change	0.00	NaN	NaN	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.75	0.64	0.11	0.60	0.64	-0.04

Table 6.21: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported freezing of p03. The splitting strategy successfully found six subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20 in column kappa (test)). p03 freezing and pain were the only symptoms where our method found suitable subsets for the majority of testing proportions.

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	0.40	0.27	1	1/1	significant locations
0.2	0.8	0.25	0.28	1	1/1	significant locations
0.3	0.7	0.55	0.19	1	1/1	significant locations
0.4	0.6	0.50	-0.01	3	2/3	significant locations, wkn circadian routine, and pause probability
0.5	0.5	0.42	0.38	1	1/1	significant locations
0.6	0.4	0.27	0.50	1	1/1	significant locations
0.7	0.3	0.19	0.14	3	2/3	significant locations, wkn circadian routine, and significant location entropy
0.8	0.2	0.14	0.67	1	1/1	significant locations
0.9	0.1	0.17	1.00	1	1/1	significant locations

Figure 6.17: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported freezing of p03. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.23)

Figure 6.18: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported freezing of p03. The splitting strategy found six subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.19: Precision for each testing period of self-reported freezing of p03 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.20: Recall for each testing period of self-reported freezing of p03 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.6 p04 and Fatigue

P04 self-reported fatigue problems over 4 weeks as better, 13 as worse, and 20 as no change from 24th July 2017 to 16 April 2018. In contrast to p01 and p03, p04 reported more stable periods than changing ones which matches our clinical assessments with the UPDRS (mean total scores of 81.8, 61.8, and 34.1 respectively) and PDQ39 (mean total scores of 17.0, 19.7, and 5.8, respectively). The best combination of features for this participant and symptom was formed by: avg flight duration, std flight length, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, circadian routine, movement time, and still time with compliance of 0.71 (5/7), and a kappa of 0.45 (moderate agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to a RWC, we found that the precision and recall for all three classes (worse, better, no change) were better than chance by a margin of 0.29, 0.06, 0.31 for precision and 0.18, 0.14, 0.31 for recall (Table 6.22). In Figure 6.21 we see that the tracking behaviour in blocks we observed in previous symptoms is found here with the longest block being nine weeks.

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.23). The best overall prediction was identified in the proportion 30% with the highest testing agreement among all proportions. Similar predictions were found in proportions 20% and 40% with fair and poor agreement respectively. Although with a negative kappa on testing, something similar is observed for proportions 60% to 90% where predictions have several features in common. Both results suggest this patient's behaviour is consistent in contiguous periods. We discuss in Chapter 7 how this observation could inform an alternative personalisation/testing strategy.

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.23 and Figure 6.24), we observe a similar behaviour as in previous participants. The minority class (better) has poor precision and recall. The majority classes (no change and worse) have better precision than chance from 90% to 60% of the testing proportions. This is of course linked to the kappa's trend described above, and we can see how precision and recall get worse than chance for the last testing proportions.

As with previous participants, although kappa over personalisation is above 0.41 for all proportions, the kappa over testing is below 0.15 for 7 out of 9 proportions suggesting the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.22: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision and recall of all three classes (worse, no change and better) are better than an RWC (albeit the precision of class better only marginally) which means our method can track weekly symptoms fluctuations for fatigue of p04 better than chance.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.64	0.35	0.29	0.54	0.36	0.18
no_change	0.85	0.54	0.31	0.85	0.54	0.31
better	0.17	0.11	0.06	0.25	0.11	0.14

Table 6.23: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported fatigue of p04. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)).

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	1.00	0.15	4	3/4	distance travelled, significant locations, wkn circadian routine, and movement time
0.2	0.8	0.77	0.23	5	4/5	avg flight duration, std flight length, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, and circadian routine
0.3	0.7	0.71	0.32	7	5/7	avg flight duration, std flight length, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, circadian routine, movement time, and still time
0.4	0.6	0.57	0.12	7	5/7	avg flight duration, avg flight length, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, pause probability, and circadian routine

Table 6.23: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported fatigue of p04. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)). (*continued*)

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.5	0.5	0.48	-0.15	2	2/2	significant locations, and pause probability
0.6	0.4	0.41	0.08	6	4/6	distance travelled, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, pause probability, and circadian routine
0.7	0.3	0.44	0.03	6	4/6	distance travelled, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, pause probability, and circadian routine
0.8	0.2	0.50	-0.35	6	4/6	distance travelled, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, pause probability, and circadian routine
0.9	0.1	0.45	-0.45	6	4/6	distance travelled, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, significant location entropy, pause probability, and circadian routine

Figure 6.21: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported fatigue of p04. It reached a moderate agreement ($\kappa = 0.45$)

Figure 6.22: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported fatigue of p04. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$).

Figure 6.23: Precision for each testing period of self-reported fatigue of p04 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.24: Recall for each testing period of self-reported fatigue of p04 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.7 p06 and Gait

P06 self-reported gait problems over 20 weeks as better and 22 as worse from 24th July 2017 to 30th July 2018. In contrast to other participants, the performance of our method was poorer: the best overall combination of features was formed by: avg flight duration, avg flight length, std flight duration, wkn circadian routine, and pause probability with a compliance of 0.6 (3/5), and a kappa of 0.18 (poor agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to a RWC, we found that the precision and recall for worse and better classes were only marginally better than chance: 0.09, 0.1 for precision and 0.08,0.1 for recall (Table 6.24). In Figure 6.25 we again see the fluctuation tracking happened in blocks, if not for two wrong classifications in the middle, the biggest block would be 15 weeks.

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.25). The best overall combination was not found in any proportion. In fact, although the kappa on all personalisation proportions is over 0.23, the kappa on all testing proportions was lower than 0.09. Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.27 and Figure 6.28), we observe that precision and recall for classes worse and better is only marginally better, but most of the time worse than chance. As with previous participants, the results suggest the personalisation/testing splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.24: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Although precision and recall for the two most common classes (worse and better) are better than the RWC, the differences are smaller with respect to other participants (0.08-0.10). Although technically our method predicted Gait problems for p06 better than chance, its relevance is likely limited.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.62	0.53	0.09	0.62	0.54	0.08
no.change	NA	NaN	NA	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.57	0.47	0.10	0.57	0.47	0.10

Table 6.25: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported gait of p06. The splitting strategy did not find subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column κ (test)).

train	test	κ (pers)	κ (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	1.00	0.09	3	2/3	distance travelled, avg flight length, and std flight duration
0.2	0.8	0.62	0.04	3	2/3	avg flight duration, std flight duration, and significant locations
0.3	0.7	0.36	-0.26	1	1/1	significant location entropy
0.4	0.6	0.31	0.05	3	2/3	avg flight duration, std flight duration, and significant locations
0.5	0.5	0.35	-0.07	3	2/3	avg flight duration, std flight duration, and significant locations
0.6	0.4	0.40	-0.19	3	2/3	avg flight duration, std flight duration, and significant locations
0.7	0.3	0.42	-0.43	3	2/3	avg flight duration, std flight duration, and significant locations
0.8	0.2	0.33	-0.30	3	2/3	distance travelled, avg flight length, and std flight duration
0.9	0.1	0.23	-0.15	3	2/3	distance travelled, avg flight length, and std flight duration

Figure 6.25: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported gait of p06. It reached a poor agreement (kappa = 0.18)

Figure 6.26: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported gait of p06. The splitting strategy found no subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.27: Precision for each testing period of self-reported gait of p06 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.28: Recall for each testing period of self-reported gait of p06 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.8 p07 and Low Energy

P07 self-reported low energy problems over 19 weeks as better and 27 as worse from 31st July 2017 to 06th August 2018. The best combination of features was formed by: distance travelled, avg flight length, std flight duration, significant locations, significant location entropy, circadian routine, and time at home with a compliance of 0.57 (4/7), and a kappa of 0.21 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to an RWC, we found that the precision for worse and better classes was only marginally better than chance: 0.11, 0.13 while recall was above chance for class better 0.18 and equal than chance for class worse 0 (Table 6.26). We observed that the biggest tracked block is six weeks long, but most of the other correct predictions are scattered over time (Figure 6.29).

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.27). We observed the same phenomena as with p06, the best overall combination was not identified, a single prediction was the most relevant (significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance) for proportions 30% to 80%, their performance on training was fair (> 0.20) but in testing was poor (< 0.10).

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.31 and Figure 6.32), we observe again something similar to p06, where precision and recall for classes worse and better is only marginally better, but most of the time worse than chance. These results suggest the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.26: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). As with gait for p06, precision and recall for the two most common classes (worse and better) are better than the RWC but the differences are small (0.08-0.10) except for recall for class better (0.17). Although technically our method predicted low energy fluctuations for p07 better than chance, its relevance is likely limited.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.68	0.57	0.11	0.57	0.57	0.00
no_change	0.00	NaN	NaN	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.56	0.43	0.13	0.61	0.43	0.18

Table 6.27: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported low energy of p07. The splitting strategy did not find subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)).

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	0.29	0.14	1	1/1	significant locations
0.2	0.8	0.30	-0.05	2	1/2	significant location entropy, and time at home
0.3	0.7	0.38	0.09	3	2/3	significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance
0.4	0.6	0.33	0.08	3	2/3	significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance
0.5	0.5	0.31	0.09	3	2/3	significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance
0.6	0.4	0.31	-0.03	3	2/3	significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance
0.7	0.3	0.25	0.00	3	2/3	significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance
0.8	0.2	0.23	-0.06	3	2/3	significant locations, pause probability, and max home distance
0.9	0.1	0.18	-0.15	3	2/3	distance travelled, avg flight length, and significant location entropy

Figure 6.29: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported low energy of p07. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.21)

Figure 6.30: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported low energy of p07. The splitting strategy found no subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.31: Precision for each testing period of self-reported low energy of p07 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.32: Recall for each testing period of self-reported low energy of p07 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.9 p08 and Gait

P08 self-reported gait problems over 29 weeks as better and 14 as worse from 31st July 2017 to 06th August 2018. The best combination of features was formed by: RoG, std flight duration, and still time with a compliance of 0.67 (2/3), and a kappa of 0.34 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to a RWC, we found that the precision and recall for class worse were better than chance : 0.18, 0.37 as opposed to only precision for class better 0.15 (recall was 0.01) (Table 6.28). Fluctuation tracking also happened in blocks with the longest being 12 weeks between 21st August and 20th November (excluding 04th September) and the second longest being ten weeks between 12th February and 16th April (excluding 2nd April) (Figure 6.33).

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.29). The best overall combination was identified from proportion 50% onwards, once more than half of the correctly tracked 12-week block is used in the personalisation set. As expected this feature has fair performance on testing at 60% and 90% (> 0.2) but not at 70% and 80% (< 0.1) where many incorrect blocks can be found in the personalisation sets (Figure 6.33).

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.35 and Figure 6.36), precision for both classes was better than chance in all but the first proportions. However, recall for class better was worse for all the monitoring period. We highlight the recall for class worse which was constantly better than chance which suggests this participant's behaviour was more consistent with our prediction during periods when his symptoms were worsening.

As with previous participants, although kappa over personalisation is above 0.34 for all proportions, the kappa over testing is below 0.20 in all but two proportions suggesting the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.28: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision for the two majority classes (worse and better) are better than an RWC. Recall for class worse is also better, but the recall for class better is equal to random chance.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff

worse	0.52	0.34	0.18	0.71	0.34	0.37
no_change	NA	NaN	NA	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.81	0.66	0.15	0.67	0.66	0.01

Table 6.29: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported gait of p08. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)).

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	1.00	-0.07	1	1/1	significant location entropy
0.2	0.8	1.00	0.06	5	3/5	RoG, std flight duration, significant location entropy, movement time, and still time
0.3	0.7	0.71	0.19	3	2/3	avg flight length, std flight duration, and still time
0.4	0.6	0.43	0.11	3	2/3	std flight duration, movement time, and still time
0.5	0.5	0.35	0.04	3	2/3	RoG, std flight duration, and movement time
0.6	0.4	0.38	0.20	3	2/3	RoG, std flight duration, and still time
0.7	0.3	0.42	0.09	3	2/3	RoG, std flight duration, and still time
0.8	0.2	0.39	0.00	3	2/3	RoG, std flight duration, and still time
0.9	0.1	0.34	0.29	3	2/3	RoG, std flight duration, and still time

Figure 6.33: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported gait of p08. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.34)

Figure 6.34: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported gait of p08. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.35: Precision for each testing period of self-reported gait of p08 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.36: Recall for each testing period of self-reported gait of p08 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

6.3.10 p08 and Pain

P08 self-reported pain problems over 23 weeks as better and 20 as worse from 31st July 2017 to 06th August 2018. The best combination of features was formed by: distance travelled, std flight duration, and still time with a compliance of 0.67 (2/3), and a kappa of 0.35 (fair agreement).

When we analysed the behaviour of each class compared to a RWC, we found that the precision and recall for both classes were better than chance: 0.2, 0.15 for precision and 0.2, 0.15 for recall (Table 6.30). Again we observed tracking blocks, the longest being 12 weeks from 11th December to 26th February. (Figure 6.37).

Although not identical, the self-reported data for p08's gait and pain are very similar, and in turn, the best overall predictions are also close (out of 3 features, the radius of gyration was replaced by distance travelled). This could be explained by the relationship between both self-reported symptoms, as for most of the study p08's was under treatment for a knee injury he suffered, thus affecting his experience of pain and gait problems.

We then explored a personalisation/testing split as explained before (Table 6.31). The best overall prediction was identified in the last two proportions with mixed results on testing ($k=0$, and $k=0.29$ respectively). As with previous participants, the predictions identified after personalisation performed poorly in testing ($k < 0.13$) except for proportion 30% ($k = 0.24$) and 90% ($k = 0.29$).

Analysing the performance of each class (Figure 6.39 and Figure 6.40), we observed that the precision and recall for both classes were marginally better than chance, except again for testing proportion 70% and 10%. As with previous participants, these results suggest the splitting is not a reliable method to personalise a set of smartphone features for symptom tracking.

Table 6.30: Comparison per class of the results of personalisation with 100% of the dataset vs a Random Weighted Classifier (RWC). Precision and recall of majority classes (worse and better) are better than an RWC which means our method can track weekly symptoms fluctuations of pain for p08 better than chance.

Class	Precision			Recall		
	PP	RWC	Diff	PP	RWC	Diff
worse	0.64	0.44	0.20	0.64	0.44	0.20
no_change	NA	NaN	NA	NA	NaN	NA
better	0.71	0.56	0.15	0.71	0.56	0.15

Table 6.31: Results personalisation/testing for periods (10% to 90%) of self-reported pain of p08. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.20$ in column kappa (test)).

train	test	kappa (pers)	kappa (test)	features	CT	Top prediction (test)
0.1	0.9	0.55	0.07	3	2/3	max home distance, movement time, and still time
0.2	0.8	0.60	0.00	3	2/3	std flight duration, movement time, and still time
0.3	0.7	0.59	0.24	3	2/3	std flight duration, max home distance, and still time
0.4	0.6	0.70	-0.01	5	3/5	maximum diameter, avg flight duration, time at home, max home distance, and still time
0.5	0.5	0.58	0.13	3	2/3	std flight duration, max home distance, and still time
0.6	0.4	0.57	0.01	3	2/3	std flight duration, max home distance, and still time
0.7	0.3	0.46	0.07	3	2/3	std flight duration, max home distance, and still time
0.8	0.2	0.43	0.00	3	2/3	distance travelled, std flight duration, and still time
0.9	0.1	0.37	0.29	3	2/3	distance travelled, std flight duration, and still time

Figure 6.37: Ground truth (square symbols) vs predictions (plus symbols) for each period of self-reported pain of p08. It reached a fair agreement (kappa = 0.35)

Figure 6.38: Kappa for each testing period of self-reported pain of p08. The splitting strategy only found two subsets of features able to track this symptom fluctuations with a fair agreement (kappa > 0.20).

Figure 6.39: Precision for each testing period of self-reported pain of p08 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the precision for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

Figure 6.40: Recall for each testing period of self-reported pain of p08 per class (better, worse or no change week). When the solid line is above the corresponding dashed line, the recall for that testing proportion (90,80,..., 20,10) for that class is better than chance.

The core idea of our method of using clinical literature to create a set of expected behaviour trends to track weekly symptom fluctuations with smartphone features was able to follow self-reported pain, gait, and fatigue changes with an agreement between poor and moderate. Unexpectedly, we found the agreement between our method and the ground truth happened in blocks, and the average block length among all participants (without taking into account one block interruptions) is 7.4 weeks (min 5, max 10). This suggests human behaviour is consistent with the clinical literature in “bursts”. When we explored, a personalisation/testing splitting strategy results were not satisfactory. Only 26/90 (28%) proportions we tested across all participants reached a fair agreement with the ground truth ($kappa > 0.2$). The splitting results and the block behaviour we observed suggest that although some past data is relevant to personalise a prediction, there is a point when people’s behaviour is not consistent; the length of this block is participant dependent and no general window size should be inferred. We discuss, the pros, cons, and limitations of our method in Chapter 7.

6.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, we have detailed the implementation of our Personal Prediction method. Informed by the clinical and technology-based monitoring literature, we selected a set of smartphone features that we hypothesised are related to the fluctuations of self-reported pain, gait, and fatigue.

After extracting 14 location and 2 activity recognition metrics, we applied our method to 10 symptoms from 6 patients. We show that our method is capable of finding a personalised subset of smartphone features to track the fluctuations of self-reported symptoms. We also explored if this method can be deployed following a personalisation/testing methodology that influences the period’s length during which the patient should collect ground truth. We discovered that this strategy is not optimal, as it cannot identify the best overall prediction consistently, and most of the predictions identified during the different personalisation proportions have poor performance in the testing periods.

This method is the third contribution of this thesis, and although still a proof-of-concept, it is evidence that it is possible to use behavioural traces to track Parkinson’s symptoms fluctuations.

Chapter 7

Discussion

In this chapter, we discuss the benefits and limitations of our method, the different technical and clinical assumptions we made during its creation and implementation, and what our results mean for our study and future personalised monitoring methods.

Our method identified a personalised subset of smartphone features for participants that tracks weekly symptom fluctuations better than chance. Our method reached a moderate agreement with self-reported ground truth for two participant-symptom pairs, p01 slow walk ($k = 0.53$) and p04 fatigue ($k = 0.45$), a fair agreement for seven pairs, p01 fatigue ($k = 0.37$), p03 low energy ($k = 0.29$), p07 low energy ($k = 0.21$), p03 freezing ($k = 0.23$), p08 gait ($k = 0.34$), p08 pain ($k = 0.35$), p03 pain ($k = 0.35$) and a poor agreement for p06 gait ($k = 0.18$). These results show the feasibility of using smartphone features to track weekly trends of Parkinson's symptoms.

Across all participants, the precision and recall of the best overall combination of smartphone features were better than a naive classifier (RWC). For our best results, p04 fatigue and p01 slow walk, the margin between our method and the RWC regarding precision was between 0.26 and 0.32 higher, and in terms of recall was between 0.20 and 0.54 higher for the two most common classes. For the other participants, their precision difference ranged between (0.09 and 0.22) and the recall difference between (0 and 0.38) with the second most common class having lower rates. The precision and recall of the minority class (either worse, better, or no change depending on the participant) were poor (worse than chance). This was expected given that in the personalisation process smartphone features are chosen to maximise kappa, and a correct match between our method and the

ground truth on the prevalent classes are more likely to affect this metric.

A prevalent approach to solve this imbalance problem in pattern recognition is to under- or oversample the dataset (Barandela et al., 2004; Chawla et al., 2002). Nevertheless, we question the relevance of this solution for our personalised models where the minority class depends on each patient’s health status. First, it is not clear if the minority class is relevant in clinical practice for that patient. Second, it is not known when or if a person will develop fluctuations labelled with that minority class and thus personalising a model might not be a pressing matter. Similarly, this makes us question our decision to classify all three classes with the same model. It might be more appropriate to personalise one model for each type of weekly trend (worse, better, and no change). This would mean reframing our multi-class classification problem as three binary classifications which would allow us first to test non-symmetric Personal Predictions if the literature suggests so (a smartphone feature can go up when a symptom goes up or down). In turn, this might generate different subsets of smartphone features each tailored to track improvement, worsening or stable weeks. Nonetheless, this may demand a longer dataset for each class or could potentially generate conflicting results that could be solved by the patient and their clinician.

In line with this, we acknowledge our assumption that summarising daily self-reported severity scores using a weekly linear trend is a proxy to Parkinson’s severity. We do not know the clinical relevance of these weekly summaries (Maetzler et al., 2016) and cannot discuss if a moderate or fair agreement over a group of weeks represents actionable information for patients or health professionals (albeit evidence suggesting people with Parkinson’s have an impaired lifestyle regularity (Camara Magalhaes et al., 2005)). However, we argue that these weekly fluctuations can play a role in patients’ care because they were freely chosen by our participants as the symptoms with the most impact in their daily lives and health-related quality of life is recognised as the most important indicator to evaluate the clinical and ecological relevant effects of a treatment strategy (Maetzler et al., 2016). We theorise these fluctuations can support clinical consultations by empowering patients and clinicians to explore behavioural trends and patterns while providing targets that are easy to understand and that follow simple rules describing the relationship between symptoms and smartphone features (i.e. weekly trends going up or down). In fact, fostering patients participation in their own care is recommended by the National Institute for Health and Clinical

Excellence (NICE) guidelines for the diagnosis and management of Parkinson's disease in primary and secondary care (NICE, 2017) and sharing information that patients can act on to better manage their health has been identified as the driver for a Precision Medicine healthcare programme (Flores et al., 2013). An early indication of the potential of this granular and longitudinal information is p07's search for daily triggers in his daily self-reported data to plan his routine (see section 4.3).

What is more, collecting smartphone data unobtrusively and in-the-wild from participant's smartphones represents an ecologically valid methodology that enables people to continue with their daily routines and relieves them from the burden associated with task-based assessments and the adverse effects of symptom awareness (Vega, Couth, et al., 2018). Alternatively, researchers could explore its suitability to track routine changes on at-risk people to prompt them to seek early clinical support, contributing to the preventive pillar of Precision Medicine (Hood et al., 2012). The first step in this direction is in progress in the European Horizon 2020 i-PROGNOSIS project programmed to run between April 2017 and October 2019, focusing on unobtrusive Parkinson's diagnosis using speech, movement, interaction and mood data extracted from smartphones (Iakovakis et al., 2018).

Our method was able to adapt to patients with different weekly trends. We monitored participants that self-reported a majority of weeks as "better" (e.g p01 slow walk), as "worse" (e.g. p07 low energy), as "no change" (e.g. p04 fatigue) or an almost balanced set (e.g p03 Pain) but our method reached an agreement better than chance for all of them. We highlight the case of p04 fatigue as it enabled us to explore our rule to label a week as no change only if both the positive and negative Personal Prediction were true or false. As expected, the compliance threshold we included played an important role. The compliance threshold for the best overall combination of features for p04 fatigue was 5/7. This means that p04's no change periods were labelled as such because the positive and negative predictions reached a compliance of 3 and 4 over several weeks. Thus, the method captures this situation by finding a combination of features and compliance threshold that is less likely (compared to lower thresholds) to find features that match our prediction by chance as more features (five) need to behave as suggested by the clinical literature. However, we cannot draw any conclusions about the second condition to label a week as no change (when both

predictions are correct), as p04 was the only participant with a majority of weeks from this class. This needs to be explored in the future.

Our method was able to track contiguous fluctuations. One of our concerns of interpolating or smoothing the daily features was introducing or extending artificial trends from past weeks into future weeks. Our results suggest that this was not the case. Although there are contiguous weeks from the same class where we could argue that interpolation or smoothing could have affected the results (like from 01st January to 22 January for p04), there are other correctly tracked periods where contiguous weekly trends change between classes (for example periods from 21 Aug to 11th Sept and 22nd January to 05th of February for p04, 14th January to 26th February for p03 freezing). However, we do not know if interpolation or smoothing are lowering the kappa coefficients (periods that were not classified correctly would be discarded or labelled differently with different interpolation/smoothing parameters). In the future, we must evaluate the effect of different smoothing algorithms and windows as well as the feasibility of choosing an imputation algorithm per feature and participant. P06 is an ideal participant to test this as her model got a poor agreement ($k = 0.18$), thus by varying imputation and smoothing rates we can explore changes in her kappa.

In relation to this, our method tracked the expected behaviour of our Personal Prediction in blocks. A Personal Prediction assumes the human behaviour being modelled remains constant over time. Thus, we did not expect to reach a perfect agreement with our ground truth. However, the predicted behaviour was observed over long continuous periods with an average length of 7.4 weeks (see Table 7.1). This suggests our participants' mobility as measured by the smartphone features followed the expected trend defined by the clinical literature. These blocks of behaviour make a case for a different personalisation/testing methodology that we detail below.

Table 7.1: Symptoms analysed with our Personal Prediction method

Participant	Tracked Symptom	Length in weeks of behaviour blocks
p01	Slow walk	10
p01	Fatigue	8
p03	Low energy	5 (10 with 1 interruption)
p03	Pain	8

Table 7.1: Symptoms analysed with our Personal Prediction method (*continued*)

Participant	Tracked Symptom	Length in weeks of behaviour blocks
p03	Freezing	7 (10 with 1 interruption)
p04	Fatigue	9 (10 with 1 interruption)
p06	Gait	6 (10 with 1 interruption)
p07	Low Energy	6 (8 with 1 interruption)
p08	Gait	9 (11 with 1 interruption)
p08	Pain	8 (12 with 1 interruption)

Our method can track non-motor symptom fluctuations. Using self-reporting to capture the most disabling symptoms for patients allowed us to track fluctuations in pain and fatigue. Although, these two symptoms are a small subset of all non-motor features people with Parkinson’s might develop, and our results should be interpreted within the limitations discussed below, our personalised methodology is responding to the “urgent need for developing unobtrusive systems to monitor non-motor endpoints in the home and community settings” as they are often sources of disability and a priority for patients, as our participants let us know (Espay et al., 2016). This represents a new alternative to investigate the relationship between human behaviour proxies and non-motor symptoms of Parkinson’s with a particular emphasis on neuropsychiatric symptoms as they have shown promise in previous research (Barnett, Torous, Staples, Sandoval, et al., 2018; Canzian et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2016).

The personalisation/testing split is not suitable for a real-world deployment. Given the behaviour blocks we observed, we were not expecting that the best overall combination of features (extracted from 100% of the data) would be identified reliably on the personalisation/testing splits. Indeed it would depend on whether these blocks were evenly distributed throughout the whole dataset, so our method would find them within the personalisation and testing proportion (which was something that we saw only with p03 pain and freezing). This splitting assumed that all data that has been collected in the past is valid to model fluctuations in the future.

With proportions 10/90, 20/80, 30/70 we explored if a few weeks of ground truth data (which would be convenient for participants) was enough to monitor a long period of fluctuations. Except for p03 freezing and some proportions of p01

slow walk, p01 fatigue, p04 fatigue, and p03 pain, the agreement for participants was poor (< 0.20). With proportions 40/60, 50/50, 60/40 we explored a more balanced splitting but except for p03 pain that reached a fair agreement on all three, and p03 low energy, p03 freezing, p01 fatigue, p01 slow walk that did so for one proportion, all other participant's agreement was poor (< 0.20). Finally, with the last three proportions 70/30, 80/20, and 90/10 we explored if by collecting more data we would capture enough fluctuation variability to track a short period (however burdensome it is to ask participants to collect ground truth data for 70%, 80%, or 90% of a year). It is not a surprise the agreement for proportion 90/10 of p03 freezing, p01 fatigue, p01 slow walk was perfect (1) given the behaviour blocks and the small number of weeks in the testing subset (3). This is because if this behaviour was observed enough times during the personalisation set, then the chosen prediction would perform well in testing. Despite these positive but misleading results, the agreement between the ground truth and the best predictions identified during the personalisation proportions was poor when applied to the test subsets.

Based on these outcomes, we propose a different splitting for future work based on contiguous windows. For example, personalise the prediction on one month of data, then test on the following month and repeat this for the following month pairs. This idea is based on the premise that behaviour is more similar in weeks that are closer to each other, something that we observed on the behaviour blocks and has been suggested in personalised tracking for mental health changes in people with schizophrenia (Wang et al., 2016). Different configurations should be explored, for example, whether or not the personalisation and testing windows have to be symmetric in size, the overlap between personalisation/testing contiguous windows which would take into account gradual changes of behaviour, and the length of each window. Researchers would want to reach a balance between the number of weeks a person must collect ground truth for and the agreement between the personalised prediction and the ground truth (the performance of the model).

In any case, this would require periodic ground truth collection, and therefore researchers need to investigate the acceptability and burden of such constraint. Nevertheless, we are optimistic this task might be feasible if participants are included in the design, and their workload is kept to a minimum based on the compliance rate of our paper diary. It is worth saying that this problem also

affects machine learning algorithms as most of them assume that the distribution of the training data (in our case the data used for personalisation) is static over time. However, human behaviour might change over time as we saw in our personalisation/testing proportion, making the predictions trained on past data invalid (Kubota et al., 2016). Then, ML models would need to be retrained with the consequent significant overhead due to the required expertise to do so (Q. Yang, Suh, et al., 2018). Alternatively, we would also explore the idea of a behaviour block catalogue: monitor people for one year as we did, personalise and test in short contiguous windows, gather a catalogue of personalised models (combinations of features), and then test over a second year choosing the best models from the catalogue according to the season of the year, or participant’s behaviour. This idea is similar to and might be accomplished through probabilistic topic models previously applied to discover routines using location data on an individual basis (Farrahi et al., 2011). That is, after modelling a patient’s routine using topics, we could group days or weeks according to their similarity which can guide the size of the personalisation/testing split. Then, we could choose an appropriate model depending on how similar the new block of behaviour is compared to the behaviour that generated each model. What is more, this could signal the moment when patients need to start collecting new ground truth after a significant number of days with unseen/different routines are detected, and no model is available to track symptoms.

Limitations. Our method reached a moderate agreement with two participants (p01 slow walk and p04 fatigue) and the distance of our method’s precision and recall to our random baseline suggest that we can track self-reported symptom fluctuations better than chance in some dataset proportions. However, there are different sources of error that need to be accounted for and represent research challenges to be tackled in the future.

- Validity of smartphone metrics. We computed 16 mobility metrics but did not have ground truth to measure the real movement of our participants, and as such we do not know, for example, for how long a person was at home. This is a limitation but also an inherent part of an in-the-wild, digital phenotyping study because the burden of asking participants to log their movement in addition to their symptom severity (ground truth data) is likely to affect adherence and enrollment in real-world deployments (Stopher et al., 2008), not to mention the extra self-reporting would also be prone

to recall bias and introduce a new error source, perhaps offsetting their benefits. Our best alternative was to rely on validated algorithms available in the literature and on the assumption that whatever difference there is compared to their real behaviour, it will be computed consistently over time. Future work could include the implementation of models validated on people with Parkinson's, but given the idiosyncratic nature of the disease, it is not clear if they would represent an improvement for personalised monitoring in comparison to healthy adults-based models. Alternatively, as technology evolves sensors will get better and so will our confidence in inferences derived from them (e.g. GPS chips with higher accuracy and resilience to physical obstacles (Moore, 2017)).

Our metrics may also be refined. For example, we did not exclude vehicle-based movement periods. Even though research indicates it is important to consider measures of different transportation modes, scientists recognise mobility performance might depend on personal factors (age, comorbidity, personal preferences, travel purpose) and external factors (built environment, access to urban and transportation services) (Zhu et al., 2017). Thus, we expect the effect of including or excluding motorised transportation to be participant dependent and leave for future work to explore how it affects our personalised models. Similarly, participant's travel purpose could be taken into account to differentiate between necessary trips (e.g. hospital appointment, driving to and from the airport) and optional trips that represent physical effort (e.g. a walk around the park or driving to swimming or yoga lessons). Likewise, our Activity Recognition metrics are a simplistic proxy to participants' movement based on the count of activity events that we deemed acceptable as our API pulling rate is consistent (3 min). An alternative is to use the confidence level provided by the API (low, medium, high) to include only trusted readings and generate movement episodes with daily duration and frequency. Nonetheless, using AR data might still be problematic as there is evidence that models calibrated on healthy subjects produce less accurate results compared to those calibrated on people with Parkinson's (Albert et al., 2012).

- Confounders in participants behaviour. It is not possible for us to verify when patients routines took precedence over their symptoms and vice-versa. When the tracking fails, is it because participants' symptoms are getting

worse, but they need to carry on with their activities? Alternatively, is it because participants' symptoms are getting better, but other circumstances make them behave as if not? These individual expected daily variations vouch for a patient-in-the-loop methodology that we outline below.

Comorbidity is another confounder that is likely to affect longitudinal monitoring approaches for the elderly. For example, we excluded demented or depressed participants and screened for cognitive decline at the middle and end (there was no decline in any participant as measured by the ACE-R, min score 97, max 100 for all participants). However, we did not assess depression at the end of the study, and thus there is a possibility that it interfered with our results given the link between depression and the mobility metrics we used (Canzian et al., 2015). Yet, comorbidity is a problem also present in traditional clinical assessment, addressed explicitly in the instructions of the MDS-UPDRS where it is recommended to assess what is seen without trying to identify the cause of impairment. P08 might be a good example as his knee injury could explain the similarity between his self-reported weekly trends for pain and gait (something we did not see for the symptoms of p01 and p03)

- Drawbacks of self-reporting. Although self-reporting might be the best way to obtain the degree to which Parkinson's interferes with daily living (Brown et al., 1989), doing so with a paper diary is prone to high attrition rates, forgetfulness, or retrospective error with truthful or fabricated answers as discussed in Chapter 4. Our paper diary's mean answer compliance rate was 96.34% over an average of 299 days. Still, we acknowledge that fabricated retrospective completion might have inflated this rate, but it is not possible to quantify it. Such a limitation is a trade-off we made to use the most suitable tool after a co-design process within our project constraints. Retrospective completion can be avoided by using digital approaches, for example, with a mobile app if it does not interfere with the research protocol, or a button-based approach like the one we prototyped, or the low-burden/high-compliance one implemented for hyperarousal episode monitoring (Eg Larsen et al., 2017). Another limitation of our diary is that we did not test its validity and reliability. While internal consistency (we only had 1 item in our scale) or equivalence (the diary is only to be rated by

one participant) are not a problem, stability might be, because the way patients conceptualise and measure symptom severity could have changed over time. The same is true for content, criterion, construct, and discriminant validity as we did not use a gold standard for pain, fatigue, or gait, and we did not assess how participants' definition of these symptoms compared to accepted clinical constructs. This is a limitation but a valid assumption in our analysis because we aimed to conceive a personalised approach where a participant's behaviour and symptom severity are compared within themselves. Thus, we do not claim that the personalised smartphone features our method found are useful to measure clinical constructs of pain, fatigue, or gait. Instead, they are valuable to track the self-reported constructs of each participant, which is encouraging evidence to investigate personalised approaches for delivering Precision Medicine.

What is more, regarding self-reporting for Parkinson's Disease, researchers and designers can use the five design implications we shared to conceive better digital and analogue tools (see section 4.3 and our published paper (Vega, Couth, et al., 2018)). Through our design process our participants supported the idea that even though they manifest diverse symptoms as the literature indicates, there is a small subset of them that affect their daily life. Thus, we suggest that this encourages the development of low-burden and validated clinical questionnaires that measure the most disabling motor or non-motor aspects of each person with Parkinson's like the PDQ-8 (Jenkinson et al., 1997). Alternatives include the digitalisation of existent scales or electronic tests that participants can complete periodically on their own like voice-based assessments (Tsanas et al., 2010), the cloudUPDRS app (Stamate et al., 2018), or an iPad-based spiral drawing test (Sisti et al., 2017). In the next section, we speculate how a patient-in-the-loop approach could complement self-reporting.

Improvements. Our method has several parameters: length of periods (weeks), method to measure change on periods (slope linear regression), compliance threshold ($F/2$ to F), criteria to label periods as better, worse, or no change, metric to assess personalisation (Cohen's kappa), and criteria to rank the best prediction (Cohen's kappa, compliance threshold, number of features).

We chose seven days as the fluctuation period's length to match participants' schedules but lengths from 2 to 15 days can be explored with weekday/weekend

stratification to account for personal differences. Potentially, researchers could explore collecting self-reported ground truth data at intervals instead of on a daily basis if multi-day trends are found clinically useful. To measure change, we can split our period in two, summarise each half with a statistic (like mean), and subtract both values, or we can also use statistical methods like Sen's slope (Pohlert, 2018) which in addition to a slope magnitude, provides confidence intervals and a p-value that could be used to rank positive and negative changes. Our method tested all feature combinations using $F/2$ to F compliance thresholds to reduce the computation time and probability of finding a relevant prediction by chance. However, the role of the thresholds from 1 to $F/2$ needs to be studied further to understand the trade-off between flexibility and the likelihood of finding by chance smartphone features that behave as indicated by the literature.

We used a rudimentary cut-off to classify weekly periods: a true positive prediction represented a negative change (positive slope), a true negative prediction represented a positive change (negative slope), and neither or both represented no change. With a different method to measure change like Sen's slope, we could set thresholds to rank a negative or positive change (in a similar way to how Cohen's kappa is ranked as poor, fair, moderate, etc.) and classify a period as no change when their slope is not significant ($p\text{-value} \leq \alpha$), when is zero, or when the confidence intervals include zero. In this way, we can potentially track more granular changes, although their clinical relevance would still need to be validated. We used Cohen's kappa to measure the performance of the personalisation stage as it gave equal weight to our three unbalanced classes. Nonetheless, a weighted kappa or precision and recall could be used to give priority to certain classes as discussed before according to clinical priorities. Finally, we chose the most appropriate prediction for each participant prioritising agreement (higher kappa), strictness (higher compliance threshold), and model simplicity (lower number of features), other combinations of these three factors should be explored, including the alternatives to the kappa coefficient that we discussed above.

The computational complexity of our method was exponential $2^F \times (F/2)$. Dimensionality reduction algorithms can be used to get rid off unnecessary features. It has been found that features based on the same behaviour type are correlated, including the mobility metrics we used (Barnett, Torous, Staples, Keshavan, et al., 2018). There are a wide variety of dimensionality reduction algorithms some of which can reduce the interpretability of the reduced factors. However, this can

be compensated by including smartphone features based on various behaviours (as we found in the literature, for example, to model the relation between sleep and fatigue). An overview of filters, wrappers and, embedded dimensionality reduction methods can be found elsewhere (Pocock, 2012).

We argue for keeping participants in-the-loop when developing and deploying personalised methods. This is in line with the participatory component in the P4 model of Precision Medicine [Hood2012]. More specifically, a participant's experience can inform the formulation of their Personal Predictions. Patients could be interviewed a priori or a posteriori to confirm or override the expected behaviour according to the clinical literature. Similarly, patients' feedback can be used to reduce the number of features we include in a personal prediction, based on the perceived impact of their symptoms in their routines (a human-informed dimensionality reduction method). If researchers follow a contiguous personalisation/testing window approach as suggested before, participants can be consulted after the first windows to verify if the fluctuations on their symptoms and the features associated correspond to a real change in their condition. For example, they can clarify when/if external circumstances made them behave differently (e.g. family problems, co-morbidities, holidays, etc.).

We also speculate that patients could participate in the training and validation of machine learning algorithms instead of relying on experts. Of course, this is a challenging task. Human-centred machine learning is a novel area with open research questions that focus on the role humans play in the creation of models, accessibility challenges, changes to current ML practices and theory, novel models, applications, and evaluation (Gillies et al., 2016). Researchers have identified four fields of expertise instrumental for the success of ML based on a study on how non-experts (people that do not have a degree in ML, statistics, mathematics or artificial intelligence) build ML models for diverse purposes in a real-world context (Q. Yang, Suh, et al., 2018): problem understanding, subject matter expertise, engineering expertise, and machine learning expertise. In the context of our problem and if we consider that the goal of a personalised model is to track individual symptom fluctuations based on human behaviour proxies, it is fair to assume that patients have a reasonable understanding of the problem (if presented in simple enough terms), and are experts in the matter of perceiving their disease progression and its impact on their daily lives. However, a human-centric approach for Parkinson's monitoring has to assume that patients have

no engineering or machine learning expertise. Also, researchers would need to consider other challenges like patient engagement, biases that might come along recalling daily activities and symptoms, and the negative impact of symptom awareness on the emotional state of patients (Vega, Couth, et al., 2018). A more detailed discussion of the potential of this approach is outside of the scope of this dissertation, but we refer the reader to recent publications that address solutions, challenges, current applications, and the potential of human-centric machine learning approaches (Dudley et al., 2018; Fiebrink et al., 2018; Q. Yang, Banovic, et al., 2018; Q. Yang, Suh, et al., 2018).

Independently of the solution to be explored, it is necessary to investigate the clinical relevance of the output of personalised models and how they might support clinical practice (Maetzler et al., 2016) as our ability to display actionable information to stakeholders is open for improvement (Espay et al., 2016). Intuitively, clinicians should be involved, but future research should explore if it is possible to leverage their expertise to assess the relevance and interpretability of smartphone features and fluctuation tracking, or even if health professionals can be part of the evaluation pipeline along with patients, taking advantage of their domain knowledge but also facing time, budget and other constraints inherent to current clinical practice.

7.1 Summary

In this chapter, we highlighted how our method can personalise a set of smartphone features to track self-reported symptom fluctuations better than chance, how it adapts to different types of weekly fluctuations, how it tracks fluctuations in blocks of behaviour, how it tracks non-motor fluctuations (as opposed to focusing only on motor symptoms), and how splitting participants' datasets into personalisation/testing proportions is not a suitable strategy to find a subset of features to track fluctuations. We also discussed the three primary sources of error in our methodology: validity of the smartphone features, confounders in participants behaviour, and drawbacks with self-reporting. Finally, we elaborated on how our method could be improved, alternatives to assumptions we made during our analysis, potential solutions to the personalisation/testing splitting, and a participant in-the-loop approach to focus and evaluate the relevance of a Personal Prediction.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Future Work

8.1 Conclusions

We answered RQ1, “What smartphone data is suitable to track Parkinson’s symptoms working around technological, ethical, and UX limitations?” by showing that smartphone features related to mobility and physical activity extracted from location and activity recognition data can track fluctuations in self-reported pain, gait, and fatigue. This is not an exhaustive list, and the personalised relationship between other features and Parkinson’s symptoms remain unexplored.

The idiosyncratic nature of Parkinson’s and the wide variety of data that can be collected from smartphones make our datasets the first contribution of this thesis (including the second dataset we collected between December 2017 and October 2018 that we did not analyse). These datasets are between 31 and 52 weeks long and have between 11 and 22 different data sources possibly relevant to Parkinson’s symptom tracking in the wild. They include clinical ground truth collected every 6 and 18 weeks, as well as daily self-reported symptom severity of motor and non-motor symptoms.

Although some of the data collection constraints we faced should disappear in the future as data collection software matures, new technological limitations are likely to appear as mobile platforms impose stronger restrictions for developers to access raw data. These obstacles should not be disregarded as they hinder the deployment of monitoring approaches in naturalistic conditions. For example, touchscreen events logging which requires admin privileges in Android phones, or app interaction collection which relies on accessibility services and that is no longer allowed if not aimed at supporting people with disabilities (“Accessibility

overview | Android Developers,” 2018). In addition to the data collection, storage, and transmission considerations we implemented, unforeseen ethical and privacy constraints are likely to arise as technology evolves and legal and ethical systems catch on. Finally, UX constraints, even if minimal in an unobtrusive approach like ours, can have a significant impact on participant enrollment (e.g. depleting the battery life of people’s devices). What is more, if we are to include patients in a personalised monitoring loop, we will face challenging HCI obstacles related to participants’ engagement, biases, and clinical benefits.

We answered RQ2, “What symptom assessment methods are appropriate to use as ground truth to validate our methods?”, by showing analogue self-reported symptom severity scores can be collected over 299 days with 96.39% compliance. As the second contribution of this dissertation, we generated knowledge that supports longitudinal ground truth collection for Parkinson’s tracking. A personalised, cheap, accessible, frictionless, portable, low-demand, automatically encoded, and flexible paper diary for daily symptom self-reporting. Paperstream, a multi-platform open-source software tool to create and encode paper diaries and surveys automatically. And five design implications that support future researchers aiming to create digital or analogue instruments for self-reporting: reduce participant completion demand, design to offset the effect of tremor on input, enable implicit reminders, design for positive and negative consequences of increased awareness, and, consider the effects of handwritten notes in compliance, encoding burden and data quality. Nonetheless, despite the high face validity and other advantages of self-reported data, its clinical validity and usefulness should be investigated further, and a digital or analogue tool should be chosen according to the projects needs and aims.

We answered RQ3, “Can we use behavioural traces to track Parkinson’s symptoms fluctuations?” by showing a set of smartphone features can be narrowed down to track individual symptom fluctuations. The third contribution of this thesis is our “Personal Predictions” method that based on behaviour trends suggested by the clinical literature, adapts a set of smartphone features that best follow this behaviour to track weekly self-reported symptom fluctuations in pain, gait, and fatigue.

The agreement between our method and the ground truth ranged between poor and moderate agreement (Cohen’s kappa between 0.19 and 0.53). The precision and recall of the two majority classes of weekly fluctuations for each

participant (better, worse, no change) were better than chance. However, a real-life deployment strategy based on a personalisation/testing split (e.g. 90%/10%) was not able to identify smartphone feature subsets relevant to track fluctuations better than chance on unseen data. Nonetheless, our results suggest the unobtrusive and personalised monitoring methodology we proposed, can be improved to track fluctuations in Parkinson's symptoms with the most impact on patients daily life.

8.2 Future Work

Additional research opportunities were identified throughout the design, instrumentation, implementation, analysis, and discussion of this project.

Augment current mobility and activity recognition smartphone features. Current mobility smartphone features can be segregated by transport type, weather conditions, time of the day, day of the week (like done with circadian routine) and time of the year. Current activity recognition features can be computed by episode and frequency and segregated at different time scales as mentioned before. Additionally, new ones can be extracted using different algorithms relying on accelerometer data (if collected with enough frequency to not depend on native APIs). Geographical information can be taken into account to create additional and more complex mobility metrics for example for quantifying duration and frequency of work-related, recreational, or on holiday activities.

Investigate other behavioural areas and smartphone features. Our methodology is agnostic to the data collection device so physiological data or inertial data can be included if devices like smartwatches are ubiquitous in the lives of people with Parkinson's. Extra features can be extracted and explored from existing smartphone sensors like done by others in the Ubicomp field for measuring conversation, sleep, noise levels, face to face encounters, voice features, daily chores, communication patterns, social media, among others. (Chen et al., 2013; Glenn et al., 2014; Harari et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2017, 2015). From a time series perspective, even more features could be computed (Christ et al., 2018) but we would be cautious when using them as some might be difficult to interpret for patients and clinicians which is relevant if they are to be kept in the loop. More specifically, we recommend the behavioural areas that we did not explore due to technical or practical reasons: typing patterns based on mobile keyboard use

(Arroyo-Gallego et al., 2017), phone usage patterns based on screen and app interaction, episodes of going up/down stairs based on location, WiFi and barometer data, and social interaction patterns based on Bluetooth, WiFi, location, and communication logs.

Investigate other ground truth collection methods that minimise problems related to self-reported data. Although we found a paper diary a suitable tool for data collection, researchers can explore the potential of electronic instruments with physical interfaces (e.g. buttons) to blend within participants routines while being personalised, portable and straightforward to use. This could allow us to measure and possibly alleviate retrospective completion and the negative consequences of symptom self-awareness when self-reporting data.

Investigate the clinical relevance of weekly fluctuations and insights gotten from our personalised model. The clinical relevance and usefulness of the weekly fluctuations we track should be explored in cooperation with clinicians and people with Parkinson's. Nonetheless, we consider them relevant as our participants ranked the severity of the symptoms that most affect their daily lives, and the subjectivity of this construct make patients probably the best person to define it (Hobson et al., 1999). The use of personalised models in clinical practice or patient self-management will also inform the choice of performance metric (e.g. precision, recall) which warrants further research.

Investigate the model's parameters and variations. Researchers can explore the effect of modifying and replacing our method's parameters. Shorter or longer fluctuation period lengths, currently we use seven days starting on Mondays. Lower compliance thresholds, currently ranging from half to the total number of features. Alternative metrics to assess the relevance of a subset of smartphone features to track fluctuations; we used Cohen's kappa, compliance threshold, and the number of features in the model but this decision could be informed by the clinical aim of the personalised model. Including feature selection algorithms giving priority to those that do not hinder feature interpretability. Different ways to measure severity trends, currently done using the slope of a linear regression, but swappable by methods like Sen's slope which in turn would allow for a different criteria to classify a fluctuation trend as "better", "worse", or "no change" and even create ranks within the first two classes. Different methods (like the angle or pause models) to extract mobility pauses and flights, currently using a rectangular model (Shin et al., 2007).

Besides, researchers should question the technical and clinical impact of ignoring uncommon types of weekly fluctuations within a participant. Furthermore, alternative real-world deployment strategies should be explored, and we suggest a contiguous windowed split for personalisation and testing along with topic models to measure patient's routine change and inform ground collection timing and window size.

Investigate a patient in-the-loop approach. In the short term, it is worth exploring approaches testing automated machine learning (Feurer et al., 2015), incremental machine learning (Gepperth et al., 2016), or time series based methods (Barnett, Torous, Staples, Sandoval, et al., 2018). In the long term, we suggest investigating the challenges of keeping patients and clinicians engaged in the creation, deployment, and evaluation pipeline of their personalised models. Asking patients to accept or reject the smartphone features that are part of the model to be personalised, to confirm the relevance of a model, or to identify relevant confounding factors after their model has been deployed. Relevant research questions include: what algorithms can be adapted for personalised monitoring using small but longitudinal data while being interpretable for clinical use? To what degree can we involve participants in the algorithms' personalisation/testing loop? What are the most effective methods to keep patients engaged so that they self-report data reliably?

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Appendix A

Pilot Study

We conducted a pilot study between July 1st and September 21st 2015 to explore the technological and UX challenges of monitoring Parkinson’s Disease using smartphones and leverage any insights to plan our main monitoring study. The pilot was our contribution to a project in partnership with researchers of the Division of Neuroscience and Experimental Psychology, from the School of Biological Sciences of the University of Manchester (Couth et al., 2016). Seven people with Parkinson’s were contacted through their local clinics, and three gave their signed consent to take part in the study (1 female, ages 58, 72 and 70). All participants were non-demented as assessed by the Addenbrooke’s Cognitive Examination-Revised (ACE-R) (Mioshi et al., 2006) and diagnosed with mild idiopathic PD as quantified by stages 1 and 2 of the Hoehn and Yahr Scale (Hoehn et al., 1967).

A.1 Materials

We screened the software and hardware available to collect smartphone sensor data. We had two constraints: a budget of £900 and the need for six phones (three for our pilot and three more for our main study). In June 2015, iOS, Android, and Windows Phone (WP) were the most prevalent mobile operative systems in the market.¹ We discarded iOS because it was out of our budget and WP because there were no data collection apps available for it. For Android, we found five mobile applications available for collecting raw sensor data (Table A.1) out of which we adopted Aware because it was open source, documented, under active development, and easy to extend through a plugin platform.

¹<http://www.idc.com/prodserv/smartphone-os-market-share.jsp>

From all Android smartphones available in June 2015 we selected those with a battery life greater than 8 hours² (we list their included sensors, price, storage, and Android version³ in Table A.2). We were looking for a smartphone with the longest battery life, lowest price and highest number of sensors (to explore as many smartphone features as possible) so we purchased a Sony Xperia Z3 Compact (XPE) and five Blue Studio Energy (BSE) to compare both devices' battery life vs the number and type of available sensors.

Table A.1: Comparison of Android apps/libraries to collect smartphone data as of June 2015

Project	Open Source	Library or App	Active development	Raw Features	Context Features	Modules
AndWellness	Yes	App	No	1	1	Yes
Funf	Yes	Both	No	37	0	Yes
EmotionSense	Yes	Library	Yes	23	0	Yes
Ohmage	Yes	Both	Yes	16	2	Yes
Aware	Yes	Both	Yes	26	6	Yes

Table A.2: Phone comparison for the pilot study done in June 2015.

Phone	Battery	Price	Compass	Light	Gyroscope	Barometer	Android
Blue Studio Energy	14h 53m	110	Yes	Yes	No	No	4.4
Huawei Ascend Mate 2	11h 29m	304	Yes	No	Yes	No	4.3
ZTE ZMax	10h 53m	170	No	No	Yes	No	4.4
Motorola Droid Turbo	10h 42m	500	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	4.4
ZTE Grand X MAX+	10h 20m	191	No	Yes	Yes	No	4.4
Sony Xperia T2 Ultra	10h 16m	200	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	4.4
Sony Xperia Z3 Compact	10h 02m	322	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	4.4

²<http://www.phonearena.com/>

³<http://gadgets.ndtv.com>

Table A.2: Phone comparison for the pilot study done in June 2015. (*continued*)

Phone	Battery	Price	Compass	Light	Gyroscope	Barometer	Android
Sony Xperia Z3	09h 29m	469	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	4.4
Sony Xperia M2	09h 19m	141	Yes	Yes	No	No	4.4
Meizu MX4 Pro	09h 19m	354	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	4.4
Huawei Ascend MATE 7	09h 03m	335	Yes	Yes	No	No	4.4
Sony Xperia C	08h 44m	161	Yes	No	No	No	4.2
Samsung Galaxy Note 4	08h 43m	509	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5.0
LG G2 Mini	08h 32m	139	Yes	No	No	No	4.4
Xiaomi MI 4	08h 32m	279	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	4.4
Acer Liquid J S	08h 32m	200	Yes	Yes	No	No	4.4
Sony Xperia T3	08h 23m	206	No	Yes	No	Yes	4.4

A.2 Deployment

We installed Aware for Android and configured the sensors shown in Table A.3 respecting their sensing rate defaults. We tested increasing the accelerometer rate from 5Hz to 16.6Hz (the next configurable option), but it depleted the battery in 8 hours on our XPE while resting on a desk with WiFi, GPS, and Bluetooth on. It will not be possible to measure tremor while participants use their phones as action tremor has a frequency between 7Hz and 12Hz (Lance et al., 1963), but it can still be useful to get rough measurements of movement. We stored the data locally on each device and did a manual backup every week. We extended Aware to add local encryption using the SQLCipher libraries⁴, configured the “Automate” Android app to zip the encrypted SQLite databases every day at 2.00 a.m, and the “Synchronize Ultimate” Android app to send these backups to a server in the University every day at 3.00 a.m. We also used the “AppLock”, “AppStart” and “Keep Running” Android apps to block, start on boot, and keep Aware, “Automate”, and “Synchronize Ultimate” running in the background.

Participants had the choice to use our smartphones as primary or secondary devices. P01 opted for a BSE as a secondary device (she did not want to use

⁴<https://www.zetetic.net/sqlcipher/>

a touchscreen), while p02 adopted the XPE and p03 a BSE with a double SIM configuration as primary phones. Participants were only instructed to recharge their devices every night and carry them for as long as possible during the day.

Table A.3: Aware sensing configuration for the pilot study

Sensor	Sony Xperia Z3 Compact (freq)	Blu Studio Energy (freq)
Accelerometer	On (5Hz)	On (5Hz)
Applications (foreground)	On	On
Applications (history)	On	On
Applications (notifications)	On	On
Applications (crashes)	On	On
Barometer	On (5Hz)	-
Battery	On	On
Bluetooth	On (1 min)	On (1 min)
Calls data	On	On
Messages data	On	On
ESM	Not Used	Not Used
Gravity	On (5Hz)	-
Gyroscope	On (5Hz)	-
Installations	On	On
Light	On (5Hz)	On (5Hz)
Linear accelerometer	On (5Hz)	-
GPS	Not Used	Not Used
Magnetometer	On (5Hz)	On (5Hz)
MQTT	Not Used	Not Used
Network data	-	-
Network traffic data	On	On
Keyboard typing	On	On
Processor	On (10 sec)	On (10 sec)
Proximity	Not Used	-
Rotation	On (5Hz)	-
Screen	On	On
Significant Motion	-	-
Telephony data	On	On
Telephony GSM data	On	On
Temperature	-	-

Table A.3: Aware sensing configuration for the pilot study (*continued*)

Sensor	Sony Xperia Z3 Compact (freq)	Blu Studio Energy (freq)
Timezone	On (1 day)	On (1 day)
WiFi	On (1 min)	On (1 min)
Plugin Google Activity Recognition	On (1 min)	-
Plugin iOS Activity Recognition	-	-
Plugin Ambient Noise	On (5 min)	On (5 min)
Plugin Contacts	Not Used	Not Used
Plugin Conversations	Not Used	Not Used
Plugin Device Usage	Not Used	Not Used
Plugin Fitbit	Not Used	Not Used
Plugin Google Login	Not Used	Not Used
Plugin Fused Location	On (3 min)	On (3 min)
Plugin OpenWeather	On (1 hr)	On (1 hr)
Plugin TinyBlackBox	Not Used	Not Used
Used sensors	29	23

A.3 Insights from the Pilot

During the 83 days of the pilot, we collected 29 different data sources from the XPE phone and 23 from the BSE phones (due to hardware limitations). Although we cannot claim that all of them are useful, we compared our pilot dataset to existent datasets in 2015. Our dataset (D1) has ≈ 290 million data points (see Table A.4). In comparison to existing smartphone datasets for PD monitoring (D2 & D3), D1 has a higher resolution (70,972 records per person per monitored hour (R/P/Hr)) and semantic richness (29 sources). This means, D1 is 34.5x bigger than D3, and although it is 5x smaller than D2, the latter has only one source. Furthermore, when compared to other smartphone datasets (D4, D5, D6) in the context of behavioural inferencing (but not PD), D1 has 5.6x more R/P/Hr than the closest dataset.

Table A.4: Comparison of our pilot dataset to *PD* and non-*PD* smartphone collected dataset in the literature.

Dataset	Sources	R/P/Hr
<i>D1</i>	29	70,972
<i>D2</i> (Hammerla et al., 2015)	1	359,243
<i>D3</i> (The Michel J. Fox Foundation, 2013)	7	2,060
<i>D4</i> (Reyes-Ortiz et al., 2015)	2	12,500
<i>D5</i> (Rawassizadeh et al., 2014)	8	183
<i>D6</i> (Laurila et al., 2012)	15	44

Based on our pilot dataset, the nature of Parkinson’s symptoms (Jankovic, 2008), the assessment tasks of the MDS-UPDRS (Goetz et al., 2008), and everyday human activities that might be influenced by PD symptoms according to the literature (e.g. (Daneault et al., 2012; Liddle et al., 2014)), we identified five behavioural areas that are amenable to computation and potentially relevant to track Parkinson’s symptoms.

1. Typing patterns. Based on keyboard use, we can compute typing errors (backspace strokes), keystrokes per day, typing speed and typing sessions metrics. Computer and mobile typing have been linked to Parkinson’s motor symptoms (Arroyo-Gallego et al., 2017; Giancardo et al., 2016).
2. Phone usage patterns. Based on the screen’s lock, unlock and touchscreen events, we can extract metrics like tap duration, pressure, and frequency. These could be proxies to upper limb motor impairment as explored in a task-based study with people with Parkinson’s and essential tremor (Montague et al., 2014).
3. Episodes of going up/downstairs. Based on the GPS, WiFi, and barometer sensors, we can extract climbing stairs episodes (count and duration) and stratify them by day and night. We theorise that metrics like walking speed while using the stairs are a proxy to gait disturbances since gait’s stride amplitude, stride speed, height of foot lift, heel strike, turning, and arm swing are affected by Parkinson’s.
4. Mobility patterns. Based on location and activity recognition data, we can extract mobility metrics like time at home, community trips, or travelled

distance (Liddle et al., 2014) and stationary, walking, or running episodes. Research has suggested an inverse proportional trend exists between Parkinson’s symptom severity and reduced physical activity (Fertl et al., 1993; Friedman et al., 1993) as well as the three mobility metrics cited above.

5. Social interaction patterns. Based on Bluetooth, WiFi, and communication logs, we can extract the number and frequency of Bluetooth and WiFi devices as a proxy to human interaction (the number of such devices being different between residential and public areas) as well as the frequency and duration of incoming and outgoing calls and texts. We theorise communication metrics are a proxy to social support, which is a construct measured in quality of life in Parkinson’s (Peto et al., 1998).

Proxy features to physical constructs like time at home, as opposed to digital constructs like screen taps, require validation that is out of the scope of this work because participants need to collect ground truth data. During our main study (see Chapter 4), participants were already self-reporting daily symptom severity and so we considered any other collection request detrimental for recruiting and study adherence. Thus, we rely on algorithms available in the literature.

As an exploratory exercise, we analysed three 10-day bins of p02’s location, Bluetooth, and WiFi data to extract social interaction and mobility metrics (Figure A.1). The first row of graphs contains Bluetooth (BT) data. The x-axis represents time, and each cross in the y-axis represents a different BT device detected over the monitored period. Two devices (A and B) are detected over several days (framed by horizontal red rectangles), they can be a proxy to measure regular social interaction with other people. Devices framed by a vertical blue rectangle are detected within a single day; they can be a proxy to periods with high social interaction (either smartphones or beacons in places like malls). Devices in green circles are detected continuously over several hours; they can be a proxy to sustained social interaction (e.g., a conversation). The second row of graphs contains location (GPS) and Geographical Information Systems (GIS) data. Points represent a latitude-longitude pair sensed over the monitored period. Circles highlight the most significant location clusters that combined with GIS data are a proxy to the most frequented places (e.g., home, supermarket, park, etc.). They can also be a proxy to city level mobility and routine; for example, during days 11 to 20, p02 did not visit the residential area that he frequented during the first ten days, and during the last 10, he visited a new location avoiding

the Community Centre. The third row of graphs contains the same data as the second one, visualised on a bigger scale (countrywide). During the first 10 days, p02 made a day trip to a nearby location (two circles, first column), in the next 10 days he stayed in his town (circle, second column) and finally, in the last 10 days, he went to the south coast of England (bottom circle, third column). This data can be a proxy to holiday periods (time spent out of town) and travelled distance. We could combine and weight different metrics coming from these data sources into a unified score that represents the social interaction of a patient.

At the end of the pilot we obtained the following insights that inform our main monitoring study:

- Five behavioural areas possibly related to Parkinson’s symptoms that we can explore. Typing patterns, phone usage patterns, episodes of going up/down stairs, mobility patterns and social interaction patterns.
- Our data collection suite (Aware plus other Android apps) was not suitable for longitudinal data collection. P01’s phone lost $\approx 50\%$, and p02 $\approx 15\%$ of accelerometer data during the first six weeks of the study due to a read-write conflict between Aware and Automate’s backup routine. Accordingly, during the subsequent weeks, we stop Aware’s sensing between 1.45 a.m. and 2.45 a.m. to allow time for the backup. Also, there was a bug in “Ultimate Synchronize” that reduced the phone’s battery life by approximately 30%. As a temporary solution, we disabled this app and switched to manual sync, but we planned to find a syncing alternative as it is not feasible to manually backup data every week for one year.
- The impact of battery life on the smartphones’ UX was significant. P03 dropped out of the study after three weeks since he was getting 8 hours of battery time presumably due to his phone usage patterns, his location in a rural area, and his double SIM configuration (in our tests the phone collected data continuously for 20 hours).
- The BSE and XPE phones were suitable phones to collect data. Once the read/write and backup problems were resolved, p01 and p02 carried their phones without issues. BSE’s battery life spanned three days as a secondary device (p01), and XPE’s battery life lasted for ≈ 18 hours as p02’s primary device. Since the XPE has more sensors than the BSE, we chose the XPE phone as the monitoring device for our main study.

Figure A.1: Bluetooth (BT) and location data of p02 recorded during 30 days. Social interaction can be modelled based on the BT devices logged around the patient (top row). From this data it can be inferred how many people are around the patient (blue boxes), how often (red boxes) and for how long (green circles). Mobility can be modelled based on GPS and GIS information (middle and bottom row). From this data, it can be inferred patient’s daily routine (change over time in the second row), most frequented places (orange circles), holiday periods (third row) and activities of daily living.

Appendix B

Ethics protocol approval

The ethics protocols for our pilot and main monitoring study were amendments to a previous study's protocol carried out in partnership with researchers of the Division of Neuroscience and Experimental Psychology, from the School of Biological Sciences of the University of Manchester. After the pilot, it took nine months from 26/Jan/2016 to 01/Nov/2016 to get the final study design approved by the UK's National Health Service (NHS) and its Health Research Authority (HRA).

- 26th January 2016 - Substantial amendment 1 submitted to NHS ethics committee for approval. Extended smartphone testing from 12 weeks to 12 months.
- 1st February 2016 - Substantial amendment 1 approved by NHS.
- 11th May 2016. We discussed the study's design with researchers and Parkinson's experts Prof. Sonja Kotz, Dr Ellen Poliakoff and Dr Samuel Couth.
- 2nd June 2016 - Substantial amendment 2 submitted to NHS ethics committee for approval. Inclusion of focus groups and interviews with PD consultants/clinicians/specialists.
- 7th June 2016 - Substantial amendment 2 approved by NHS. Automatically sent for Health Research Authority (HRA) review.
- June/July 2016 - Iteration of several amendment drafts.
- 8th August 2016 – HRA approval for substantial amendment 2. This was a new process introduced around early July.
- 23rd August 2016 - Substantial amendment 3 submitted to the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medical and Health Sciences. Inclusion

of more tests and frequent assessment over the 12-month monitoring period, as per our protocol.

- 1st September 2016 - Substantial amendment 3 submitted to NHS ethics committee for approval.
- 15th September 2016 - Substantial amendment 3 approved by NHS. Automatically sent for HRA review.
- 1st November 2016 - HRA approval for substantial amendment 3.

Appendix C

Contributions to the Aware Framework

12th December 2018

To whom it may concern:

I am writing this letter at the request of MSc. Julio Vega, to highlight his contributions to the AWARE framework since January 2017. I've developed and evaluated an interdisciplinary and collaborative context instrumentation middleware, AWARE (<http://www.awareframework.com>), for researchers, developers and end-users, where raw sensor data from hardware-, software- and human-based sensors are converted to high-level context, shared transparently among other applications, sensors and humans alike. AWARE is one of the first context instrumentation frameworks that considers the wide range of interrelated sources of context information and the relationships amongst them, including the user's individual and social behaviour. More importantly, it is a platform accessible to non-technical researchers, which allows remote, distributed and large-scale user studies, providing a better understanding of people in the real world, and is not restricted to a laboratory setup. Today, AWARE is open-source (Apache 2.0) and freely available to academia and industry alike in a public GitHub repository and it's been exploited in both scientific and commercial products.

I had the pleasure of getting to know Mr. Vega's during his ongoing doctoral degree at the University of Manchester, UK. Mr. Vega's effort and dedication to his research and coursework inspire me greatly. His first contribution to AWARE was on improving the robustness of WiFi Access Point scanning. This quickly followed by improvements into power saving strategies using our significant motion sensor to eliminate redundant data collection from high-frequency sensors (accelerometer, gyroscope, etc.). Other improvements on the client (disabling non-existing device sensors), memory leaks due to open database connections, proper handling of secure connections and encryption of the local databases and scalable remote data synching were pivotal to the core client functionality. In a nutshell, Mr. Vega contributions were significant to the widespread adoption of the Android client. We can only be extremely thankful to his work on the framework.

Should you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Yours sincerely,

Denzil Ferreira

Appendix D

Project constraints for self-reporting prototypes

Our design process was delimited by the following constraints. Per our ethics protocol, we had three six-week design cycles with an equal number of sessions to deploy a new prototype or get feedback from our users. We had a budget to buy technology of approximately £30 per participant. Participants' smartphones were upgraded to Android 6 as a result of a technical fault that forbade continuous Bluetooth sensing in Android 5.1.1 on a Moto X Play device using the Aware Framework. In consequence, any technology-based developed prototype had to be compatible with Android 6 and the chipset Qualcomm MSM8939 inside the Moto X Play.